

**ASSESSMENT OF ELECTRONIC PUBLIC PROCUREMENT READINESS IN
GOVERNMENT DEPARTMENTS**

by

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the dissertation submitted for the degree M Tech: Logistics at the Tshwane University of Technology is my own original work and has not previously been submitted to any other institution of higher education. I further declare that all sources cited or quoted are indicated and acknowledged by means of a comprehensive list of references.

DN Maepa

DEDICATION

This dissertation is dedicated to my parents, 'Mama le Mama, mother and grandmother' who have been the pillars of my life, as God blesses me as a result of their prayers. I am blessed to have you in my life. I still want to say 'ke leboga go mmenagane, thank you very much' for everything you have done for me. I could not have done it without you by my side.

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'For with God nothing shall be impossible' - Luke 1:37

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ABSTRACT

Governments all around the globe are using information and communication technology to improve the quality of public procurement services. Slow adoption of electronic public procurement (e-PP) in South Africa raises questions regarding the reasons behind this. This study was motivated by a lack of understanding of the factors that affect e-PP readiness and the main e-PP readiness challenges in South Africa. Readiness assessment presents an opportunity for public procurement reform.

The study focused on the e-PP readiness of five identified national government departments from the ministerial clusters in South Africa. These government departments included economic sectors, investment, employment and infrastructure development; social protection, community and human progress; improvement of governance, development of state capacity and institutions; justice, crime prevention and security; and international cooperation, trade and security ministerial clusters. This study assessed the readiness of South African government departments to adopt e-PP. A descriptive design was adopted to collect quantitative information among 113 public procurement officials working for five national government departments in South Africa. These officials were selected using probability, cluster sampling techniques. Data were collected using self-administered questionnaires and in addition, frequency distribution presentation and discussion, factor analysis, reliability analysis, Chi-Square test and ANOVA were performed to determine factors that affect e-PP readiness as well as the relationships

between e-PP readiness challenges and its adoption and selected demographic variables.

Six factors were found to affect e-PP readiness in South African government departments. These factors included the technology and legal framework. The findings also showed that three factors influence e-PP readiness challenges, which included a lack of staff enthusiasm. Government can therefore take into account these factors when deciding on e-PP readiness and streamline procurement processes in the South African public sector.

Keywords:

Public procurement, electronic procurement, electronic public procurement, electronic readiness, electronic public procurement adoption, government departments

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

ADB: Asian Development Bank

ANOVA: Analysis of Variance

Chi²: Chi-Square Test

CIPS: Chartered Institute of Purchasing and Supply

CSCMP: Council of Supply Chain Management Professionals

CSD: Central Supplier Database

CSFs: Critical Success Factors

DHA: Department of Home Affairs

DMRE: Department of Mineral Resources and Energy

DOH: Department of Health

DOI: Diffusion of Innovation

DOT: Department of Tourism

DSBD: Department of Small Business Development

DTPS: Department of Telecommunications and Postal Services

e-Commerce: Electronic Commerce

ECTA: Electronic Communications and Transactions Act

e-Government: Electronic Government

e-informing: Electronic Informing

e-MRO: Electronic Maintenance, Repair and Operating

e-PP: Electronic Public Procurement

e-Purchasing: Electronic Purchasing

e-readiness: Electronic Readiness

e-Reverse auctioning: Electronic Reverse Auctioning

ERP: Enterprise Resource Planning

e-Sourcing: Electronic Sourcing

eTender: Electronic Tender publication portal

e-tendering: Electronic Tendering

EU: European Union

ICT: Information and Communication Technologies

IT: Information Technology

KMO: Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin

LOGIS: Logistical Information System

MDB: Multilateral Development Bank

OCPO: Office of the Chief Procurement Officer

OECD: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

PCA: Principal Component Analysis

PEOU: Perceived Ease of Use

PU: Perceived Usefulness

SAP: System Administrative Processes

SCM: Supply Chain Management

SITA: State Information Technology Agency

SMEs: Small and Medium Enterprises

TAM: Technology Acceptance Model

TRA: Theory of Reasoned Action

UNCITRAL: United Nations Commission on International Trade Law

UTAUT: Uniform Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION

This study assesses the readiness of government departments to adopt electronic public procurement (e-PP) in South Africa. In the final chapter of this study (Chapter 5), recommendations are made to assist government departments to benefit from e-PP adoption and streamline public procurement. This chapter provides background to selected and relevant concepts related to e-PP and readiness. The chapter also provides a literature overview followed by the research problem and research objectives. The research methodology, ethical considerations, limitations of the study and chapter outline are then explained. The chapter ends with a conclusion.

1.2. BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

The advent of the Internet provided an opportunity for governments to reverse the trend of costly, time-consuming, and inefficient public procurement (Patel, Kumar & Khajuria, 2016:264; Singh, Ismail, Wei, Imran & Ahmed, 2020:424). The National Treasury has initiated phases in transforming the South African public sector procurement from a traditionally paper-based to a partially electronic system (National Treasury, 2016:6; Mpehle & Mudogwa, 2020:2). This initiative aims to curb the red tape, remove barriers to conduct business with the state, and to allow public procurement to perform key functions

pertaining to service delivery and improvement of performance of government departments (Dzuke, 2017:1; Anthony, 2018:46).

Procurement reforms in South Africa are coordinated by the Office of the Chief Procurement Officer (OCPO) created in 2013 to maintain the procurement system and oversee the manner in which government conducts business with the private sector (National Treasury, 2013). The OCPO initiative to modernise and improve current archaic procurement began with the establishment of Central Supplier Database (CSD) and electronic tender (e-tender) publication portal. Kramer (2016:35) and Manyathi (2019:113) state that the introduction of the CSD and e-tender has impelled public sector procurement in South Africa to be more efficient and cost effective because of the adoption of modern technology that permits partial use of e-PP.

As the South African government annually spends about R900 billion on procuring goods, works and services (National Treasury, 2018:1), a need for corrective action is obvious to ensure alignment with and adherence to the relevant section 217 (1) of the Constitution of South Africa. According to this section of the Constitution (1996), when the government procures goods or services, it must do so in accordance with a system “that is fair, equitable, transparent, competitive and cost effective” (Constitution, 1996). Implementing e-PP is vitally important. When implemented properly, billions of rand can be saved, and better services delivered across the country.

The term *e-PP* refers to the use of information and communications technology (ICT) in the public sector to automate and create more responsive and dynamic procurement processes (Cucciniello, Gasco, Nasi, & Yuan, 2018:2342). According to Masudin, Aprilia, Nugraha and Restuputri (2021:11), *e-PP* has emerged as a method to reclaim lost procurement integrity, to increase transparency, and limit potential for corruption. The development of *e-PP* depends more on putting the policy, strategic planning, management, and government elements in place, rather than just the actual application of ICT. This would therefore indicate the necessity of electronic readiness (*e-readiness*) of government departments and other public entities to adopt *e-PP* as policy.

Roy and Upadhyay (2017:67) posit that *e-readiness* determines the ability of an entity to apply ICT. Ali and Alrayes (2014:221) find that *e-readiness* assessment is useful as it enables concrete planning and encourages positive changes in government departments. Shukla, Khan, and Shah (2016:3) state that readiness assessment can help *e-PP* to expedite procedural execution times, simplify processes, ensure constant monitoring of public expenditure, as well as sufficient time for strategic thinking and transparency due to uniform success. It is, therefore, argued in this study that *e-PP* readiness assessment creates an opportunity for public sector procurement reform and for changing the way procurement is being conducted, with the purpose of enhancing procurement effectiveness. The study therefore seeks to assess *e-readiness* of *e-PP* adoption in South African government departments.

1. 3 LITERATURE OVERVIEW

This section provides an overview of the literature on e-PP readiness that was reviewed for this study. Chapter 2 contains a detailed discussion and review of the literature. The discussion covers technology adoption models, an overview of manual public and electronic procurement, electronic readiness factors in e-PP adoption, and the conceptual framework.

1.3.1 Technology acceptance model

This study uses the technology acceptance model (TAM) as a theoretical framework to investigate the readiness of South African government departments to adopt of e-PP. The TAM, proposed by Davis (1989), has been used in several research studies, and as a result it has gained prominence in the literature on technology adoption (Mailizar, Burg & Maulina, 2021:7059; Dirsehan & Van Zoonen, 2022:199; Rosli, Saleh, Ali, Abu Bakar, & Mohd Tahir, 2022:3). The primary purpose of TAM is to anticipate the adoption of new technology among users and to reveal information system design flaws before its widespread use. TAM is a classic theory that describes the range of human behaviour when it comes to accepting and adopting new technologies (Sulistyaningsiha & Hanggraenib, 2021:5327). According to Kamal, Shafiq, and Kakria (2020:4), user willingness is a vital factor in the successful adoption and utilisation of technology.

The TAM model has two major components: perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU) (Mathieson, 2001:178). These two components have a significant impact on user attitude (attitude of use) and determine users' behavioural intention (intention of use) to adopt new technology (Bhattarai & Maharjan, 2020:132), which in turn estimates the actual system utilisation (Alswaigh & Aloud, 2021:223). The PU focuses on the degree to which a user anticipates advantages from technology, whereas the PEOU indicates the degree to which users expect fewer barriers to technology usage (Davis, 1989:320). Several studies have utilised the TAM model to investigate factors that may influence technology and e-PP adoption in Indonesia (Odi & Erma, 2020), Tanzania (Siwandeti, Sanga & Panga, 2021), South Africa (Swart, Sotiriadis & Engelbrecht, 2019), Kenya (Omenda, 2019) and Ghana (Ofori & Fuseini, 2020).

The advancement of technology causes disruptions that might have a detrimental impact on the acceptability of technology in any organisation (Yigitcanlar & Cugurull, 2020:3). With the TAM evolving into a stable model that is often used and recognised as the most appropriate to forecast user acceptance (Odi & Erma, 2020:128; Mailizar, Burg & Maulina, 2021:7059), it will be possible to accurately comprehend how public procurement officials embrace a system. As a result, the TAM will lead to increasing e-PP adoption.

1.3.2 Public procurement and electronic procurement

For government to function, it requires goods, works and services. The government may buy such goods, works, or services using its own resources or by contracting with other

entities, which is known as *public procurement* (Neupane, Soar, Vaidy, & Yong, 2012:22; Kusi, Antwi, Nani, Mensah & Akomeah, 2016:634; Adjei-Bamfo & Maloreh-Nyamekye, 2019:2). In nearly every country, public procurement plays a critical role in the growth of the national economy, making it crucial (Asian Development Bank, 2013:ix). Turley and Perera (2014:v) and Ambe (2016:2016) contend that for the South African government, procurement is both a strategic instrument and a mechanism for implementing policies for socioeconomic transformation.

Governments all over the world are embracing ICT to improve the quality of public procurement services to promote social and economic prosperity (Boakye, Asante & Dadzie, 2019:67; Ekpendu, 2021:32). The effort to reverse traditional procurement processes can only be effective and efficient if there is a readiness to adopt ICT to monitor procurement processes across the public sector. According to Rouse (2019), ICT refers to communication technology, such as networking components, systems and applications that individuals and organisations utilise to engage in the digital world. The Department of Telecommunications and Postal Services (DTPS) (2017:5) sees ICT as a significant enabler for governments worldwide in their attempts to offer improved services and efficiency while strengthening their relationships with citizens and businesses. As a result, ICT is highly regarded as a tool for setting the government's service delivery standards and monitoring overall performance.

The introduction of ICT has the potential to create opportunities for growth in public sector procurement through the removal of any procedural impediments, speeding up

communication and processes to modernise administration (Boakye *et al.*, 2019:67; Ahmad, 2021:564). These ICT benefits have been influential in public procurement within national departments worldwide where e-PP has been implemented (Ali & Alrayes, 2014:220; Amukanga & Otuya, 2020:22). An examination of various institutions that have adopted e-PP worldwide (i.e., the national governments of Italy, New Zealand, Australia, South Wales and Kenya) suggests that e-PP can be a successful tool in improving procurement processes in socio-technical and institutional environments (Department of Finance and Administration, 2005:1; Chen, Bretschneider, Stritch, Darnall & Hsueh, 2021:4). Orina (2013:14) argues that institutions that have adopted e-PP describe a roadmap of the unique e-PP activities, provide background on decisions made and the e-PP activities that are being currently utilised. Furthermore, government needs to be fully involved from the onset in the e-PP adoption preparation and have a vision and strategies for an e-PP system (Orina, 2013:14).

1.3.3 E-readiness and e-PP adoption

Merriam-Webster Dictionary (2022) defines *readiness* as "the state of being ready". The *state* refers to readiness aspects (discussed in section 2.3.3). Priambodo, Sasmoko, Abdinagoro, and Bandur (2021:867) define *e-readiness* as a measure to determine whether or not an organisation is ready to adopt, use, and profit from e-PP. E-readiness is described as the extent to which a country, government, or community is prepared and capable of participating in the networked world in terms of their relative knowledge and readiness in most of the critical aspects for the adoption (Centre for International

Development, 2000; Kalui, 2019:33; Al Khalifa, Dey & Sarea, 2021:411). According to Koyu, Singh, Kalai, Laitonjam and Meena (2018:118), e-readiness is the ease of use and access to information technology (IT) infrastructure, as well as the policies to sustain and participate in the worldwide global network.

The assessment of e-readiness is essential in order to identify key characteristics of e-PP that are desired, as well as some advances that should be avoided. According to Pal, Singh, and Dhaliwal (2020:94), measuring e-readiness entails “examining electronic connectivity, knowledge, attitude, and abilities to use ICT”, as well as confidence in utilising ICT. The e-readiness of an organisation is determined by examining its relative progress in the areas that are most important for ICT adoption (Goh & Blake, 2021:2).

According to Oppong (2020:26), e-PP streamlines procurement processes to reduce the time and cost of doing business for government and service providers and/or suppliers, standardise procurement processes across government departments, achieves better value for money spent through increased competition, provides equal opportunity to all service providers and/or suppliers, and in the end reduces corruption. For Ahmed (2018:14), the purpose of adopting e-PP is to improve efficiency and transparency in public procurement by implementing a complete e-PP solution that will be used by all government departments. The necessity to solve the various challenges connected with the existing paper-based procurement method demands the adoption of e-PP (Ofori & Fuseini, 2020:30).

1.3.4 Readiness factors in e-PP adoption

Orina (2013:10) found that, for smooth e-PP adoption, government departments should be ready in terms of operating environment, legal, economic organisational and technology environment. These factors should be clearly outlined by the government to minimise adoption challenges during implementation.

In the operating environment, government needs to consider aspects such as procurement structures, e-PP support levels and the drivers of e-PP adoption. Regarding legal aspects, government needs to consider local, national, and international jurisdiction in relation to readiness. The local, national, and international legislation may be a hindrance to adoption of e-PP as the government may be forced to amend some of its laws to accommodate e-PP implementation requirements (Kramer, 2016:3; Anthony, 2018:44). The economic environment relates to both the supplier and buyer, who should be able to meet the costs of implementing and running the e-PP system. The organisational environment focuses on the planned level of adoption and considers the financial impact of the e-PP adoption. The technology environment is concerned with the government putting in place required infrastructure at all levels to efficiently disseminate the e-PP service (Orina, 2013:10).

1.3.5 Readiness challenges in e-PP adoption

The slow e-PP adoption in South Africa raises questions as to what challenges its adoption faces (Makau, 2014:1; Patel, Kumar & Khajuria, 2016:264). The readiness

challenges of government departments related to e-PP adoption include resistance to change, lack of IT and Internet skills, and lack of staff enthusiasm (Orina, 2013:34). The United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (2018:3) identifies the mindset change of procurement officials to embrace new procurement approaches and practices as the main readiness challenge in the introduction of an new procurement system, including e-PP.

In South Africa, government departments use various operating systems to deliver services to citizens. This challenge has been acknowledged by National Treasury (2015:59) that states that there are fragmented and underutilised procurement systems to support supply chain management (SCM) processes in the public sector. This leads to fragmented data, varied compliance levels and poor performance (National Treasury, 2015:63).

1.4 RESEARCH PROBLEM

The fast-growing adoption of ICT has made a paradigm shift to the view as to how procurement processes should be performed because of various technological innovations being factored into the current public procurement system. Currently, a dual public procurement system is utilised in government departments comprising paper-based and electronic-based features (i.e., CSD and e-tender portals), whereas the paper-based system is associated with inefficiency and corruption (Koto & Kanjere, 2021:66). It is widely recognised that introducing an e-PP system to replace a paper-based

procurement system can potentially lead to substantial improvements in public procurement, such as transparency, efficiency, and effectiveness (Asian Development Bank, 2013:10; Sunmolaa & Shehu, 2020:1587). However, a fully adopted e-PP system can, to a large extent, aid to enhance the efficiency of procurement processes and minimise corrupt practices within government departments. This study only focuses on the electronic-based feature and assesses readiness factors affecting adoption challenges within government departments in South Africa.

Although several studies have investigated e-PP readiness in the public sector in developing economies such as Kenya (Orina, 2013), Ghana (Siita, 2014) and Indonesia (Nugroho, 2015), an extensive search of various databases including SABINET, indicated that the readiness of government departments to adopt e-PP has been scarcely investigated in South Africa. A lack of knowledge exists on the readiness factors affecting e-PP adoption in the South African context. In addition, the readiness challenges faced by government departments in the adoption of e-PP in South Africa may not be well known. This study therefore sought to fill this knowledge gap in literature.

1.5 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The main objective of the study is to assess the readiness factors of e-PP that affect the adoption challenges in the government departments of South Africa. From the main objective, the following secondary objectives are formulated:

- To determine readiness factors affecting the e-PP adoption in the South African government departments; and
- To determine the readiness challenges of e-PP adoption in South Africa's government departments and how these challenges can be addressed or dealt with.

1.6 BRIEF OVERVIEW ON RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology followed in this study is briefly described in this section. A detailed discussion of the research methodology is provided in Chapter 3. The discussion includes research philosophy, research design, sampling design (describing the population, sampling technique and sample size), data collection and research instrument, and data analysis.

1.6.1 Research philosophy

In basic ways, how one understands and uses theory impacts how one conducts research (Bell, Bryman & Harley, 2019:26). Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018:63) define research philosophy as a collection of ideas or principles to follow. Research philosophy relates to the researcher's assumptions about the world, which will support the research approach and methods used to attain the study objectives (Creswell & Clark, 2018:43). According to Strunk and Locke (2019:60), the research philosophy outlines how the research plan, research problem, data collection and analysis, findings, and

recommendations are developed. The philosophical approach used in this study was positivism, which is well suited to collecting and analysing quantitative data through a survey and determining the correlations between dependent and independent variables. Positivism regards reality as something that can be determined and expressed objectively via investigation (Leedy, Ormrod & Johnson, 2019:418).

1.6.2 Research design

Each research study requires a systematic plan to progress. According to Burns and Veeck (2020:62), research design is a master plan that outlines the techniques that will be utilised to collect and analyse data for a research project. The overall strategy for the investigation, according to Bairagi and Munot (2019:70), includes the type of study, data gathering techniques, experimental designs and statistical approaches for data sampling. This study used a descriptive research design to address the questions concerning who, what, where, when, and how government departments are ready to adopt e-PP (Hair Jr, Page & Brunsveld, 2020:164), as well as to better explain the phenomena of interest (Burns & Veeck, 2020:44). Descriptive research is conducted to collect data in order to get a thorough description, image, or attributes of a situation (Johnson & Christensen, 2020:1045). Descriptive studies are best suited for investigating and understanding a situation as it at present exists in the world (Leedy *et al.*, 2019:148).

1.6.3 Sampling design

Sampling is the process of selecting a sample from a population (Johnson & Christensen, 2020:677). Population refers to the number of all targeted and particular individuals on which data are generated from (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2020:180). This study targeted public procurement officials working at various levels of procurement in South African national government departments (i.e., low, middle and senior management service). The selection of these officials was made on the basis of their expertise, knowledge and direct involvement in procurement processes and decision making in various departments.

To ensure population representativity, the sample units were made from the sampled population (Kothari & Garg, 2019:153). Sampling units are the units that are chosen for or excluded from an analysis (Cohen *et al.*, 2018:676). The sample units for this study were five (5) identified national government departments from South Africa's government clusters in Section 3.4.2.1. Clustering is focused on bringing together departments that have similar, related or shared goals in order to achieve an integrated governance framework (Koma & Tshiyoyo, 2015:36).

The public procurement officials in each national government department cluster were chosen in this study using a probability, cluster sampling method. Each element has a known likelihood of being included in the sample when using probability sampling; however, non-probability sampling does not allow the researcher to determine this probability (Patten & Newhart, 2018:100). Cluster sampling is a sampling technique in

which the target population is partitioned into clusters or groups, which are then randomly sampled (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2019:321). A total of 150 public procurement officials from five national government department clusters participated in this study. This sample size is larger than the one used in a similar study that was estimated through Bartlett, Kotrlik and Haggins' (2001) computational method, provides a more accurate estimate of population values, and was determined in an economical and practical manner, as advised by Wiid and Diggins (2015:210). It was also informed by the researcher's budget, timing and risk constraints, as advised by Hair Jr *et al.* (2020:164).

1.6.4 Data collection and research instrument

Data collection is a method of obtaining responses to questions the researcher put to respondents (Burns & Veeck, 2020:284). This study employed primary and secondary data methods to gather information about e-PP readiness in South African government departments (Kumar, 2019:271; Chawla & Sondhi, 2015:11). The primary data for this study were collected from public procurement officials from the five national government department clusters, as pointed out in section 1.5.3, employing an online self-administered survey questionnaire. This study also employed secondary data on the trend of willingness and readiness to adopt e-PP by South African government departments. These data were pivotal in the discussion of primary data results and were sourced from dissertations and theses, books and journal articles, and internet, just to name a few.

The survey questionnaire used to collect primary data for this study was adapted from existing questionnaires used in similar studies conducted in developing countries such as Kenya (Orina, 2013), Ghana (Siita, 2014) and Indonesia (Nugraho, 2015) to suit the South African government context. This research practice seeks to ensure contextual relevance and avoid bias (Malhotra, Nunan & Birks, 2017:328).

The questionnaire used for data collection for this study was made up of three parts: Part A of the questionnaire consisted of demographic questions about the respondents, Part B dealt with factors affecting the e-PP readiness in South Africa's government departments, and Part C focused on the challenges related to e-PP readiness in South Africa's government departments. A five-point Likert scale (where 5 represents "strongly agree", and 1 represents "strongly disagree") was employed to collect data on the extent to which respondents agreed and disagreed with the statements of Part A and Part B of the questionnaire. Some dichotomous questions were also included in the questionnaire to ensure clarity and unequivocal meaning.

1.6.5 Data analysis

Data analysis is the process that summarises data in an easy-to-understand manner (Bell *et al.*, 2019:12). It entails identifying and measuring variance in a set of variables (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2019:11). In this study statistical analyses were performed using the Stata V15 statistical software package and included both descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics in the form of frequency distributions summarised findings

on demographic data of public procurement officials from the five national government department clusters revealing some dataset characteristics that needed further understanding through inferential statistics (see Chapter 4). Four types of inferential statistical analysis were performed: factor analysis, reliability analysis, Chi-Square test and a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The results of these analyses are provided and discussed in sections 4.4.1.2, 4.4.1.3, 4.4.2.1, 4.4.2.2, 4.5.1, and 4.5.2.

1.7 LIMITATIONS

This study has certain limitations. Firstly, the suspension of all non-COVID-19-related research due to the outbreak in South Africa disrupted the distribution of questionnaires to public procurement officials. Second, this study was limited to a sample of public procurement officials from five (5) identified national government departments in South Africa's ministerial clusters. Third, the literature on scholarly e-PP initiatives is quite limited, implying that e-PP adoption and implementation initiatives in the South African public sector are still in their early phases. The majority of studies have been undertaken in other countries, and this study relied on the literature from those studies.

1.8 CHAPTER OUTLINE

This dissertation consists of five chapters. Chapter 1 outlined the overall plan for this study and provided the background information on selected and relevant concepts related

to e-PP and readiness. It identified the research problem and formulated the research objectives. The chapter provided a brief overview on the research methods followed to answer the research objectives, and the limitations of this study. Chapter 2 discusses the literature on e-PP readiness. It starts with models of technology adoption, followed by a general review of public procurement and electronic procurement, and then moves on to a discussion of electronic readiness in e-PP adoption. The chapter also provides the conceptual framework and concludes with a summary. Chapter 3 details the research methodology used to meet the research objectives of this study. The chapter begins with a description of the research philosophy, then moves on to research design, sampling design, data collection and research instrument. Validity and reliability, data analysis and ethical considerations are also explained. The chapter ends with a summary of the research methodology discussed. Chapter 4 provides data analysis and findings. The chapter begins with the response rate, followed by a descriptive statistical analysis, factor analysis and inferential statistical analysis. It ends with a summary of key findings. Chapter 5 concludes this study by outlining the state of readiness for South African government departments to adopt e-PP. This chapter starts with the conclusions and recommendations for each secondary objective, then links secondary objectives to questionnaire questions, empirical findings, conclusions and recommendations. The chapter then discusses the study's limitations, suggests future research, and ends with a final word. **Figure 1.1** presents a graphical sketch of this dissertation.

Source: Own

FIGURE 1.1: Sketch of the study

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

All governments worldwide spend almost 11 trillion United States Dollar (USD) every year on public procurement (Fazekas & Blum, 2021:32). In South Africa, at least 42% of South Africa's national budget is spent on the acquisition of goods and services (Chipkin, Tshimomola & Brunette, 2014), which makes it an exorbitant number when juxtaposed to the overall national budget of South Africa. The South African public sector during the 2016/17 financial year, spent 938 billion Rand on procuring goods, works and services (National Treasury, 2018:1). This is an enormous amount of money and if used fittingly and efficiently, the money can be a great tool for service delivery to the citizenry of South Africa who need basic services (i.e., water, electricity and sanitation) and infrastructure (i.e., roads, schools and clinics).

Governments worldwide have realised the urgent need for transforming their procurement process to take full advantage of the potential offered by electronic commerce (e-Commerce) through replacing various phases of manual public procurement with electronic means. E-Commerce in general is a new concept in trade and provides many advantages, including the potential to reduce operating costs and simplify international trade (Mekhmonov & Temirkhanova, 2020:39).

Ahimbisibwe, Wilson and Ronald (2016:11) and Fazekas and Blum (2021:10) demonstrate that manual procurement systems have a significant effect on transaction costs of sourcing and payment of goods, works and services. The United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (2013:27) and Duma (2018:28) point out that manual procurement involves high levels of human contact, which presents a high risk of corruption. Keulemans and Van De Walle (2017:328) state that paper-based public procurement has always been plagued by favouritism. In South Africa, public institutions commonly utilise a traditional paper-based procurement system which is facing extensive criticism regarding corruption, inefficiency, and ineffectiveness (National Treasury, 2015; Daoud & Ibrahim, 2018:2). Therefore, there is a need for transformation with a dynamic transition to an electronic public procurement (e-PP) system that can be used for improved and swift delivery of services to citizens. According to the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (2013:27), the goal of e-PP is to primarily eliminate or minimise the direct human interactions between service providers and/or suppliers, and procurement officials, which is the main source of corrupt behaviour in public procurement.

E-PP is often part of the country's larger electronic governmental (e-Government) efforts to better serve its citizens and businesses in the digital economy (Bhaukaurally, Jaunky & Ramesh, 2017:11; Mohungoo, Brown & Kabanda, 2020:47). Nguyen, Phan, Le and Nguyen (2020:520) define e-Government as the use of technology, particularly the Internet, to provide public services to citizens, business and other government entities. E-Government is an enabling tool that aids governments to accomplish their developmental and administrative goals.

Many government departments around the world have identified e-PP as a government's priority agenda and have implemented the e-PP system to improve their daily working operations (Tutu, Kissi, Osei-Tutu & Desmond, 2019:2). Several scholars, such as Roy and Upadhyay (2017:67), have pointed out that "a country's e-readiness is essentially the degree to which a community is qualified to participate in the networked world. It is measured by judging the relative advance of the most vital extents for the adoption of information and communication technologies (ICT) and their most recent applications".

This chapter reviews the literature on e-PP readiness. It begins with models of technology adoption, then an overview of public procurement and electronic procurement, followed by a discussion on electronic readiness and ends with a summary.

2.2 MODELS OF TECHNOLOGY ADOPTION

To understand why users behave differently when adopting technology such as e-PP in government departments, different scholars have developed models of technology adoption. The technology adoption models most applicable to this study include the technology acceptance model (TAM), diffusion of innovation (DOI) and uniform theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT). These models are briefly discussed in the subsections that follow.

2.2.1 Technology acceptance model

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is one model that can be used to analyse the factors that influence a system's acceptability (Oturakci, 2018:43; Sari, 2020:5). TAM, according to Singh, Ismail, Wei, Imran, and Ahmed (2020:426), is about acknowledging that innovation acceptance is influenced by the user's feelings about the system and its perceived benefits. Mutuku (2020:37) points out that TAM is based on Fishbein and Ajzen's Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), which proposes that an individual's attitude toward carrying out a behaviour motivates that behaviour.

According to Sulistyaningsiha and Hanggraenib (2021:5327), TAM is a classic theory that identifies the range of human behaviour in accepting and implementing new technology. It is stressed that TAM predictions for user acceptance are based on perceived expediency and perceived ease of use (Davis, 1989; Davis, 1993). This model has been applied in a number of technology contexts, according to Brandon-Jones and Kauppi (2018:2) and Ramkumara, Schoenherrb, Wagnera, and Jenamanic (2019:335), and it provides recognised and proven explanations for technology usage. Afolabi, Ibem, Aduwo, Tunji-Olayeni and Oluwunmi (2019:15) explain that TAM shows how employees feel the innovative tool will increase their job productivity. This theory emphasises the relevance of how users feel (human behaviour) toward a specific instrument in determining whether or not they embrace a technology.

2.2.2 Diffusion of innovation

Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) refers to the process by which new technology is introduced into the field of development communication (Ali, Raza, Puaah & Amin, 2019:624). DOI is defined as "the process by which an innovation is communicated over time among members of a social system through specific channels" (Roger, 1995:11). Min, So, and Jeong (2018:3) describe *diffusion* in this context as a social process in which people communicate with others about the adoption of an innovation. DOI is a broad psychological theory that seeks to predict how people decide whether to adopt a new innovation by identifying adoption patterns and comprehending its structure (Rogers, 1995). Theorists most commonly employ this theory to investigate the formation and adoption of new ideas (Samoei & Ndede, 2018:393).

DOI theory, according to Issa (2020:11), is a prominent paradigm in the technological adoption spectrum that has been thoroughly investigated by previous researchers. By abandoning manual processes, the DOI has extensively demonstrated how people welcomed and used e-ordering and e-invoicing (Lamorte, 2019). This model has assisted organisations in understanding how prospective buyers implement and engage with new technology over time, as well as how an idea can progress through several stages of adoption by various players.

2.2.3 Uniform theory of acceptance and use of technology

The Uniform Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) is a model established by Venkatesh, Morris, Davis, and Davis (2003). According to Venkatesh *et al.* (2003:447), four elements impact a person's adoption of information technology (user acceptance): performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions. According to Ronaghi and Forouharfar (2020:5), *performance expectancy* refers to an individual's belief that using a technology would boost users' work performance. *Effort expectancy* is related to the degree of convenience of using technology (Rahi, Mansour, Alghizzawi & Alnaser, 2019:3). For Wan, Xie and Shu (2020:4), *social influence* refers to how individuals alter their behaviour to satisfy the needs of a social setting. *Facilitating conditions* are an individual's perceptions of the resources and support available to perform an action (Palau-Saumell, Forgas-Coll, Sanchez-Garcia, & Robres, 2019:6). These four elements greatly impact users' behavioural intention and usage (Cheng, Sharma, Sharma & Kulathunga, 2020:5).

The purpose of UTAUT is to define the level of user acceptance and behaviour when using information technology (Cheng, Sharma, Sharma & Kulathunga, 2020:5; Andwika, Witjaksono & Azizah, 2020:28). According to Chang, Chen, Xu, and Xiong (2021:4), UTAUT is a comprehensive and thorough model that is used to examine the process of technology adoption and the variables that encourage or discourage potential adopters from embracing innovation. Morchid (2019:78) adds that UTAUT not only synthesises

studies on technology usage and acceptance, but it also promotes a creative framework capable of detecting unique patterns of behaviour in a variety of situations.

This study used TAM as a theoretical framework to examine the readiness of South African government departments to adopt e-PP as the model emphasises that the attitudes and acceptance of public procurement officials towards the e-PP system should be studied prior to e-PP adoption.

2.3 PUBLIC PROCUREMENT AND ELECTRONIC PROCUREMENT

2.3.1 Public procurement

Australia's Chartered Institute of Purchasing and Supply (CIPS) defines *procurement* as the function of business management that ensures an organisation's identification, sourcing, accessing and management of the necessary external resources to reach its strategic aims (CIPS, 2013:5; Kwasi, 2020:33). Procurement is described as the process which is concerned with "developing and implementing strategies to manage an organisation's expenditure portfolio to contribute to the organisation's overall goals and maximise the total cost of ownership" (CIPS Glossary, 2017; Ahmed, 2018:23). In the public sector context, procurement is believed to be a vital function of government that is responsible for satisfying government requirements for goods, works and services in a timely manner (Yano & Nondi, 2018:292).

Government comprehends the potential of procurement to improve public sector productivity through savings and economies of scale (Gurria, 2016:3; Ambe, 2016:279; Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2019:3), as it is destined to meet public needs and ensures accountability for tax payers' money. This view is stressed by Abdallah (2015:42) who states that proliferating transparency and accountability is essential for economic development and ensuring value for money in public procurement. Manyathi (2019:165) assessed the influence of public procurement processes on service delivery and found a widespread lack of transparency in South Africa's public procurement. Based on this transparency deficit, it is argued that since public procurement accounts for a large portion of public resources, it is imperative that the process of procurement occurs in an accountable, transparent and well-managed manner to guarantee high quality service delivery and to protect the public interest (OECD, 2017). In the public sector, the procurement process is the sequence of activities which starts with the assessment of needs and then is followed by the awarding of contracts, contract management processes and finally payment (Ambe, 2016:278; Fourie & Malan, 2020:4).

The National Treasury along with the Office of the Chief Procurement Officer (OCPO) as the custodians of public procurement in South Africa require adherence by procuring entities to the laid down procurement process and procedures to achieve procurement performance in government departments (National Treasury, 2015:6). Amemba, Nyaboke, Osoro and Mburu (2013:43) assert that the public procurement process should sustain integrity through restricting malpractices in order to make informed decisions.

Public procurement is one of the elements within a supply chain focusing primarily on the locating and purchasing of goods, works and services within the supply value chain (Boateng, 2009; Gabela & Okeke-Uzodike, 2020:639). According to the Council of Supply Chain Management Professionals (CSCMP) (2013:187), SCM “encompasses the planning and management of all activities involved in sourcing and procurement, conversion, and all logistics management activities. Importantly, it also includes coordination and collaboration with channel partners, which can be suppliers, intermediaries, third party service providers, and customers”. Thus, SCM integrates supply and demand management within the public sector.

Public procurement is increasingly regarded as a vital tool for transforming society and represents a significant proportion of South Africa’s demand for goods, works and services. The function of procurement is a critical activity in the public sector and must be carried out efficiently and effectively (Musau, 2015:12; Fourie & Malan, 2020:4). Public sector efficiency is achieved through an efficient procurement function, among other things. A quest for effective and efficient procurement has been instrumental in the adoption of electronic procurement.

2.3.2 Electronic procurement

Following the increased adoption of Internet for organisational uses, the function of procurement is transitioning from traditional paper-based processes to e-PP (Bartai &

Kimutai, 2018:45; Boakye *et al.*, 2019:67). Chen, Bretschneider, Stritch, Darnall, and Hsueh (2021:4) view e-PP as an Internet-based purchasing system that provides buyers (i.e., government departments or any public entities) with electronic purchasing, order processing and enhanced administrative functions. Masudin, Aprilia, Nugraha and Restuputri (2021:1) define e-PP as the use of ICT technology to execute part or all of the procurement process. Suleiman (2015:145) describes e-PP as the use of integrated ICT to perform “procurement processes including searching, sourcing, negotiation, ordering, receipt and post purchase review”. According to Bhaukaurally, Jaunky and Ramesh (2017:11), e-PP is “the combined use of electronic ICT to enhance the links between customer and supplier with other value chain partners, thereby to improve external and internal processes; it is the key component of electronic business and e-Commerce”.

As one of the core enablers of electronic government, the applicable definition of e-PP in this study is automation of the procurement of goods, works and services through IT-based communication and processing, and replacement of paper-based means. This definition is adopted because it extrapolates the study context.

The purpose of e-PP is to ensure comprehensive and up-to-date public procurement systems for all government departments and public entities (Ahmed, 2018:14). He further points out that e-PP can play a pivotal role in improving the procurement process in respect of openness, efficiency and cost savings (Ahmed, 2018:24). It is argued that ICT-enabled technology such as e-PP plays a significant role in minimising the risk of corruption in public procurement processes (Mohungoo *et al.*, 2020:47).

The improvement of the e-PP process results in minimised errors in the supply of goods, works and services and minimised errors in the accounting process, and ensures faster payment procedures and fewer bureaucratic procedures (Cheseto, Gudda, Naikuni & Mbuchi, 2019:152). In fact, Kusi, Antwi, Nani, Mensah and Akomeah (2016:634) state that government departments will only be able to reduce administration and operational costs through the usage of e-PP as business processes are reduced and streamlined. And to optimise the efficiency of service delivery, a uniform public procurement system is essential (National Treasury, 2015:59).

As emphasised by Nawi, Roslan, Salleh, Zulhumadi and Harun (2016:330), e-PP “transforms the manual procurement practice into an electronic, Internet-based practice.” Compared to a paper-based procurement, e-PP is viewed as a standard, secure and reliable universal communication system (Kramer, 2016:1).

Electronic public procurement encompasses several elements including electronic ordering and automated procurement systems (Samoei & Ndede, 2018:388). Sometimes e-PP can be confused or used interchangeably with the term ‘electronic purchasing (e-Purchasing)’, which refers to simply conducting a transaction electronically. The transition of the procurement process to the Internet has the potential to benefit all facets of procurement including selection, bidding, payment, and inventory processes (Chandra, Narsireddy, Sastry, Sreedhar & Dasari, 2020:80). The transition arose from a need for better change management to convince service providers and/or suppliers to embrace change and utilise technology in the procurement process. E-PP solutions are a way to

address many public sector procurement requirements as e-PP adoption will lessen the administrative burden for both government and business and improve the supervising of procurement patterns, contracts and prices (National Treasury, 2016:6).

2.3.2.1 E-procurement technology adoption

The public sector's intentions have been significantly influenced by the adoption of new inter-organisational system technologies, of which e-PP enables connection between government departments and contractors through an online platform that automates the entire government's procurement process (Mahmood, 2013:120). According to Ahmed (2018:14), the vision of e-PP is to enhance the efficiency and transparency in public procurement through adoption of a comprehensive e-PP solution to be used by all government departments in the country. In the South African context, e-PP adoption can aid the OCPO within the National Treasury to plan procurements and make the procurement process impartial, fair and transparently managed.

The adoption of e-PP is necessitated by the need to address the numerous issues associated with the traditional paper-based procurement system (Ofori & Fuseini, 2020:30). As a result of these issues, it is essential to adopt an e-PP system that ensures all processes are carried out electronically, eliminating the need for any manual processes (Tutu *et al.*, 2019:2). Because times, norms, and government priorities have changed, the public sector SCM cannot continue to function in a manner what was considered appropriate during previous decades. However, e-PP is not a perfect solution

to all of the problems associated with manual procurement processes since it has its own set of concerns that might impede optimal attainment of the desired results (Kramer, 2016:17; Sithole, 2017:42). But the advantages of e-PP outweigh the disadvantages, and it is a viable panacea for reforming public sector procurement while maintaining its integrity.

The literature gives a complete categorisation of all the benefits realised in the private and public sectors following the introduction of an e-procurement system (Belisari, Appolloni & Cerruti, 2019:221). Adoption of e-PP technology will modernise public procurement and provide government with the opportunity to:

- Reduce the administrative burden of government and business;
- Provide consistent reporting of procurement information;
- Source strategically through better and smarter data procurement analysis; and
- Monitor procurement patterns, contracts and prices efficiently (National Treasury, 2015:60).

2.3.2.2 E-procurement systems

2.3.2.2.1 E-procurement systems globally

Although there are different types of e-PP systems that focus on one or several stages of the procurement process, e-PP is an end-to-end solution that consolidates and streamlines many procurement processes across organisations (Siita, 2014:11; Opong, 2020:27). De Boer, Harink and Heijboer (2002:26), in their study on assessing the impact

of various forms of electronic procurement on a firm's integral purchasing costs, identified various types of e-PP, including electronic maintenance, repair and operating (e-MRO), Web-based enterprise resource planning (ERP), electronic sourcing (e-Sourcing), electronic tendering (e-tendering), electronic reverse auctioning (e-Reverse auctioning), and electronic informing (e-informing). Each of these types of systems is designed for a specific purpose and has its own specific functionality and features (Neupane, Soar, Vaidy & Yong, 2012:306). Both e-MRO and Web-based ERP are able to create and approve purchase requisitions, place purchase orders and receive goods and services using Internet-based software (Ateto, Ondieki & Okibo, 2013:104). For e-MRO, the ordered goods and services are supplies of MRO, while the goods and services ordered are product-related in the case of Web-based ERP.

E-sourcing involves identifying new service providers and/or suppliers with IT for a category of purchasing requirements (Musau & Nyaboga, 2020:70). Another form of e-PP is e-tendering, which concerns the process of sending requests to service providers and/or suppliers for information and prices and receiving their responses using IT. E-reverse auctioning consists of buying goods and services from various known or unknown service providers and/or suppliers by means of IT (Ali & Alrayes, 2014:221; Tiwari, Chan, Ahmad, & Zaman, 2019:924). E-informing involves collecting and distributing information internally and externally through IT (De Boer *et al.*, 2002:26).

The main governmental agenda of developed and emerging economies is to make governments transparent, accountable, efficient, and effective (Mambo, Ombui & Kagiri,

2015:955). E-PP systems have already been introduced and utilised by developed countries in the public sector. For instance, Australia, New Zealand, the United States, Denmark and Japan have already implemented e-PP systems obtaining higher achievement and with numerous perceived benefits (Neupane *et al.*, 2012:312). However, the adoption and implementation of e-PP systems has been slow - due to readiness aspects (discussed in section 2.3.3), particularly in developing nations like Bahrain, Singapore, Malaysia, Turkey and India (Ali & Alrayes, 2014:220).

2.3.2.2.2 E-procurement systems in African governments

Most African governments have enacted public procurement reforms, but e-PP has yet to be widely adopted on the continent (Anthony, 2018:3). Consequently, the levels of public procurement reforms in African countries are not significantly different, and they were preceded by assessments of the existing procurement system (Dza, Fisher & Gapp, 2013:51). Before the introduction of public procurement reforms, many African governments relied on procurement systems from the colonial period (De la Harpe, 2015:1574). According to the World Bank, Africa's slow adoption of e-PP is due to a shortage of IT infrastructure and obsolete administrative cultures (Thomas, Abdoulaye, Frannie & Sithabile, 2007; Anthony, 2018:40). Dza *et al.* (2013:54) maintain that the problems confronting many countries in Africa are a lack of qualified personnel, practitioners' inability to adequately interpret procurement laws, and a high level of corruption. They also cite a lack of political commitment to fully commit to procurement reforms to remove one of the many barriers to the successful adoption and implementation of e-PP systems in Africa (Dza *et al.*, 2013:54).

As of 2018, Zambia joined Rwanda as one of Africa's early adopters of e-PP, with other countries in Africa following suit (World Bank, 2018:5). Manyathi (2019:76) investigated public procurement in African countries and discovered that South African public procurement lags behind its African counterparts in terms of legislative consolidation, innovation, and use of new technology in public procurement processes.

2.3.2.2.3 E-procurement systems in South Africa

The quest for improving service delivery tops the agenda for most government departments in South Africa (Mambo *et al.*, 2015:967). Since 2015, many innovations in SCM technology have been phased into the current manual system to establish a e-PP system in South Africa (National Treasury, 2016:6). Kramer (2016:6) attests that at this present moment, the e-PP platform in South Africa has only managed to modernise the archaic public procurement system with the introduction of electronic communication means between government procuring entities and potential suppliers.

The government of South Africa is in transition to retain the lost integrity of SCM, and enhance and modernise procurement in the public sector since its adoption of electronic features into procurement processes. Electronic features were introduced with the establishment of Electronic Tender (eTender) publication portal and Central Supplier Database (CSD), both managed by the OCPO to set the policy on contents and functionality, and coordinate the administration of both portals with users (National Treasury, 2015:1). And since their adoption, procurement processes are now simpler for the buyer (government departments) and the seller (service provider and/or supplier),

although this technology (eTender and CSD) is part of a fragmented and underused system as 45% of public procurement is still manually conducted (National Treasury, 2016:6; Ambe, 2016:287). These procuring technologies are discussed for background information.

eTender Portal

The eTender Publications Portal is one of the OCPO's initiatives to promote fair, transparent, competitive and cost-effective procurement in an accessible environment (National Treasury, 2016:7). The eTender publication portal aims to simplify and standardise the procurement process through publishing government notices, bids, advertisements and awards. The advertisement of bids and the publication of awards are among the constitutional requirement for goods, services and works to be procured in a manner that is “fair, equitable, transparent, competitive and cost effective” (National Treasury, 2015:1). The eTender portal service is an attempt to enhance opportunities for South African businesses to identify and compete for governmental bidding opportunities (National Treasury, 2015).

The eTender portal was introduced by the National Treasury on 1 April 2015 with the purpose of advertising all bid documents for tenders, providing a list of tenders and their respective prices, publishing cancellations and details of the winning bidder, and scores of the rest of the bidders by all government departments, constitutional institutions and public entities (National Treasury, 2016:7). This intervention has phased out

advertisements in newspapers and the government gazette (Nene, 2015:17). The eTender portal application ensures that all potential service providers and/or suppliers who wish to supply institutions and who are Public Finance Management Act (PFMA) compliant with their goods and services have easy access to advertised bids.

The eTender portal has been found to improve transparency and will increasingly reduce corruption and the number of tender disputes (National Treasury, 2016:7). Procuring entities have experienced cost reduction due to less need to print bidding documents since the introduction of the portal (National Treasury, 2015). Although the eTender portal has had a beneficial impact and continues to contribute to reducing duplication, fragmentation and inefficiency in the public sector and the corruption scourge is still a hindrance (National Treasury, 2016:7). Munzhedzi (2016) in his study labelled procurement practices and corruption in the South African public sector as inseparable twins. The eTender portal provides small and medium enterprises (SMEs) with opportunities to bid, but price tags on bidding documents still constitute a barrier for potential service providers and/or suppliers to get information of advertised tenders (National Treasury, 2015). Some public entities sell bidding documents and bidders must purchase these documents to be able to get tender information, including specification and terms of reference in order to prepare a competitive response (National Treasury, 2015).

In addition, public sector procuring entities are required to also advertise their bids and publish their awards in the Government Tender Bulletin (National Treasury, 2015:4). Both

eTender and the Government Tender Bulletin have increased fairness and competition since every service provider and/or supplier has access to the same information at any given time. E-Tender has removed the barrier of distance and/or location of potential bidders as they may be notified of advertised, cancelled and awarded bids by visiting the portal.

Central Supplier Database

The CSD is a single database that serves as the source of all supplier records for all spheres of government (Statistics South Africa, 2017). The introduction of the CSD on 1 September 2015 has significantly reduced the red tape surrounding means to do business with the South African government, as service providers and/or suppliers are no longer faced with substantial administrative burdens, incurring costs to buy database documents and to register on the databases of each department, municipality and public entity (National Treasury, 2016:7). Spheres of government before the advent of the CSD did not have a uniform and standardised registration process that verifies supplier information (National Treasury, 2016:1). Since its inception, with the mandate to provide consolidated, accurate, up-to-date, complete and verified supplier information, a dozen of service providers and/or suppliers have registered on the CSD. This has saved millions of South African Rands for government by eliminating duplication of registration of service providers and/or suppliers at different departments and public entities (National Treasury, 2016:7). From 1 April 2016, it became compulsory for service providers and/or suppliers who wish to do business with government to register on the CSD (National Treasury,

2016:7). Prospective service providers and/or suppliers who are interested to pursue business opportunities with government are required to register once on the National Treasury's database and are encouraged to utilise the simplified self-registration function on the CSD website (Nene, 2015:17).

The efforts and actions of government aimed to improve the performance of SCM and to prevent fruitless and wasteful expenditure. However, the rotation of suppliers is not incorporated in the CSD, as it is the responsibility of every department or any public entity to put supplier rotation policies in place to ensure fairness, openness and compliance (Mpehle & Mudogwa, 2020:7). The lack of rotational mechanism provides procurement officials with the opportunity to rotate their preferred service providers without the necessary service delivery capacity for personal gains, which affects service quality (Zitha, Sebola & Mamabolo, 2016:67).

2.3.2.3 E-procurement benefits and challenges

The way government departments perceive the benefits of e-PP will determine the level of the system adoption and it is highly likely that government departments will use e-PP if they are aware and confident of the adoption benefits. Such benefits include reduction of transaction errors and transaction costs, enhancing customer service, reduction of paper transactions, minimising order cycle and improved relationships with service providers and/or suppliers (Mohamed & Milimu, 2016:1185; Fazekas & Blum, 2021:10). Mose, Njihia and Magutu (2013:379) and Mpehle and Mudogwa (2020:4) opine that

service providers and/or suppliers should be informed about the e-PP benefits by way of consultation at the earliest possible time in the project. The gains of introducing e-PP in the public sector include ensuring the best tax payers' value for money, increased effectiveness and efficiency, consistent procurement practice across government departments and environmentally friendly practice due to a "paperless" process (Vaidya, Sajeev & Callender, 2006:91; Samoei & Ndede, 2018:388). These views are consistent with those of Svidronova and Nemeč (2016:324), who note that an efficient public procurement system could be a significant source of potential savings in the public sector.

Despite the various benefits offered by using e-PP, government departments in South Africa are likely to meet many challenges when adopting the e-PP system. These challenges are discussed in Section 2.4.4.

2.3.2.4 E-procurement critical success factors

Many factors can affect the readiness and willingness of government departments to adopt e-PP. Masudin *et al.* (2021:3) argue that, for public-sector institutions to become successful in adopting e-PP, it is vital for top management to comprehend the critical success factors (CSFs) associated with ICT adoption. Mose *et al.* (2013:375) assessed CSFs and challenges in e-procurement adoption in Kenya's private sector. They identified five CSFs, namely the commitment of employees and management to the success of e-procurement adoption; reliability of IT and supplier performance; monitoring the performance of e-PP system; user acceptance of e-PP system; and top management

support. These are some of the most important CSFs that government departments in South Africa need to consider in their efforts to transition from traditional paper-based procurement processing to e-PP.

Jain, Abidi and Bandyopadhyay (2018:103) posit that CSFs and challenges should be considered prior to e-PP adoption and implementation to assure everything is in place because adoption and implementation of e-PP can be a waste if carried out at the wrong time and/or the wrong place. Nawi *et al.* (2016:332) investigated the benefits and challenges of e-procurement implementation in a Malaysian company. They identified infrastructure and legislation, technology, resource constraints, environment, and organisational and management characteristics as contributing factors affecting the readiness, adoption and implementation of e-PP. These factors are therefore indicators of an organisation's willingness to adopt and implement e-PP.

The success of e-PP relies more on fundamental procurement aspects than electronic aspects. It is therefore vital for the public sector to prepare in terms of finances, infrastructure and legislation, human capital, technology, organisational structure and management support. This effort aims to ensure successful e-PP adoption and implementation, because a properly implemented e-PP system can connect government departments with service providers and/or suppliers while managing all interactions (Mose *et al.*, 2013:377; Ngeta & Kisimbii, 2020:16).

2.4 ELECTRONIC READINESS IN E-PP ADOPTION

2.4.1 E-readiness concept

Priambodo, Sasmoko, Abdinagoro and Bandur (2021:867) define electronic readiness (e-readiness) as a measure that indicates whether an organisation is ready or willing to adopt, use and benefit from e-PP. An e-readiness assessment is one of the main phases of technological development in any country, because it represents the transformation of society including transition from traditional relations and methods to more modern ways (Hassan & Fatimah, 2014:2). Brandon-Jones and Kauppi (2018:2) demonstrate the significance of readiness assessment following disappointing e-PP adoption levels and performance outcomes witnessed during e-procurement implementation at a university in the Netherlands.

In Africa, reluctant e-PP adoption was identified in Kenyan public organisations raising questions as to what challenges its adoption in the public sector faces (Kisang & Rotich, 2014:1). This seems to be a global trend and underlines the need for government departments in South Africa to conduct readiness assessments for employing a digitalised procurement system that will allow requisition, order and purchase of goods, works and services using the Internet. This view is consistent with that of Jain *et al.* (2018:91) who mention that expectations, level, structure and environment must be considered to enable successful e-PP adoption. It is expected in this study that the outcomes of assessing e-PP readiness in government departments can contribute

towards addressing some of the current procurement challenges faced in the procurement system in South Africa.

A study by Ali and Alrayes (2014:227) investigating the effect of e-readiness factors on e-PP adoption revealed that awareness surrounding the environment of e-procurement was significantly related to the adoption of e-PP in various governmental entities. It is believed that the effort to conduct readiness assessment can complement and create an opportunity for public procurement reform, strengthen the need for transition from traditionally paper-based to electronic procurement and change the way procurement is steered (Chipembele & Bwalya, 2016:319). The e-PP readiness assessment is meant to serve as an advisory tool and aims at:

- pointing out competences that must be in place to assure a reasonable basis for success in the e-PP development process;
- practically describing the conditions under which e-PP development will occur;
- informing broad and/or sectorial e-PP strategy and action plan development; and
- providing a monitoring and evaluation tool (UNDESA, 2018:42).

2.4.2 Case studies of e-PP readiness in selected countries

In this section, case studies of e-PP readiness in selected countries are provided for background information. These countries include Italy, Kenya and South Africa. These countries have been selected because of their different economic levels and experiences in adopting e-PP.

2.4.2.1 E-PP readiness in Italy

As the European Union (EU) transitioned from traditional to e-PP methods, one of the early adopters of e-PP in the EU was the Italian public sector (Sagar & Venkatesh, 2019:36). E-PP in Italy has promoted simple and innovative procurement procedures and micro-level initiatives that enable the efficiency and transparency of government operations through IT (Neupane *et al.*, 2012:313). The usage of e-PP in the Italian government has increased vastly since its adoption and appears to have fulfilled its economic justification as well as reaping additional benefits that comprise standardisation, transparency, fair competition and ease of ordering (Belisari *et al.*, 2019:235). Although e-PP is not compulsory throughout Italy, there are few states that do not opt to apply e-PP (Sagar & Venkatesh, 2019:37).

The Italian public administration attains savings and bigger efficiency because of e-PP adoption (Comite, 2014:1658). Neupane *et al.* (2012:313) attest that the e-PP system has been beneficial for Italy as it contributes to best quality of governance and increased competition among bidders. The government of Italy deemed change management necessary, developing a programme to communicate the value of the new business model (e-PP) and providing training to public administration bodies and particularly suppliers, because SMEs constitute a large portion of the economy and exert pressure for equal access to government business (Belisari *et al.*, 2019:235). The Italian government is conversant with understanding e-PP requirements and the changes e-PP brings to the traditional purchasing environment through continued interventions to

determine system challenges and provide a complete end-to-end solution for stakeholders (European Commission, 2004:137).

E-PP technology performance in Italy indicates that e-PP helps to promote competition among service providers and/or suppliers (Neupane *et al.*, 2012:313). As a result, this helps the Italian government to direct service providers and/or suppliers to the right government project. According to the European Commission, (2004:141), the Italian government obtained excellent governance since the implementation of e-PP system at government level.

2.4.2.2 E-PP readiness in Kenya

The government of Kenya in the recent past has undergone major public procurement developments and institutional strengthening (Bartai & Kimutai, 2018:49). Public institutions in Kenya are approaching e-PP technologies with various strategies based on the perceived risk and benefits associated with the technology, their competitive position and environment. E-PP has drastically improved on the lost time and errors emanating from the exchange of paper and retyping of data (Ateto *et al.*, 2013:104). By examining the procurement process in the Local Government Engineering Department of Bangladesh, Ahmed (2018:22) evaluated the transparency of e-PP in public procurement and found that time and cost are the significant measures to gauge the success of procurement processes. Furthermore, it should be highlighted that e-PP adoption has changed how government departments coordinate and structure the relationships of their

business by firstly cutting down the time and cost required to appoint a service provider and/or supplier (Ahmed, 2018:22).

Developing countries, including Kenya, recognise the benefits of adopting e-PP. Ali and Alrayes (2014:220) point out that e-PP adoption is becoming a top priority for countries seeking to improve and grow. Masudin, Aprilia, Nugraha and Restuputri (2021:3) posit that the overall benefits of e-PP may be low where there is lack of top management support; as for successful e-PP adoption at all levels, the support of top organisational actors is critical. According to Ngeta and Kisimbii (2020:14), the Kenyan procurement system plays a most important role in utilising government resources and achieving the economic development agenda.

2.4.2.3 E-PP readiness in South Africa

The readiness of e-PP in South Africa was discussed in section 2.2.2.2.2. The South African government's e-PP is in its infant stage as it was introduced six years ago (in 2015). Instead of meeting the requirements for goods, works and services in a timely manner, the procurement of government departments in South Africa has proven to be long, cumbersome and time consuming (Ambe, 2016:279; Fourie & Malan, 2020:8). The adoption of e-PP is commonly faced with many challenges and predicaments, as most public sector institutions are still struggling with the proper adoption of e-PP (Patel, Kumar & Khajuria, 2016:264; Mohungoo *et al.*, 2020:47).

The reviewed three governments (i.e., Italy, Kenya and South Africa) describe unique e-PP activities and background on why and how procurement decisions were made and implemented and what e-PP activities are currently performed.

2.4.3 Readiness factors in e-PP adoption

Readiness to adopt e-PP induces automation and streamlining of procurement processes to reduce the time and cost of conducting business for government and service providers and/or suppliers, standardises the procurement processes across government departments, enables better value for money spent by increasing competition, allows equal opportunity to all service providers and/or suppliers, and ultimately reduces corruption (Oppong, 2020:26).

To ensure effective e-PP adoption, government departments should be ready in terms of the operating environment, legal environment, economic environment, organisational environment, and technical environment (Orina, 2013:10). A subsequent discussion on each of these environments is provided for background purposes.

2.4.3.1 Operating environment

In South Africa, public sector procurement operates under a dual paradigm that is partially paper-based with some electronic features. The manual, paper-based system utilises traditional procurement to procure goods, works and services (Patel *et al.*, 2016:264).

Thus, Bausa, Kourtidis, Liljemo, Loozen, Rodrigues and Snaprud (2013:15) posit that a paper-based system might have been efficient for decades, but the traditional procurement process must be abolished or reduced and transferred to electronic-based processes which are prone to lead to better, more efficient and effective procurement (Pasiopoulos, Siskou, Galanis, Prezerakos, Moisoglou, Theodorou & Kaitelidou, 2013:16).

The operating environment is being faced with immense challenges causing strain to service delivery, and the South African citizenry at the receiving end are the ones suffering the most. In 2015, the National Treasury SCM review claimed that the implementation of consistent procurement practices across the local, provincial and national governments was satisfactory. However, Turley and Parera (2014:v) set forth that officials responsible for implementing procurement policies are hampered by a lack of operation guidance on how to implement procurement policies and practices consistently and on how to put appropriate departmental policies into practice. This is a worrying factor as the South African government is not making sufficient progress in implementing consistent procurement policies and practices at a desired pace (Ambe, 2016:278).

In addition, several public-sector organisations worldwide have identified public procurement as a major function of government and that e-PP should be a top priority on the e-Government agenda (Fernandes & Vieira, 2015:588). Furthermore, Nawi *et al.* (2016:330) state that it is now critical to know the drivers of e-PP adoption since most organisations still struggle with proper adoption of e-PP.

2.4.3.2 Legal environment

The legal environment of public procurement in South Africa constitutes a minimum provision in the e-PP legal and regulatory framework (Anthony, 2018:4). Kramer (2016:36) and Manyathi (2019:208) claim that e-PP requires a comprehensive and supportive legal and regulatory framework to achieve its desired results. Bausa *et al.* (2013) point out that the deficient legal environment means that government departments are hampered by inadequate government policies and legislation regarding e-PP, and that it may further lead to an e-PP barrier. To be ethical in the procurement process, procurement policies and regulations must be adhered to and discretion minimised in circumstances of high risk due to possible undue influence. This is because sound public procurement policies and practices are among the necessary elements of good governance (Van Der Walt, 2012:32).

As highlighted in Section 2.3.3.1, South Africa currently has a dual public procurement system in place being partly paper based with some electronic features. Since the inception of public procurement reforms, there have not been any amendments to the legislation and regulations governing public procurement to accommodate the adoption of e-PP and facilitate the reform process (Kramer, 2016:3). The only provisions made to adopt e-PP in the legal and regulatory framework have been in the form of circulars and instruction notes issued by the National Treasury. Even though issued circulars and instructions notes are formal documents encompassing the legal and regulatory framework, they are not highly regarded. It is because the purpose of circulars and

instruction notes are meant to inform accounting officers of government departments, constitutional institutions and public entities about any directive developments (Kramer, 2016:3; Anthony, 2018:44).

The Asian Development Bank (ADB) and the Model Law on Public Procurement of the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law (UNCITRAL) sets the tone for a proposed course of action, because the ADB is a founding member of the Multilateral Development Bank (MDB) (Asian Development Bank, 2013:ix). The legal and legislative requirements set out by ADB and UNCITRAL stipulate the need for recognition of regulations and policies to align e-PP with manual procurement and comply with an e-PP system which is “fair, equitable, transparent, competitive and cost-effective” (National Treasury, 2010:62). These policies should attune the existing traditional paper-based procurement process to the e-PP environment rather than duplicating it directly (UNCITRAL, 2014:302). Regulations and compliance control the micromanagement steps throughout the procurement process and provide means of political minimisation (UNCITRAL, 2014:302), because political ‘interference’ regularly might just be a manifestation of legitimate political representation on the broad impacts of procurement. Regulating e-procurement by means of legislation will not only ensure legal certainty to a large extent, but also ensure promotion of transparency and competition (Anthony, 2018:47).

2.4.3.3 Economic environment

The adoption of e-PP will offer additional opportunities for the business industry leading to a globally competitive economy and assisting to secure sustainable economic growth (Mpehle & Mudogwa, 2020:8). This is because the global economy is currently undergoing transformation where IT plays a key role in the adoption and implementation of e-PP (Patel *et al.*, 2016:264). It is noted that an e-PP initiative requires a large financial commitment and makes it complicated when assessing e-PP adoption benefits of the financial investment (Orina, 2013:32). However, investment costs of e-PP adoption can usually be justified by a reduction in transaction costs and related administrative costs. Thus, the required financial commitment leads to resource constraint barriers, particularly when the cost of establishing e-PP system is high for government departments (Orina, 2013:32). E-PP requires more attention from government departments for successful adoption to contribute to the growth and wellbeing of South Africa's economy (Nawi *et al.*, 2016:329). Fernandes and Vieira (2015:590) also assert that improving procurement within government departments is a priority since it represents the starting point for the control of public deficits and good economic development.

2.4.3.4 Organisational environment

Fernandes and Vieira (2015:594) evaluated the impact of e-PP adoption in Portugal's SMEs and found that organisational factors are critical variables that explain the variance in innovation readiness. Adebayo and Evans (2015:3) affirm the necessity of awareness

of the potential impact of e-PP on organisational performance. In addition, Priambodo *et al.* (2021:868) acknowledge that the size of government departments is one of the primary organisational determinants of e-PP adoption. Regression analysis of a study conducted by Moon (2005:67) suggests that larger and more managerially innovative government departments are more likely to be ready and active to adopt e-PP. In their study of the challenges facing the use of e-PP applications in public organisations, Kisang and Rotich (2014:10) second the assertion that e-PP is more evident in larger organisations than in smaller ones. Subsequently, government departments now find themselves under greater pressure to find viable ways of better and improved public services.

There has been an increasing recognition in the literature that procurement officials play an important role in influencing the success of e-PP projects. Hence, organisations seeking to maximise their investments in e-PP technology need to understand that the antecedents of employees' acceptance are critical (Brandon-Jones & Kauppi, 2018:3). As pointed out by Koech, Ayoyi and Mugambi (2016:22) and Mohungoo *et al.* (2020:53), "resistance to change" is one of the biggest barriers to introducing e-PP. Whenever change is imposed, there is a high level of reluctance duly, because of the uncertainty associated with the change (Ahimbisibwe *et al.*, 2016:11). Resistance to change is an obstacle primarily driven by the fear of change to a new system. Hence, willingness to accept flexibility is vital for organisations that seek to reap many of the perceived benefits of change (Premathilaka & Fernando, 2020:97). Toroitich, Mburugu and Waweru (2017:247) posit that government departments need to understand why people resist changes and identify the possible ways to resolve such issues. Consistent with the view,

Koech *et al.* (2016:22) argue that cultural change needs to take place prior to adoption of e-PP.

2.4.3.5 Technology environment

The technology context represents the compatibility and pool of technologies a firm could adopt (Suleiman, 2015:147; Priambodo *et al.*, 2021:867). E-PP is a technology solution enhancing corporate buying through the Internet (Jain *et al.*, 2018:89). The technical implementation of e-PP enables the transformation of organisational structures and workplace practices. At present, the rate at which individuals and organisations use various Web-based ICTs, including e-PP, to carry out procurement activities is increasing (Aduwo, Ibem, Ayo-Vaughan, Uwakonye & Owolabi, 2017:220). Although government departments envisage major new investments in IT, they are likely to face a significant array of technological obstacles that must be overcome if successful technology adoption is to be achieved (Doherty, McConnell & Ellis-Chadwick, 2013:5; Priambodo *et al.*, 2021:867).

Fernandes and Vieira (2015:594) and Mohungoo *et al.* (2020:52) single out technology-related inhibitors, such as security concerns about the information traded, the lack of interoperability between systems and low uniformity in public procurement procedures as causing resistance to change, as well as the absence of an adequate organisational culture to encourage technological advance. Brandon-Jones and Kauppi (2018:2) identify the need for training procurement officials. This support for procurement officials may be

lessened by ensuring that e-PP system has effective design-covering system navigation and system usability. According to Berisha-Nmani (2013:107), the use of IT to support the execution of business activity stimulates rapid and efficient communication, exchange of large amounts of information, integrates multimedia documents, digitalises procurement activities and creates virtual organisations. Mose *et al.* (2013:593) observe that unavailability of Internet access to business and people will create non-participation in procurement processes; this creates a need for adequate digital and telecommunication infrastructure (De la Harpe, 2015:1588). The utilisation of e-PP relies heavily on the availability, nature and capacity of the existing infrastructure, such as broadband coverage (Sithole, 2017:57; Mpehle & Mudogwa, 2020:3). Therefore, e-PP adoption in South Africa can revolutionise the buying function of government departments by streamlining and automating labour intensive procurement routines.

Public-sector e-PP is a complex socio-technical system rooted in various layers of government. The different layers of government and cooperation across diverse agencies can create joint action; thus inter-agency cooperation will result in a crucial cooperation between government agencies and service providers and/or suppliers coming together to implement the e-PP system (Orina, 2013:3; Issa, 2020:52).

2.4.4 Readiness challenges in e-PP adoption

The challenges associated with readiness of government departments to adopt e-PP, as identified by Orina (2013:34), include lack of IT and Internet transaction skills, resistance to change and lack of enthusiasm among personnel. Thus, the main challenge when

introducing a new system, is changing the mindset of existing procurement officials to accept new approaches and practices (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2018:3). In addition, another main challenge for e-PP project is the establishment of an appropriate and context-tailored strategy, because every project of this nature and magnitude needs to be rooted carefully, analytically and with a dynamic strategy.

The fragmentation of operating systems within government departments in South Africa is another concern for effective e-PP adoption. SCM processes are currently supported by a variety of procurement systems that are fragmented, underutilised, and differ in functionality, scale and performance (National Treasury, 2015:59). National government departments currently use one or more of the following procurement systems: Logistical Information System (LOGIS), Intenda, Procure to Pay, Hardcat, and System Administrative Processes (SAP), among others (National Treasury, 2015:61). The LOGIS system was created in the mid-1990s and was first used in the early 2000s to help government departments in South Africa procure, control and regulate optimal stock levels (National Treasury, 2015:61). Intenda was designed in 2001 specifically to deal with electronic sourcing, with key features such as basic supplier management, spending analysis, and the development of sourcing strategies. Procure to Pay is an automated procurement process that consists of requisitioning, bidding, contract awarding and payment (Olali, 2015:9). Hardcat offers solutions for fixed asset management, asset intelligence and asset auditing. SAP is an enterprise resource planning (ERP) system that combines the organisation's major business processes. Within SCM, it is used for

requisition and data management, as well as remuneration of contractors and suppliers (Laryea, Ibem, Pagiwa & Phoi, 2014:8).

It is difficult to manage and integrate the above-mentioned disparity in ICT usage. As Dza *et al.* (2013:51) point out, this often leads to cost and effort duplication, as well as confusion and difficulty in procurement decision-making. The various SCM systems now employed in the public sector, according to the National Treasury (2015:63), result in fragmented data, uneven processes, varied compliance levels and poor outcomes. The incompatibility of e-PP software with existing procurement methods complicates the implementation of an end-to-end e-PP system (Rukuni, Maziriri & Mulaudzi, 2020:411). Although technology allows for faster innovation and improvement of SCM, the present ICT infrastructure restricts the ability to optimise the performance of SCM systems.

The e-PP adoption practice in the public sector mainly aims to eliminate the difficulties experienced with the paper-based procurement method and promote more integrated and frank processes. Fernandes and Vieira (2015:592) assert that the adoption of e-PP will have a significant impact on the service providers and/or suppliers because of the enabling role of ICT tools in improving the effectiveness and efficiency of SMEs. Adopting a fully paperless procurement system would improve procurement efficiency as all relevant information would be available through an electronic platform (Costa, Arantes & Tavares, 2013:239). However, the challenges identified above reveal some areas that need to be looked into to ensure successful e-PP adoption and implementation.

2.5 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

A conceptual framework shows the relationship between two variables, the dependent and the independent variable (Mohamed & Milimu, 2016:1183; Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2018:69). In this study, the dependent variable is e-PP adoption challenges and the independent variables are the e-PP readiness factors (operating environment, legal environment, economic environment, organisational environment, and technical environment). The independent variables collectively affect e-PP adoption as shown in **Figure 2.1**. The framework posits that the presence or absence of the indicated independent variables would determine the readiness of government departments to adopt e-PP.

Source: Adapted from Orina (2013:17)

FIGURE 2.1: E-PP environment

In accordance with **Figure 2.1**, operating environment, legal environment, economic environment, organisational environment, and technical environment together affect government departments' decisions with regard to the readiness in adopting e-PP. This means that e-PP readiness factors play a critical role in determining e-PP adoption outcome. Therefore, disregarding to assess e-PP readiness factors through readiness

assessment of these environments would result in e-PP adoption failure in government departments.

2.6 SUMMARY

To ascertain the readiness of government departments to integrate ICTs into their procurement processes, an e-readiness assessment procedure should be carried out because each e-readiness initiative needs to be rooted carefully, analytically and with a dynamic strategy. It is thus widely documented that where public or private entities are ready and willing to adopt and implement e-PP properly, benefits arise for all stakeholders. Supporters of e-PP adoption in government departments are confident that it will overcome many problems of manual paper-based procurement and lead to better, more efficient and more effective public procurement.

The review of literature shows that even modern, technical tools are not adequate to ensure success. E-PP is not a mere technical solution but an end-to-end business solution. Technology investment has the potential to significantly improve the efficiency and effectiveness of SCM. Furthermore, studies reveal various success factors, including an effective procurement policy and practice, strategies that enable buyers (government departments) and sellers (service providers and/or suppliers) to adopt and use e-PP systems, an effective communication programme that communicates the value of e-PP to all stakeholders and a well-designed change management program to integrate these diverse components. Literature critique identified two common challenges of the public sector comprising a task to manage the competing priorities in government and policy

reform, and developing the skills base for procurement officials. It also suggests that ICT will become a vital part of procurement and lead to higher e-PP adoption rates as staff who use it share their low-risk experiences and perceptions.

However, scholarly literature on e-PP initiatives is very limited and it can be that e-PP adoption and implementation initiatives in the public sector are in their early stages. Despite South Africa's procurement reforms, there are still challenges in public procurement and making the shift from manual handling of public procurement to e-PP, requires a well-planned and sustained effort. Public sector procurement integrity needs to be retained and e-PP is a promising panacea.

CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

The previous chapter (Chapter 2) provided the theoretical foundation for this study, discussing the state of public and electronic procurement in the world and in South Africa and the readiness for e-PP in government departments in South Africa. This theoretical foundation formed the basis for empirically constructing and determining this study's research variables, address the research problem and achieve the research objectives. This chapter presents the research methodology used to achieve the research objectives of this study. The chapter begins with a discussion of the research philosophy followed by research design and population, and sampling. The chapter then discusses data collection, research instrument, validity and reliability, data analysis and ethical considerations. The chapter concludes with a summary of the research methodology discussed.

3.2 RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY

Before discussing the concept of research philosophy, it is important to first define *research*. Research is a discerning, truth-seeking process that collects, analyses, interprets and publishes information to make decisions more effective (Hair Jr, Page & Brunsveld, 2020:3). Burns and Veeck (2020:6) define *philosophy* as a system of values or principles to be lived by. The research philosophy sets out how the research plan,

research problem, data collection, data analysis, findings and recommendations are formulated (Strunk & Locke, 2019:60). For Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019:130), research philosophy (philosophy of science) is the belief system and the fundamental principles or assumptions that underlie how knowledge is developed. Research philosophy is therefore the assumptions that the researcher has, or how the researcher sees the world. These assumptions will form the basis of the research approach and the methods chosen to attain the research aim (Creswell & Clark, 2018:43).

Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019:144) distinguish five main philosophical stances that are generally used in business and management sciences, namely positivism, interpretivism, pragmatism, critical realism and postmodernism. Each type of philosophy is briefly discussed as follows:

- Positivism is a philosophical approach to scientific study, which is based on objective knowledge from experience, direct observation and results that can be measured empirically using quantitative methods, i.e., surveys (Hatch, 2018:15). It is gradually correlated with the quantitative method of analysis than qualitative research (Creswell & Creswell, 2018:44). It is believed that positivism emphasises "the widespread need for generalisation of the world and the need for accurate measurement" (Mukherji & Albon, 2018:107) and tends to rely exclusively on theories that can be directly tested (Saunders *et al.*, 2019:146).
- Yin (2018:56) describes interpretivism as a concept that has been used as a synonym for all qualitative research. Interpretivism is based on the view that information can only be produced and interpreted in ways that give meaning to

experience (Hatch, 2018:15). This philosophical stance allows researchers to understand the subjective nature of social action (Bryman & Bell 2019:10). Interpretivism is an alternative to a positivist view and assumes that a strategy is required to accept the difference between human beings and the objects of natural sciences (Bell, Bryman & Harley, 2019:30).

- Pragmatism underlines the belief that all that has practical and functional significance is essential and valid (Johnson & Christensen, 2020:145). Pragmatism declares that ideas are only important if they promote action (Denzin & Lincoln, 2018:548). Pragmatism, according to Creswell and Creswell (2018:48), arises from actions, situations and consequences rather than from past conditions. It uses various data collection sources to better answer the research question and to stress the value of conducting research that best solves the research problem (Creswell & Poth, 2018:83).
- Critical realism is a philosophical position that holds things to be true to the degree that they yield results (Babbie, 2021:41). According to Saunders *et al.* (2019:147), critical realism focuses on what people see and feel about the fundamental mechanisms of reality that form observable events. Creswell and Clark (2018:687) claim that this philosophical position shares features with positivism and aims to provide insight into the role of scientific practice. Critical realism is critical, since it presents the possibility of a transition that might shift the status quo (Bell *et al.*, 2019:559).
- Postmodernism is described as questioning the assumptions of positivism and the theories that justify "objective" reality (Babbie, 2021:41). Denzin and Lincoln

(2018:1402) see the core of postmodernism as the doubt that any method, discourse or tradition has a fundamental and general claim to be the “right” or privileged source of authoritative knowledge. Hatch (2018:16) adds that postmodernism exposes and tries to correct the errors that modernism conceals. In contrast to modernism, this philosophy promotes self-image (Johnson & Christensen, 2020:1082).

This study adopted positivism as this philosophical stance is well suited to collect and analyse quantitative data through a survey and to determine the relationships between dependent and independent variables, as illustrated in section 2.4.

3.3 RESEARCH DESIGN

Mohamed and Milimu (2016:1187) define research design as a comprehensive plan of how a particular issue or inquiry is performed. According to Barngatuny and Kimutai (2015:111), research designs explain how data was gathered for evaluation. According to Kothari and Garg (2019:29), research design serves as a blueprint for the collection, measurement and evaluation of data. Different research designs are used to study business and management problems based on various research standpoints such as research purpose or methodological choices. Regarding research purpose, research can be either descriptive, evaluative, exploratory, explanatory or a combination of some of these (Saunders *et al.*, 2019:186). Each of these research designs is discussed as follows:

- Descriptive research design seeks to obtain data that describe the characteristics of topic of interest accurately (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2020:164) or of certain groups to estimate or predict the behaviour of individuals in a particular population (Thomas, Silverman & Nelson, 2015:19). In this type of research design, the questions about who, what, where, when and how are answered (Burns & Veeck, 2020:81).
- Evaluative research design aims to study the processes and outcomes of an attempted solution (McDaniel Jr & Gates, 2015:7). This design is used in applied research to understand, test or assess how well something performs (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2018:79). Babbie (2021:356) points out that evaluative design focuses on research purpose rather than a particular method for determining the impact of social interventions. The main question that evaluative studies usually pose is, “has the intervention accomplished its objectives?” (Bell *et al.*, 2019:57). According to Yin (2018:327), evaluative assessments take the form of inquiries in order to reach both formative and summative judgments.
- Explorative design is used in a study that aims to explore an unknown field (Bairagi & Munot, 2019:9). It attempts to establish underlying and rough comprehension of a little understood phenomenon (Marshall & Rossman, 2016:78). Exploratory research, as Burns and Veeck (2020:64) indicate, is most frequently unstructured, informal research aimed at collecting background information on the general idea of the research problem.
- Explanatory design is one that is employed in studies that attempt to "connect dots" to answer why and how types of questions (Neuman, 2014:31; Johnson and Christensen (2020:681). Explanatory studies aim to distinguish the cause and

effect (why and how) of relationships that exist between different variables (Kumar, 2019:15). They also clarify the patterns of the phenomena in question (Marshall & Rossman, 2016:78; Hair Jr *et al.*, 2020:169).

- Combined research design is a form of research that poses narrow, particular questions and broad and general questions (Clark & Creswell, 2015:56). This design uses mixed methods to promote a combination of descriptive, evaluative, exploratory and explanatory research (Saunders *et al.*, 2019:188).

This study adopted a descriptive research design to answer the questions about who, what, where, when and how that pertain to the readiness of government departments to adopt e-PP. This was made possible through the use of a structured survey questionnaire (see Appendix B).

3.4 SAMPLING DESIGN

This section describes the sampling design used for this study. The section subsequently discusses the population and sampling, consisting of sampling frame and sampling elements, sampling techniques (methods) and sample size.

3.4.1 Population

Population is the group or collection that the study is interested in generalising about (Babbie, 2021:200; Bairagi & Munot, 2019:90). The population is the number of all

targeted persons with peculiar characteristics (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2020:180). The target population, according to Johnson and Christensen (2020:681), is the narrower circle from which the actual sample is drawn.

For this study the target population consisted of public procurement officials working at various levels of procurement in South African national government departments (i.e., low, middle and senior management service). These officials were selected specifically because of their expertise in and knowledge of public procurement at strategic, tactical and operational levels and also because of their direct involvement in the procurement of goods, works and services within the supply chain environment.

3.4.2 Sampling

Sampling, according to Kumar (2019:292), is the "method of selecting a few respondents (a sample) from a larger group (a sample population) to be the basis for estimating the prevalence of interest information". According to Saunders *et al.* (2019:292), sample refers to a part of the population selected, reflecting the broader population. Leedy, Ormrod and Johnson (2019:171) believe that a sample "should be chosen so carefully that, through it, the researcher is able to see the characteristics of the total population in the same proportions and relationships as would be seen if the researcher were to examine the total population". This is because the reliability of the findings is largely dependent on the choice of the sample (Kumar, 2019:48).

3.4.2.1 Sampling units

A sampling unit is defined by Malhotra, Nunan, and Birks (2017:414) as a unit containing the element that is available for selection at some stage of the sampling process. Chawla and Sondhi (2015:251) see a sampling unit as “a single member of a particular sample”. To be representative of the population, the sampling units in the sample must be distributed in the same proportion as the population's elements (Kothari & Garg, 2019:153). However, if the sampling unit differs from the element, it is important to determine precisely how the elements within the sampling unit should be chosen (Malhotra *et al.*, 2017:416).

According to Bairagi and Munot (2019:92), the sampling process must follow the sampling plan and include the selection of sampling units. Furthermore, sampling units are often too diverse to be represented reliably. As a result, researchers should use data collection units that are considerably smaller than sampling units (Burns & Veeck, 2020:232).

The sample units for this study consisted of five (5) identified national government departments from the ministerial clusters in South Africa. The five ministerial clusters with cross-cutting programmes are economic sectors, investment, employment and infrastructure development; social protection, community and human development; governance, state capacity and institutional development; justice, crime prevention and security; and international cooperation, trade and security. Clustering is concerned with

grouping together departments with similar, related or shared objectives with a view of achieving an integrated governance system (Koma & Tshiyoyo, 2015:36).

3.4.2.2 Sampling elements

Bryman and Bell (2019:10) see a sampling element as a “single case in the population”. The sampling element consists of a single member of the population (Chawla & Sondhi, 2015:250). In order to represent the population of the sample, it is important that the sampling frame contains all population elements. According to Babbie (2021:209), a sample that is adequately drawn shall include the necessary details to define the population of the elements that make up the sampling frame. **Table 3.1** summarises the sampling elements used in this study.

TABLE 3.1: Summary of sampling elements

National government departments	Public procurement officials
1. Department of Mineral Resources and Energy (DMRE)	30
2. Department of Health (DOH)	30
3. Department of Home Affairs (DHA)	30
4. Department of Small Business Development (DSBD)	30
5. Department of Tourism (DOT)	30

3.4.2.3 Sampling techniques

According to Kothari and Garg (2019:13), a sampling technique is a definite plan established before any data is collected, primarily to obtain a sample from a given population. Sampling techniques can be either probability sampling or non-probability sampling (Saunders *et al.*, 2019:296). With probability sampling, each element has a known probability of being included in the sample, but non-probability sampling does not enable the researcher to establish this probability (Patten & Newhart, 2018:100). This study used probability, cluster sampling to select public procurement officials in each of the national government department clusters. Cluster sampling is a sampling method where the target population is divided into clusters or groups, and these are then sampled randomly (Saunders *et al.*, 2019:321). It is used when the researcher can access a complete list of the population clusters (Singh & Masuku, 2014:5). Saunders *et al.* (2019:313) state that “for cluster sampling, your sampling frame is the complete list of clusters rather than a complete list of individual cases within the population”.

3.4.2.4 Sample size

Sample size as defined by Clark and Creswell (2015:237) is the “number of respondents that participated in the study and provided data”. Kumar (2019:292) sees sample size as the number of components to be used in the study. According to Wiid and Diggins (2015:210), sample size should be selected primarily for an accurate estimate of population values, but this should be accomplished economically and practically. A similar

study relied on the sample of 50 public procurement and IT officials determined using the Bartlett, Kotrlik and Haggins' (2001) estimate computation. However, this study drew a sample size of one hundred and thirteen (113) public procurement officials from the five national government department clusters. **Table 3.2** breaks down the sample size highlighting government clusters, government departments, target sample and sample realisation.

TABLE 3.2: Breakdown of sample size

Ministerial clusters	Government departments	Target sample	Realised Sample
1. Economic sectors, investment, employment and infrastructure development	DMRE	30	50
2. Social protection, community and human development	DOH	30	22
3. Governance, state capacity and institutional development	DHA	30	20
4. Justice, crime prevention and security	DSBD	30	14
5. International cooperation, trade and security	DOT	30	7
Total		150	113

Table 3.2 shows that 30 procurement officials were targeted per ministerial cluster and in different levels of management (3x higher, 12x middle and 15x lower). The realised sample in the table shows that the economic sectors, investment, employment and infrastructure development cluster obtained higher number of respondents (50) than the targeted number of respondents (30). This might be due to the merger of the Department of Mineral Resources and the Department of Energy to form the Department of Mineral

Resources and Energy (DMRE) that resulted in the reconfiguration of two procurement units into one (Government Communication and Information System, 2019:24). The table also shows that the international cooperation, trade and security cluster obtained a lower number of respondents (7) than the targeted number of respondents (30). This might be due to the fact that public procurement officials were working on schedules because of Covid-19 restrictions at the Department of Tourism (DOT) at the time of survey administration.

This study took into account the following three factors pertaining to the determination of the sample size:

- **Budget** - The greater the sample size, the more resources are required to make a choice;
- **Timing** - The greater the sample size, the longer it requires to collect information and finish the assessment; and
- **Risk associated with any choice** - The greater the risk, the greater the amount of precision required (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2020:164).

3.5 DATA COLLECTION

Data collection is the systematic collection of information from a sample to answer a research question (Bairagi & Munot, 2019:131). According to Kumar (2019:271), there are two key approaches to gathering information about a situation, person, problem or phenomenon. These approaches to information gathering can be categorised as primary

and secondary data methods (Chawla & Sondhi, 2015:11). Primary data collection methods differ from secondary data collection methods because primary data are originally collected, while secondary data collection is simply compilation (Kothari & Garg, 2019:95). Researchers collect primary data or secondary data or both to answer their research questions or achieve their research objectives (Saunders *et al.*, 2019:338). These types of data collection are each discussed below for background information.

3.5.1 Primary data

Primary data, according to Burns and Veeck (2020:90), are the types of information collected by the researcher primarily for the research project at hand. According to Kumar (2019:223), advances in communication technology have made the collecting of primary data via an online questionnaire quite common. Primary data for this study were collected from public procurement officials working for the five national government department clusters, as indicated in sections 3.4.2.2, 3.4.2.3 and 3.4.2.4, using an online, self-administered survey questionnaire. This online questionnaire was posted on SurveyMonkey with the link to the email addresses of public procurement officials from the five national government department clusters. These email addresses were obtained from a database of the consulting company that was contracted to post and manage the online questionnaire on SurveyMonkey. An e-mail containing a web link to the online questionnaire via the SurveyMonkey website was sent to public procurement officials of the five national government department clusters and instructions on how to complete the questionnaire were also included. In addition, the e-mail also contained an information

leaflet on the purpose of the study, the time it takes to complete the questionnaire and on ethical issues observed for participating in this study, as explained in section 3.9.

3.5.2 Secondary data

Secondary data refer to data previously obtained by someone other than the researcher (Chawla & Sondhi, 2015:96; McDaniel Jr & Gates, 2015:73). According to Malhotra *et al.* (2017:94), secondary data provide more advantages than primary data, i.e., simple access to data, at a low cost and with quick access. As secondary data provide a key component of a successful research design, this study used secondary data on the trend of readiness and willingness of South African government departments to adopt e-PP. These data came from various sources including journal articles, books, dissertations and theses, and the Internet, among others.

3.6 RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

A research instrument is a collection of questions designed to generate data required to reach the objectives of a research project (McDaniel Jr & Gates, 2015:271; Bell *et al.*, 2019:231). Chawla and Sondhi (2015:202) posit that the basic requirement for a research instrument is to clearly define research objectives that should be converted into clear questions. This study employed a survey questionnaire as a research instrument to collect primary data, as indicated in section 3.5.1. This questionnaire is an adaptation of the existing questionnaires used in similar studies in Kenya (Orina, 2013), Ghana (Siita,

2014) and Indonesia (Nugroho, 2015) to suit the South African government context. This is consistent with Malhotra *et al.* (2017:328), who advocate that the adaptation of an existing questionnaire or research instrument to the new socio-cultural setting is a way of displaying contextual relevance and of avoiding bias.

According to Barngetuny and Kimutai (2015:112), survey questionnaires are ideal for data collection from a larger group. Surveys provide the researcher with an overview of what the target population thinks about a specific phenomenon or reality (Babbie, 2021:276). In order to obtain precise measurements of the phenomenon, questionnaire construction is critical (Imai, 2017:398). Wiid and Diggines (2015:158) add that the design and development of a questionnaire is of the utmost importance, as researchers often collect data from respondents through such a medium. The Internet has had an impact on questionnaire development and use, since the leading Internet self-service questionnaire-building platform, SurveyMonkey, provides survey design, respondent invitation, data collection, analysis, and results reporting (McDaniel Jr & Gates, 2015:297).

The questionnaire used to collect data for this study was divided into three parts: the first part (Part A) consisted of questions on the demographic profile of respondents, such as age, gender, educational level and job designation. The demographic profile of respondents offered background for analysis and interpretation of study findings (Burns & Veeck, 2020:64). The demographic questions not only helped the survey screen respondents (Chawla & Sondhi, 2015:250), but also segment them and revealed hidden trends of the dataset (Smith & Albaum, 2013:94).

The other two parts (Part B and Part C) contained questions based on the study's four objectives. Part B sought to assess factors that affect e-PP readiness in South African government departments, while Part C focused on the challenges associated with the readiness of government departments for the adoption of the e-PP system in order to shed light on what needed to be taken into account to ensure successful e-PP adoption. Respondents were asked to indicate to what extent they agreed or disagreed with the statements on factors that affect the e-PP and e-PP readiness challenges in South Africa's government departments by clicking on an option, using the five-point Likert scale where 5 represents "strongly agree", and 1 represents "strongly disagree". In addition, dichotomous questions were also used in the questionnaire to ensure a clear and unequivocal response.

The questionnaire also included a comment box to allow public procurement officials to record any concerns or opinions they may have about e-PP in addition to what had been covered in the questionnaire. The results of this comment box added less value to the main findings and are therefore presented and discussed in Appendix A.

3.7 VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY OF INSTRUMENT

The two most important and fundamental characteristics of good research are the validity and reliability of any measuring instrument. Mohajan's (2017:1) study of the two criteria for good measurement in the field of research has shown that the validity and reliability

of the instrument are key features in the assessment of any measuring instrument or tool for good research. Leedy *et al.* (2019:103) consider validity and reliability of measurement instruments to be those factors that influence the degree to which a researcher can learn more about the phenomena under study, and the likelihood that a researcher will obtain statistical significance in any data analysis. According to Singh (2014:83), researchers must use validity and reliability in quantitative research to increase transparency and reduce research bias.

3.7.1 Validity

Validity is the degree to which the findings are valid (Leedy *et al.*, 2019:104). This encompasses the entire experimental concept and determines whether the results obtained meet all the criteria of the scientific research method (Kothari & Garg, 2019:74). According to Musau (2015:22), validity refers to inference accuracy and meaning based on the results of the research. A test is reliable when it can be used under stable conditions by many different researchers, with consistent results that do not vary (Ivankova, 2015:260).

According to Creswell and Creswell (2018:153), the use of an existing instrument sets out the validity of the scores received from the use of the instrument in the past. This study used an adapted questionnaire that was pilot-tested with 20 public procurement officials working for the Department of Mineral Resources because they were conveniently accessible. Pilot-testing questionnaires were distributed to the selected officials within the

department through emails. According to Bell *et al.* (2019:107), the purpose of the pilot study is to refine the survey questionnaire so that there would be no problem in answering the questions and no problem in recording the data. The findings from the pilot study helped the researcher to identify and revise some questions that respondents struggled to answer to ensure that those questions were well understood and properly answered.

3.7.2 Reliability

Ivankova (2015:262) defines *reliability* as the degree to which a measuring instrument produces stable and consistent results. Leedy *et al.* (2019:107) describe reliability as the accuracy with which a measuring instrument produces certain consistent results when the object measured has not changed. The better the reliability of the performance, the more accurate the results, which increases the chance to make the right research decision (Bairagi & Munot, 2019:117). According to Creswell and Clark (2018:325), reliability is designed to measure the accuracy, precision, repeatability and dependability of the study.

This study used Cronbach's alpha to ensure internal consistency reliability. Cronbach's alpha, according to Malhotra *et al.* (2017:360), is the average of all potential split-half coefficients arising from the various divisions of the scale items. Cronbach's alpha is the most commonly used measure of reliability (Bell *et al.*, 2019:82). Researchers generally consider an alpha greater than or equal to 0.7 as sufficient for most social science research, depending on the study objectives (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2020:261). In support of this

view, Saunders *et al.* (2019:518) state that Cronbach's alpha ranges between 0 and 1 and the values of 0.7 or above indicate that the questions in the scale are internally consistent. Internal consistency reliability assesses the potential to achieve consistent findings as different samples are used to test a phenomenon over the same time span (McDaniel Jr & Gates, 2015:234). The results of reliability tests are provided in section 4.4.2.

3.8 DATA ANALYSIS

Clark and Creswell (2015:254) emphasise that researchers analyse their quantitative data using statistics and report the findings of the study to fulfil their research objectives. Kothari and Garg (2019:126) explain that the analysis of the data is intended to break down the data and shed light on the nature of the elements and the relationship between them. While data analysis is not an end in itself, it is a knowledge-based approach that helps address the problem at hand and encourages effective decision making (Malhotra *et al.*, 2017:546).

The data collected for this study were cleaned and then processed with Stata Release 15. Stata, according to Thomas (2021:164), is a data analysis and statistics programme. This application is the most widely used complete and integrated software package for data analysis, data management, graphics, and regression (Stockemer, 2019:73). Data processing included the development of a coding scheme, data entry and analysis. The data coding was done to allow the responses to be grouped into different categories to

facilitate data conversion and measurement comparisons. Schindler (2019:227) postulates that encoding requires assigning numbers or other symbols to responses in a manner that allows a limited number of categories to respond to a group.

Patten and Newhart (2018:203) distinguish two branches of statistics, i.e., descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. Ivankova (2015:220) regards *descriptive statistics* as the term used in the analysis of data to describe and summarise data in a valid and meaningful way. According to Adams and Lawrence (2019:215), descriptive statistics is “a type of quantitative (numerical) analysis used to summarise the characteristics of a sample”. This study used descriptive statistics to summarise findings on the demographic profile of public procurement officials from five national government department clusters through frequency distributions (see Section 4.3). This analysis helped uncover hidden characteristics of the dataset needed for inferential statistical analysis.

Leedy *et al.* (2019:330) define inferential statistics as the use of a descriptive statistical sample to generalise the population from which the samples were taken. Inferential statistics uses the mathematics of probability theory to test whether the descriptive results are likely to be due to random factors or to a specific relationship (Babbie, 2021:489). This study performed four analyses to determine the relationships between dependent and independent variables. These included factor analysis, reliability analysis, Chi-Square test and ANOVA. These analyses are discussed in the sections that follow, except reliability analysis, which has been discussed in section **3.7.2**.

3.8.1 Factor analysis

Factor analysis is the most often used multivariate statistical approach for examining correlations among a number of variables and discovering clusters of strongly linked variables that represent underlying themes (factors) within the data variables (Mukherjee, Sinha & Chattopadhyay, 2018:103; Leedy *et al.*, 2019:334). In factor analysis, all variables under assessment are analysed together to extract the underlined one (Malhotra *et al.*, 2017:599). Chawla and Sondhi (2015:560) see this analysis as a linear combination of variables that does not distinguish between dependent and independent variables. McDaniel Jr and Gates (2015:476) describe factor analysis as a technique for simplifying data by reducing a large number of related variables to a smaller number of unrelated variables. Factor analysis aims to identify the dominant variables in the sample (questionnaire) and their correlations (Johnson & Christensen, 2020:488; Babbie, 2021:480).

Before performing a factor analysis, various conditions must be fulfilled: The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin and the Barlett's sphericity test (Williams, Brown & Onsmann, 2012:5; Afolabi, Ibem, Aduwo, Tunji-Olayeni and Oluwunmi, 2019:6; Nguyen, Phan, Le & Nguyen, 2020:525).

3.8.1.1 The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin test (KMO)

The KMO test determines how appropriate the data is for factor analysis. According to Cohen *et al.* (2018:820), the KMO statistics correlate pairs of variables and the magnitude of partial correlations among variables, and that requires many pairs of variables to be statistically significantly associated. KMO statistics range from 0 to 1 (Williams *et al.*, 2012:5) and Kaiser (1970), Field (2018:1005) and Tabachnick and Fidell (2019:483) all recommend that the KMO scale should be 0.60 or higher (maximum is 1) in order to proceed with factor analysis. Kaiser (1970) also proposes a cut-off value of 0.5 for factor analysis and an optimal value of 0.8 or higher so that the sample can be adequate. A low value of KMO indicates that the correlation between variables cannot be explained by other variables (Chawla & Sondhi, 2015:56; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019:483).

3.8.1.2 The sphericity test

The sphericity test analyses correlations to the identity matrix (checks for redundancy between variables) (Yong & Pearce, 2013:80; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019:483). This test, according to Hair Jr. *et al.*, (2019:136), determines if the data are compatible with factor analysis. Cohen *et al.* (2018:820) state that Bartlett test of sphericity analyses correlations between variables and should show statistical significance ($p\text{-value} < 0.05$) to prove sampling adequacy. However, as the sample size increases, this test becomes more sensitive in discovering correlations between variables (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2019:136), The results of both the KMO and the Barlett's test of sphericity are important to indicate how

suitable factor analysis is for a given set of data collected (Roy & Upadhyay, 2017:75; Cohen *et al.*, 2018:820; Nguyen *et al.*, 2020:525).

3.8.1.3 Principal component analysis

After establishing the appropriateness of factor analysis for data analysis, it is required to determine how many factors will be retrieved from the given set of data by means of the principal component analysis (PCA) (Chawla & Sondhi, 2015:580). PCA is a pattern recognition technique used to detect similarities and differences in a set of data (Bairagi & Munot, 2019:92). According to Malhotra *et al.* (2017:717), PCA is a factor analysis method that examines the overall variance in the data. The original variables are converted into a smaller set of linear combinations in PCA, with all of the variation in the variables being used (Pallant, 2016:202).

Field (2018:1004) discovered that not all factors are retained in both PCA and factor analysis, and an extraction process is used to choose how many factors to keep. The number of factors retained prior to rotation has a significant impact on the outcome of a factor analysis (Ford, MacCallum & Tait, 1986:294). Kaiser's (1970, 1974) sampling adequacy measure (criterion of the Kaiser Guttman method) is used to determine how many variables should be extracted. According to this method, the number of factors to be extracted should be equal to the number of factors with an eigenvalue of at least one (Kothari, 2004:322; Chawla & Sondhi, 2015:562). Eigenvalues are measures of variation between factors, with the sum of a factor's squared loadings indicating the amount of

variance accounted for by that factor (Cohen *et al.*, 2018:820). As a result, only factors with greater eigenvalues (more than one constitutes a factor) are regarded as essential and are retained and studied further (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2020:430).

3.8.1.3.1 Rotation technique: Varimax

After factor extraction, rotation is often used to increase strong (high item loadings) correlations between factors and variables while decreasing low item loadings (Williams *et al.*, 2010:9; Field, 2018:1007; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019:625). According to Cohen *et al.* (2018:820), the rotation process keeps variables that are closely related together while separating them from variables that are not. The most commonly used rotation technique is called Varimax. Tabachnick and Fidell (2019:487) describe Varimax rotation as a "variance-maximising method". This method seeks to minimise the number of variables with high loadings on each factor (Pallant, 2016:207; Hair Jr *et al.*, 2019:150; Mukherjee, 2020:202). Mukherjee (2020:202) stresses that the Varimax technique seeks to increase the variation of factor loadings by making high loadings higher and low loadings lower for each factor. When the factor matrix is rotated, the variance is transferred from early to later factors, resulting in a simpler and more coherent factor pattern. This study used Varimax rotation to determine the factorial structure of Part B of the questionnaire consisting of 27 Likert scale questions (see **Table 4.6, Table 4.7** and **Table 4.10**). Besides the Varimax rotation, the test of internal consistency of the factors was considered by assessing the Cronbach's alpha value of each factor on Part B and C of the questionnaire (see **Table 4.11 – 4.18**).

Factor loading indicates the degree of association between a variable and a factor (Chawla & Sondhi, 2015:567; Babbie, 2021:490). A lower loading of an item suggests that it may not be an appropriate measure of its factor, and low loaded (> 0.40) items will be removed from the factor (Fabrigar & Wegener, 2012:26; Field, 2018:1023). The higher the loading, the more the variable a precise measure of the factor is (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019:654). A name will be assigned to each factor so that it may be characterised or described (Cohen *et al.*, 2018:824). In this study, a cut-off point of 0.40 (factor loadings $\Rightarrow .40$) for factor loadings is used as it is considered meaningful and practically significant (Ford *et al.*, 1986:296; Hair Jr *et al.*, 2019:151; Laher *et al.*, 2019:56). The results of factor analysis for this study are presented and discussed in section 4.4.1.

3.8.2 The Pearson Chi-Square test

The Pearson Chi-square test “measures the difference between a statistically generated expected result and an actual (observed) result to see whether there is a statistically significant difference between them” (Cohen *et al.*, 2018:789). This test reveals how certain one is about the existence of a relationship between the dependent and independent variables in the population (Malhotra & Dash, 2016:712; Bryman & Bell, 2019:187). Each of these variables can be classified into two or more categories (Cohen *et al.*, 2018:789). According to Pallant (2016:237), the Chi-square test compares the observed frequencies (or percentages) of cases in each category to the values that would be anticipated if the variables under consideration had no relationship. This study used the Pearson Chi-Square test to determine whether a relationship between e-PP adoption

challenges and adoption of e-PP exists (see **Table 4.19**). If the p-value of the Pearson Chi-Square test is greater than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$), no statistically significant relationship exists between e-PP adoption challenges and adoption of e-PP; therefore, e-PP adoption challenges do not influence e-PP adoption (refer to **Table 4.19**). Then, if the p-value is equal or less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$), a statistically significant relationship exists between e-PP adoption challenges and adoption of e-PP; therefore, e-PP adoption challenges influence e-PP adoption (refer to **Table 4.19**).

3.8.3 Kruskal-Wallis test

The Kruskal-Wallis test (also known as one-way ANOVA) is a nonparametric rank-based test used to evaluate whether or not there are statistically significant differences between two or more groups of an independent variable on a continuous or ordinal dependent variable (Corder & Foreman, 2009:100; Cohen *et al.*, 2018:820). Johnson and Christensen (2020:1394) define the one-way ANOVA as a technique for testing for statistically significant differences in the means of two or more independent groups. Statistical significance, according to Johnson and Christensen (2020:1004), indicates that the difference between the group means is higher than what would be expected by chance alone. In this test, one independent variable (referred to as a factor) is associated with several levels (Pallant, 2016:274; Malhotra *et al.*, 2017:604). The Kruskal-Wallis test was used in this study to assess the relationship between years of service in the public sector procurement/SCM role and perceptions of the challenges of e-PP adoption. As with the Pearson Chi-square test, If the p-value of the Kruskal-Wallis test is greater than

0.05 ($p > 0.05$), no statistically significant relationship exists between years of service in the public sector procurement/SCM and perceptions of the challenges of e-PP adoption; therefore, years of service in the public sector procurement/SCM do not influence perceptions of the challenges of e-PP adoption (refer to **Table 4.19**). Then, if the p-value is equal or less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$), a statistically significant relationship exists between years of service in the public sector procurement/SCM and perceptions of the challenges of e-PP adoption; therefore, years of service in the public sector procurement/SCM do influence perceptions of the challenges of e-PP adoption (refer to **Table 4.19**).

3.9 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Johnson and Christensen (2020:370) view *ethics* in research as a set of widely accepted moral principles that provide guidelines and behavioural expectations for the most acceptable conduct towards experimental subjects and respondents, employers, sponsors, other researchers, assistants and students. According to Hair Jr *et al.* (2020:63), research ethics are the standards of conduct of the researcher in relation to the interests of those who become or are affected by the research project. Ethical considerations are particularly important when human beings are involved in the research project (Patten & Newhart, 2018:32), with the fundamental rule that research participation must not cause harm to respondents (Babbie, 2021:64). Loseke (2017:102) emphasises this point and indicates that the wellbeing of study respondents is the primary consideration in all aspects of social research.

The study adhered to ethical regulations and guidelines of the identified national government department clusters and of Tshwane University of Technology's (TUT) Research Ethics Committee. The accounting officers of national government department clusters permitted the researcher to administer online questionnaires to their public procurement officials. In accordance with the requirements of the Protection of Personal Information Act (POPI Act), public procurement officials (respondents) were informed that data collected from them would be treated confidentially and, if published, data would be coded to protect the identities of public procurement officials and of the national government department they work for. Consequently, without the express written consent of the public procurement officials, the data collected would not be used for either commercial purpose or be open to third parties.

In addition to the ethical considerations mentioned above, the following ethical guidelines were adhered to (Leedy *et al.*, 2019:112):

- Public procurement officials were entitled to withdraw from this study without giving reasons, as their participation was voluntary;
- Data collected from public procurement officials were kept confidential; therefore, no names of public procurement officials were shared with any third party;
- All the information collected was treated as group data, and no individual data of public procurement officials were reported;
- Participation in this study did not expose public procurement officials to any harm or risk (i.e., psychological or other) at no stage during the research process since public procurement officials were asked to complete an online questionnaire only;

- Results and findings of this study were honestly reported; and
- The dignity and character of all stakeholders were maintained and they were not subject to embarrassment.

3.10 SUMMARY

This chapter discussed the research design and methodology followed in this study. The study followed a positivistic approach and a descriptive design to assess the readiness of government departments to adopt e-PP. Public procurement officials working at various levels of management were targeted as population for this study. These officials were selected using probability cluster sampling in each of the national government department clusters. An online self-administered survey questionnaire was used to gather data, which were analysed using both descriptive (frequency distributions) and inferential analyses (factor analysis, reliability analysis, Chi-Square test and the Kruskal-Wallis test (a one-way ANOVA). Ethical principles considered were also highlighted. Chapter 4 presents and discusses data analysis and findings.

CHAPTER 4: DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

4.1 INTRODUCTION

Chapter 3 presented and discussed the research methodology adopted to meet the research objectives of this study. In this chapter, the collected data are analysed, and the study's findings are discussed. As stated in Chapter 3, this study used Stata Release 15 statistical analysis software to analyse data obtained from a sample of 150 public procurement officials working in national government departments across ministerial clusters. The chapter starts with the response rate followed by the descriptive statistical analysis that provides the results of the demographic profile of the respondents. The chapter also provides the inferential statistical analysis, with specific emphasis on or reference to factor analysis, reliability analysis and relationships between research variables.

4.2 RESPONSE RATE

A total of 113 responses were collected from the 150 public procurement officials targeted in the five identified national government departments from all (five) ministerial clusters. This gave a 75% response rate, which is regarded as outstanding and well fitting for generalising the findings to a larger population, according to Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) and Johnson and Christensen (2014:347).

4.3 DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS ANALYSIS

The descriptive statistical analyses of data collected are structured under three main headings: demographic profile of respondents, factors affecting e-PP readiness and e-PP readiness challenges. The results of descriptive analyses of sampled data under each main heading are presented, interpreted and discussed in the sub-sections that follow.

4.3.1 Demographic profile information of respondents

The graphical frequency distributions of the sample of public procurement officials from the identified (five) national government departments representing each (five) ministerial cluster consisted of their age group (**Figure 4.1**), gender (**Figure 4.2**), highest level of education (**Figure 4.3**), name of government department (**Figure 4.4**), designation (**Figure 4.5**), SCM unit/division (**Figure 4.6**), number of years in public procurement/SCM (**Figure 4.7**) and knowledge of the Internet (**Figure 4.8**). The results of the frequency distributions of respondent demographic data are presented, interpreted and discussed in the paragraphs that follow.

FIGURE 4.1: Respondent age group

Figure 4.1 reflects the age group of public procurement officials from the five national government department clusters that were sampled in this study. The results show that about 28.32% (n=32) of the public procurement officials were between 46 to 60 years old, 39.82% (n=45) of public procurement officials were between 36 to 45 years of age, 29.2% (n=33) of public procurement officials were between 26 and 35 years of age, and 2.65% (n=3) of public procurement officials were between 18 and 25 years of age. Based on these results, it emerges clearly that the majority (68.14%, n=77) of public procurement officials between the ages of 36 and 60 are aging out of national government department clusters. This implies that there are fewer youths (31.85%, n=33, between the ages of 18 and 35, as defined by South Africa's Youth Development Agency Act, 2008) working in public procurement as a result of the government's failure to attract and hire young people who can accelerate reform and influence e-PP adoption because they are far more prolific users of ICT than older public procurement officials (World Bank, 2005:85). Consistent

with this view, Duma (2020:62) recommends training (and retraining) for the older generation of public procurement officials (those over the age of 36) in order to enhance support for successful e-PP readiness and adoption.

FIGURE 4.2: Gender

Figure 4.2 shows that the gender of public procurement officials from the five national government department clusters was almost equally distributed, with 51.33% (n=58) of males against 48.67% (n=55) of females. This means that there is a slightly higher number of men than women involved with public procurement in national government department clusters. This pattern is consistent with the gender profile of the South African public sector showing that gender representation still remains below 50% (Statistics South Africa, 2014:179). Based on this result, it is clear that the government has fallen short of addressing employment equality in terms of employing more women in the

workplace, particularly in procurement units of public entities, in order to reduce gender imbalances and comply with the *Employment Equity Act No. 55 of 1998*.

FIGURE 4.3: Highest level of education

According to **Figure 4.3**, 7.08% (n=8) of public procurement officials possessed a grade 12/Matric Certificate and only 1.77% (n=2) of the public procurement officials held an N6 Certificate; 18.58% (n=21) of public procurement officials had a National Diploma/Diploma. It is also seen in **Figure 4.3** that 31.86% (n=36) of public procurement officials possessed a Bachelor's Degree/Advanced Diploma/B Tech and 21.24% (n=24) were holders of Honours Degree/Postgraduate Diploma. The results further show that 17.7% (n=20) of respondents in public procurement had a Master's Degree, while 1.77% (n=2) had a Doctoral Degree. From the results, it is clear that 59.29% (n=67) of public procurement officials from the five national government department clusters had an undergraduate qualification while 40.71% (n=46) possessed a postgraduate qualification.

This shows that all public servants involved with procurement in national government department clusters were formally educated, implying that they had prerequisite computer skills, which may have a direct impact on effective e-PP readiness. This is supported by Rahim and Athmay (2013:2580) and Soga (2018:56), who found that the level of education influences e-Government service usage, with more educated staff using the services more than less educated ones.

FIGURE 4.4: National government department clusters

On national government department clusters, **Figure 4.4** reveals that 17.69% (n=20), 19.46% (n=22), 12.38% (n=14) of public procurement officials worked in the governance, state capacity and institutional development cluster, social protection, community and human development cluster, and justice, crime prevention and security cluster, respectively. The figure shows that 44.24% (n=50) of public procurement officials worked in the economic sectors, investment, employment and infrastructure development cluster,

while 6.17% (n=14) formed part of the international cooperation, trade and security cluster. **Figure 4.4** also shows that almost half (44.24%, n=50) of the public procurement officials who participated in this study belonged to the economic sectors, investment, employment and infrastructure development cluster. This suggests that the economic sectors, investment, employment and infrastructure development cluster had more public procurement officials eager and willing to share their perceptions on e-PP readiness than public procurement officials of other sampled clusters in South Africa.

FIGURE 4.5: Designation of staff within government departments

Figure 4.5 illustrates the designation of public procurement officials within government departments, with 15.04% (n=17) being administration clerks and 30.09% (n=34) working as administration officers; 20.35% (n=23) of public procurement officials were assistant directors, 15.04% (n=17) were deputy directors, and 11.5% (n=13) were directors. **Figure**

4.5 also shows that 6.19% (n=7) of public procurement officials were chief directors, while only 1.77% (n=2) were chief financial officers.

According to the public sector management level structure, there are three levels of management: low management service (administration clerks and administration officers), middle management service (MMS) (assistant directors and deputy directors), and senior management service (SMS) (directors, chief directors, and chief financial officers) (Department of Public Service and Administration, 2002). Based on the results as displayed in **Figure 4.5**, it became clear that 45.13% (n=51) of public procurement officials who responded to the questionnaire were in low level management, followed by middle level management at 35.39% (n=40), then top managerial level at 19.46% (n=22) respectively. Since top management was included, the results of this study may safely be generalised because top managers are the ones involved in decision making that has an influence on the success of e-PP readiness (Duma, 2018:21).

FIGURE 4.6: SCM unit/division

According to Ambe and Maleka (2016:660), SCM units/divisions serve as the foundation for implementing an effective SCM system throughout all spheres of government. **Figure 4.6** depicts the SCM unit/division public procurement officials work in. Public procurement officials selected one or more SCM units/divisions they work in and this resulted in a total frequency of 285. The results in **Figure 4.6** indicate that public procurement officials work in more than one SCM unit/division with Acquisition Management topping the percentage per cases at 63.72% (n=72), followed by Supply Chain Performance at 53.1% (n=60). 46.9% (n=53) of the public procurement officials worked in Demand Management, sharing the same percentage per cases with those who worked in Logistics Management and 41.59% (n=47) of public procurement officials dealt with Disposal Management. Working in a variety of SCM units/divisions helps public procurement officials to develop a comprehensive understanding of the procurement process. The National Treasury (2015:4) observed, however, that this had the unintended consequence of producing a lack of clarity on the roles and responsibilities of public procurement officials. The National Treasury's (2015:64) SCM review study recommended standardising these SCM unit/division functions in order to facilitate the adoption of standard operating procedures using common interfaces for successful e-PP readiness.

FIGURE 4.7: Number of working years in public sector procurement/SCM space

Figure 4.7 shows that 2.65% (n=3) of public procurement officials had less than 1 year working experience in public sector procurement/SCM, while 9.73% (n=11) had 1 to 4 years of working experience in public sector procurement/SCM; 16.81% (n=19) of public procurement officials had 5 to 7 years of working experience in the public sector procurement/SCM. **Figure 4.7** also shows that 28.32% (n=32) of public procurement officials had been in the procurement/SCM space for 8 to 10 years, while 42.48% (n=48) had over 11 years of experience working in public sector procurement/SCM. This implies public procurement officials with 1 to 11 years of working experience were more informed on and experienced in traditional paper-based public procurement systems than those with less than 1 year of experience. This finding also showed that a high number of public procurement officials do not leave the public sector procurement sections, indicating a low staff turnover. While this is a good factor for the public procurement profession, it has a negative impact on e-PP readiness because procurement officials would need to change their mindset to accept new procurement approaches.

FIGURE 4.8: Knowledge of the Internet

Figure 4.8 shows that out of a total of 113 public procurement officials who rated their knowledge of the Internet, 40.71% (n=46) indicated that their knowledge of the Internet was very good, followed those whose knowledge of the Internet was reasonably good (39.82%, n=45) and then those who indicated that they had an average Internet knowledge (17.7%, n=20). Only 1.77% (n=2) of public procurement officials had a very poor knowledge of the Internet. This means that the majority (80.53%, n=91) of public procurement officials were able to use and engage with the Internet, which is a significant step towards readiness for e-PP adoption.

4.3.2 Factors affecting e-PP readiness

The graphical frequency distributions of factors affecting e-PP readiness (operating environment, legal environment, economic environment, organisational environment and

technological environment) are tabulated per variable according to each factor and an interpretation and discussion of these frequency distribution results are also provided using a five-point Likert scale.

4.3.2.1 Operating environment

The procurement environment contains comprises components of e-PP support, drivers of e-PP adoption and procurement structures that currently operate with a dual paradigm, partly paper-based, with some electronic features. In this environment, the frequency distribution results on procurement policy, structure of the procurement system, electronic features and overall level of e-PP adoption are presented and interpreted.

4.3.2.1.1 Procurement policy

Figure 4.9 provides the frequency distribution of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with regard to the statement that procurement policy prevents the implementation of e-PP system.

FIGURE 4.9: Procurement policy

The results, as illustrated in **Figure 4.9**, indicate that 8.85% (n=10) of the public procurement officials strongly agreed, 46.01% (n=52) agreed and 31.86% (n=36) of public procurement officials neither agreed nor disagreed that the government's procurement policy prevents the implementation of a e-PP system. **Figure 4.9** also showed that 5.31% (n=6) of public procurement officials disagreed with the statement and 7.96% (n=9) strongly disagreed. This means that the majority (54.87 %, n=62) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed that the government's procurement policy prohibits the use of the e-PP system, compared to 13.27 % (n=15) who disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement. This finding is consistent with the findings of the Australian Government Information Office (2005) and Doherty, McConnell, and Ellis-Chadwick (2013), who suggest that a lack of public policy on e-PP was a barrier to e-PP adoption in various countries.

Government departments frequently have competing priorities to attend to, such as economic transformation and job creation, and e-PP is always not one of these. This is why e-PP has been successful in governments where these priorities, as well as policy reforms, have been clearly stated and maintained.

4.3.2.1.2 Procurement structure

Figure 4.10 presents the frequency distribution of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with regard to the statement that the structure of the procurement system is favourable to the adoption of e-PP.

FIGURE 4.10: Structure of the procurement system

The results in **Figure 4.10** show that 7.08% (n=8) of the public procurement officials strongly agreed that the procurement system structure is favourable to the adoption of e-PP, and 41.59% (n=47) agreed. A total of 19.47% (n=22) of public procurement officials

were neutral about the statement. An equally distributed percentage (15.93%, n=18) was found among public procurement officials who disagreed with the statement and for those who strongly disagreed. Results from **Figure 4.10** reveal that approximately 49% (n=55) of public procurement officials strongly agreed and agreed to some degree that the procurement system structure is favourable to the adoption of e-PP, while 31.86% (n=36) of public procurement officials disagreed and strongly disagreed. Although a nearly half of public procurement officials agreed with the statement, the percentage of those who disagreed with the statement deserve some attention. The widening gap between both views may be attributed to the high level of decentralisation of South Africa's procurement system. This is inferred by National Treasury's (2015:3) acknowledgement of the wide fragmentation of South Africa's public procurement due to factors such as the legal environment and legacy systems. To address the challenges related to the decentralised procurement system, the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD, 2015:15) suggests that public entities must investigate and leverage the potential of centralisation to improve efficiency of the public procurement system.

4.3.2.1.3 Partial electronic features

Figure 4.11 presents the frequency distribution of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with regard to the statement that the use of partial electronic features restricts the adoption of a full e-PP system.

FIGURE 4.11: Use of partial electronic features

The results in **Figure 4.11** show that 9.73% (n=11) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that the use of partial electronic features (i.e., Central Supplier Database and eTender publication portal) prevents the adoption of a full e-PP system and 15.93% (n=18) agreed, 36.28% disagreed and 19.47% strongly disagreed. Those who were neither in agreement nor in disagreement were 18.58% (n=21). The majority of public procurement officials (55.75%, n=63) disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement against 25.66% (n=29) who agreed and strongly agreed. The results imply that implementing partial electronic features was the first step in reforming public procurement. However, Kramer (2016:36) and Sithole (2017:169) found that introducing a few e-PP technologies to an existing traditional system at a time would result in a haphazard e-PP system.

4.3.2.1.4 Level of e-PP adoption

Figure 4.12 provides the frequency distribution of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with regard to the statement that the overall level of e-PP adoption in the public sector affects the government department decision to implement the e-PP system.

FIGURE 4.12: Level of e-PP adoption

The results, as depicted in **Figure 4.12**, show that 13.27% (n=15) of the public procurement officials strongly agreed, 27.43% (n=31) agreed, and 28.32% (n=32) of public procurement officials were uncertain as to the overall level of e-PP adoption that affect their decision to implement the e-PP system in government departments. **Figure 4.12** also shows that 20.35% (n=23) of public procurement officials disagreed with the statement and 10.62% (n=12) strongly disagreed. According to the results of **Figure 4.12**, about 41% (n=46) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed that the

overall level of e-PP adoption in the public sector affected their decision to implement the e-PP system in government departments. This is not shared by almost 31% (n=35) of the other public procurement officials in the same sampled population. The findings imply that government departments may not make individual decisions to adopt e-PP because the National Treasury should initiate e-PP legislation for approval by parliament (Vabaza, 2015:25).

4.3.2.2 Legal environment

The legal environment considers national and international jurisdiction with respect to the readiness and recognition of legislation and policies to align e-PP with manual procurement and to conform to a fair, transparent, competitive and cost-effective e-PP system.

4.3.2.2.1 National legislation

Figure 4.13 provides the frequency distribution of the level of agreement of public procurement officials regarding the statement suggesting that national legislation inhibits the adoption of e-PP in government departments.

FIGURE 4.13: National legislation inhibits the adoption of e-PP

The results exhibited in **Figure 4.13** show that 11.5% (n=13) of public procurement officials strongly agreed and 27.43% (n=31) agreed that national legislation inhibits the adoption of e-PP in government departments; 17.7% (n=20) of public procurement officials neither agreed nor disagreed with the statement. The results in **Figure 4.13** also show that 30.09% (n=34) of public procurement officials disagreed that national legislation inhibits the adoption of e-PP in government departments and only 13.27% (n=15) strongly disagreed with the statement. While 39.94% (n=44) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed that that national legislation inhibits the adoption of e-PP in government departments, 43.36% (n=49) disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement. This result demonstrates that the national legislation in place aids readiness of e-PP adoption. However, the legal framework is not yet adequately capable of allowing the full use of e-PP because South African legislation governing public

procurement does not specifically include e-PP (Anthony, 2018:44; Mpehle & Mudogwa, 2020:5).

The *Electronic Communications and Transactions Act* (ECTA), which intends to provide for electronic transactions, and to promote the use of e-government services, appears to be a legislative enabler for the adoption of e-PP (The Presidency, 2002:16). To prevent legal confusion and to offer a consolidated piece of law that addresses the specific needs of an e-PP system, it is critical that legislation specifically aimed at the regulation of e-PP in South Africa be adopted (Anthony, 2018:45).

4.3.2.2.2 International laws

Figure 4.14 presents the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement suggesting that international laws hinder the adoption of e-PP in government departments.

FIGURE 4.14: International laws hinder the adoption of e-PP

Figure 4.14 shows that 2.65% (n=3) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that international laws hinder the adoption of e-PP in government departments, and 8.85% (n=10) agreed with the statement; 28.32% (n=32) of public procurement officials neither agreed nor disagreed that international laws hinder the adoption of e-PP in government departments. **Figure 4.14** also shows that 21.24% (n=24) of public procurement officials strongly disagreed that international laws hinder the adoption of e-PP in government departments and 38.94% (n=44) disagreed. This means that over three-fifths (60.18%, n=68) of public procurement officials disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement against 11.5% (n=13) of public procurement officials who agreed and strongly agreed with the statement. International laws and charters can play a role in e-PP readiness, particularly if government departments intend to do business with international firms.

One of the international instruments that govern e-PP is the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law (UNCITRAL) (Mazibuko, 2018:31). Its purpose is to encourage trade among nations by modernising and harmonising international trade regulations (UNCITRAL, 1998:17). The model law on electronic commerce 1996 was the UNCITRAL's first legislative document (UNCITRAL, 1998). UNCITRAL then published the model law on electronic signatures 2001 (UNCITRAL, 2002), the electronic communications convention 2005 (UNCITRAL, 2007), and, most recently, the model law on electronic transferable records 2017 (UNCITRAL, 2018). The National Treasury, on

the other hand, would be responsible for ensuring that national government departments adhere to international laws and regulations governing the adoption of e-PP by.

4.3.2.2.3 South African legal framework

Figure 4.15 presents the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating that the current South African legal framework is favourable to the adoption of e-PP.

FIGURE 4.15: South African legal framework is favourable to the adoption of e-PP

The results of the frequency distribution, as shown in **Figure 4.15** indicate that 5.31% (n=6) of public procurement officials strongly agreed, and 44.25% (n=50) of public procurement officials agreed that the current South African legal framework is favourable to the adoption of the e-PP. The figure also shows that 23.01% (n=26) disagreed and 7.08% (n=8) strongly disagreed that the current South African legal framework is

favourable to the adoption of the e-PP; 20.35% (n=23) of public procurement officials were undecided on the statement, meaning that they neither agreed nor disagreed with the statement. This means that nearly half (49.56%, n=56) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed with the statement against 30.09% (n=34) who disagreed and strongly disagreed. This study's results refutes previous findings in Kenya by Orina (2013:37) that indicate that a proper legal and regulatory framework is needed to support an end-to-end e-PP system. The current South African legislation makes no specific reference to e-PP, and no amendments to the laws and regulations (*Public Finance Management Act and Preferential Procurement Policy Framework Act*) have been made to facilitate the public procurement reform process since the inception of South Africa's dual public procurement system (partly paper-based with some electronic features) (Kramer, 2016:3; Anthony, 2018:44). However, the ECTA (as mentioned in Section 4.3.2.2.1) highlighted its intention to provide for electronic transactions in order to encourage the use of e-government services (The Presidency, 2002:16).

4.3.2.2.4 Anticipated changes to legal framework

Figure 4.16 presents the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating that the anticipated changes to the South African legal framework affect the adoption of e-PP.

FIGURE 4.16: Anticipated changes to legal framework affect the adoption of e-PP

Figure 4.16 shows that 5.31% (n=6) of the public procurement officials strongly agreed, 33.63% (n=38) agreed, and 27.43% (n=31) of public procurement officials neither agreed nor disagreed that the anticipated changes to the South African legal framework affect the adoption of e-PP in government departments. The figure also shows that 28.32% (n=32) of public procurement officials disagreed and 5.31% (n=6) strongly disagreed with the statement. The frequency distribution of public procurement officials who agreed and strongly agreed, and those who disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement, differs by 5.31%. This implies that the custodians of public procurement (the National Treasury and Parliament) have not initiated sufficient changes/amendments to the current South African legal framework. Recent developments in the South African public procurement system, however, indicate that the entire regulatory framework will be redrafted in the form of a new Public Procurement Bill, with the goal of simplifying the confusing and fragmented regulations that currently govern public procurement

processes (National Treasury, 2020). It is believed that regulating e-PP through legislation will go a long way (Anthony, 2018:10). Based on the above, the researcher argues that the current regulatory framework (laws and regulations) must be reformed for successful e-PP readiness.

4.3.2.2.5 Favourable legal framework

Figure 4.17 shows the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating that the South African government provides a favourable legal framework in order to adopt e-PP.

FIGURE 4.17: Favourable legal framework to adopt e-PP

Figure 4.17 shows that 5.31% (n=6) of public procurement officials strongly agreed, and 39.82% (n=45) agreed that the South African government offered a favourable legal framework for the adoption of the e-PP; 29.2% (n=33) of public procurement officials

displayed neutrality on the statement, while 17.7% (n=20) and 7.96% (n=9) of public procurement officials respectively, disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement. The figure also reveals that 45.13% (n=51) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed that the South African government offered a favourable legal framework for the adoption of the e-PP. On the other hand, 25.66% (n=29) of public procurement officials demonstrated disagreement and strong disagreement with the statement. This result contradicts the finding in **Figure 4.16**; however, given that only two-fifths of public procurement officials agreed with the statement, it may be deduced that the legislative environment for e-PP adoption is favourable to some extent. It is therefore important that the South African government speed up procurement regulatory reform in order to demonstrate e-PP readiness and enhance the service delivery capability of public entities.

4.3.2.3 Economic environment

The economic environment is concerned with both the buyer (government departments) and the seller (suppliers and/or service providers), who should be able to cover the costs of adopting and operating the e-PP system, and consider the financial and economic challenges associated with e-PP adoption and implementation.

4.3.2.3.1 Operating costs

Figure 4.18 provides the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating that the operating costs of

government departments have decreased since the inception of partial electronic features.

FIGURE 4.18: Operating costs

The results, as depicted in **Figure 4.18**, show that 10.61% (n=12) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that operating costs in government departments have decreased since the introduction of partial electronic features (i.e., CSD and eTender Publication Portal) and 32.74% (n=37) agreed with the statement. **Figure 4.18** also shows that 25.66% (n=29) of the public procurement officials disagreed with the statement and 7.96% (n=9) strongly disagreed. The figure also shows that 23.01% (n=26) of the public procurement officials did not indicate their agreement or disagreement on the statement. Therefore, 43.36% (n=49) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed with the statement against 33.62% (n=38) who disagreed and strongly disagreed. This result suggests that partial e-PP technologies are benefiting South African public procurement

to some extent, which is consistent with the findings of Anthony (2018:46) and Mpehle and Mudogwa (2020:8). However, it should be stressed that one of the mechanisms that would enable the government to realise value for money and become more efficient is the modernisation and streamlining of procurement processes through the use of technology (Nawi, Roslan, Salleh, Zulhumadi & Harun, 2016:329).

4.3.2.3.2 Financial challenges

Figure 4.19 provides the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating that the financial challenges have affected the adoption and speed of implementing a e-PP system.

FIGURE 4.19: Financial challenges

Figure 4.19 shows that 8.85% (n=10) of public procurement officials strongly agreed and 45.13% (n=51) agreed that financial challenges have affected the adoption and speed of

implementing e-PP system, while 19.47% (n=22) of public procurement officials disagreed and 5.31% (n=6) strongly disagreed with the statement; 21.24% (n=24) of the remaining public procurement officials were neutral (neither agreed or disagreed) on whether financial challenges had an impact on e-PP adoption. More than half of the public procurement officials, nearly 54% (n=61), agreed and strongly agreed that financial challenges have impaired the acceptance and pace of the introduction of the e-PP system, compared to 24.78% (n=28) who disagreed and strongly disagreed. Given that South Africa presently uses partial e-PP (CSD and eTender), establishing an end-to-end e-PP system will need a substantial financial investment (Kramer, 2016:24). As a result, the South African government should commit considerable financial resources to the effective implementation of the e-PP system.

4.3.2.3.3 Perceived hidden costs

Figure 4.20 presents the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating that there are perceived hidden costs that hinder the adoption of e-PP.

FIGURE 4.20: Perceived hidden costs

The results in **Figure 4.20** reveal that 11.5% (n=13) of the public procurement officials strongly agreed that there are perceived hidden costs (short-term or long-term) to obstruct the adoption of e-PP, and 43.36% (n=49) agreed; 23.01% (n=26) of the public procurement officials disagreed that there are perceived hidden costs (short-term or long-term) to obstruct the adoption of e-PP and 0.88% (n=1) strongly disagreed with the assertion. **Figure 4.20** also shows that the remaining 21.24% (n=24) of public procurement officials had a neutral view (neither agreed nor disagreed) on this concern. Therefore, 54.86% (n=62) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed that there are perceived hidden costs (short-term or long-term) to obstruct the adoption of e-PP, while 23.89% (n=27) disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement. This suggests that, despite government departments' efforts to encourage suppliers and/or service providers to use e-PP, short-term or long-term hidden costs, such as maintenance and support costs, modernisation and upgrade costs, may be higher without the

necessary technical knowledge (Huai, 2012:1161). As a result, the researcher believes that proper planning, as well as technical competence and personnel, should be given the necessary attention.

4.3.2.3.4 Economic challenges

Figure 4.21 indicates the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating that there are economic challenges when sourcing for clients to use the e-PP system.

FIGURE 4.21: Economic challenges

On economic challenges, **Figure 4.21** shows that 15.04% (n=17) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that there are economic challenges when sourcing for clients to use the e-PP system and 42.48% (n=48) agreed; 22.12% (n=25) of the public procurement officials disagreed with this statement, but none of public procurement

officials strongly disagreed. **Figure 4.21** also shows that the remaining 20.35% (n=23) of public procurement officials did not express their opinion about whether there are economic challenges in sourcing for clients to use the e-PP system. This means that the majority (57.32%, n=65) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed, compared to 22.12% (n=25) who disagreed. This demonstrates the economic challenges that government departments will have in finding suppliers to use e-PP, given that not only public procurement officials, but also suppliers who will use the e-PP system, will require training and support for active participation (Asian Development Bank, 2013:2; Mpehle & Mudogwa, 2020:4).

4.3.2.4 Organisational environment

The organisational environment centred on the planned level of adoption, the value of awareness of the potential impact of e-PP on organisational performance and the need to understand the antecedents of employees' acceptance.

4.3.2.4.1 Ethical challenges

Figure 4.22 provides the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating that there are ethical challenges in government departments that prevent the adoption of e-PP.

FIGURE 4.22: Ethical challenges

Figure 4.22 indicates that 8.85% (n=10) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that there are ethical challenges in their department that prevent the adoption of e-PP, and 32.74% (n=37) agreed; 31.86% (n=36) and 6.19% (n=7) of the public procurement officials disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement, respectively. **Figure 4.22** also shows that 20.35% (n=23) of the public procurement officials neither agreed nor disagreed with the statement. A total of 41.59% (n=47) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed with the statement, while 38.05% (n=43) disagreed and strongly disagreed. A narrow difference between the two opinions of public procurement officials may indicate uncertainty about ethical concerns (such as acts of corruption, fraud, nepotism, and bribery) in government departments that prevent e-PP adoption. The integrity of public sector procurement must be preserved, and e-PP seems to be a potential solution.

4.3.2.4.2 Negative attitude of employees towards adoption of e-PP system

Figure 4.23 presents the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating that the negative attitude of employees towards adoption of e-PP system is an obstacle to the e-PP system implementation in the department.

FIGURE 4.23: Negative attitude

Figure 4.23 shows that 11.5% (n=13) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that the negative attitude of employees towards the adoption of the e-PP system is an obstacle to the e-PP system implementation in government departments, 34.51% (n=39) agreed and 17.99% (n=20) neither agreed nor disagreed with the statement. The results also show that 29.2% (n=33) of public procurement officials disagreed that the negative attitude of employees against the adoption of an e-PP system is an obstacle to adoption in the department, while 7.08% (n=8) strongly disagreed. Therefore, 46.01% (n=52) of

public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed that the negative attitude of employees towards adoption of e-PP system is an obstacle to the e-PP system implementation in government departments, compared to 36.28% (n=41) who disagreed and strongly disagreed. Based on this finding, government departments should motivate and train public procurement officials to develop a positive attitude towards the adoption e-PP system. Such an endeavour would prevent excessive resistance and sabotage of the implementation of the e-PP system in government departments (Kusi, Antwi, Nani, Mensah & Akomeah, 2016:643).

4.3.2.4.3 Transparency challenges

Figure 4.24 presents the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating that there are transparency challenges in government departments about adoption of e-PP.

FIGURE 4.24: Transparency challenges

The results in **Figure 4.24** show that 9.73% (n=11) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that there are transparency challenges in government departments about adoption of e-PP, 30.97% (n=35) agreed, and 25.66% (n=29) displayed neutrality on the matter. **Figure 4.24** also shows that 27.43% (n=31) of public procurement officials disagreed that the adoption of the e-PP poses transparency challenges for government departments, and 6.19% (n=7) strongly disagreed. This means that 40.7% (n=46) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed with the assertion, while 33.62% (n=38) disagreed and strongly disagreed. Transparency in e-PP system plays a vital role because it ensures that public procurement information is open and accessible to role players (i.e., users, suppliers and other decision makers) (Asian Development Bank, 2013:14). This reduces the opportunities for corruption during the procurement process and the amount of authority exerted by public procurement officials (Mundree, 2018:22).

4.3.2.4.4 Accountability issues

Figure 4.25 provides the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating that there are accountability issues in the adoption of e-PP in government departments.

FIGURE 4.25: Accountability issues

Figure 4.25 shows that 10.62% (12) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that there are accountability issues in the adoption of e-PP government departments, 38.05% (n=43) agreed, and 23.89% (n=27) decided not to indicate their position on this issue (they neither agreed nor disagreed); 23.89% (n=27) of public procurement officials disagreed and 3.54% (n=4) strongly disagreed that there are accountability issues in the adoption of e-PP in government departments. This suggests that 48.67% (n=55) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed that there are accountability issues in the adoption of e-PP in government departments against 27.43% (n=31) of public procurement officials who disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement. With the numerous issues that public procurement faces, such as transparency and corruption, e-PP use will provide an audit trail that is critical for ensuring accountability in the procurement process, and this could be used against public procurement officials who

engage in malfeasance, as procurement transactions would be available and traceable (Sithole, 2017:48).

4.3.2.4.5 Leadership gap

Figure 4.26 provides the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating that a leadership gap in the department prevents e-PP adoption.

FIGURE 4.26: Leadership gap

The results in **Figure 4.26** show that 17.7% (n=20) of the public procurement officials strongly agreed that a leadership gap in government departments prevents e-PP adoption and 30.09% (n=34) agreed with the statement. 23.89% (n=27) of the public procurement officials had a neutral view on the matter as they neither agreed nor disagreed. The figure also displays that 23.89% (n=27) of public procurement officials disagreed that a

leadership gap in government departments prevents e-PP adoption, while 4.42% (n=5) strongly disagreed. The majority (47.79%, n=54) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed that a gap in departmental leadership prevents e-PP adoption, compared to 28.31% (n=32) who disagreed and strongly disagreed. This result suggests that adequate leadership support is needed in order to be ready for successful e-PP adoption. This finding supports the views of various scholars (Eadie, Perera, Heaney, & Carlisle, 2007:111; Koech, Ayoyi & Mugambi, 2016:22; Anthony, 2018:43) who indicate that a lack of leadership at the top of the hierarchy to steer government departments toward readiness to adopt e-PP is likely to permeate the entire public sector and cripple e-PP implementation efforts.

4.3.2.4.6 System implementation

Figure 4.27 presents the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating that system implementation is a problem in government departments.

FIGURE 4.27: System implementation

Figure 4.27 shows that 18.58% (n=21) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that system implementation is a problem in the department, and 33.63% (n=38) of public procurement officials agreed with the statement; 16.81% (n=19) of public procurement officials were neutral (they neither agreed nor disagreed) on the statement. **Figure 4.27** also reveals that 24.78% (n=28) of public procurement officials disagreed that system implementation is a problem in the department and 6.19% (n=7) strongly agreed. From **Figure 4.27** it can be observed that the largest (52.21%, n=59) proportion of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed that system implementation is a problem for government departments, compared to 30.97% (n=35) who disagreed and strongly disagreed. This finding could be explained by various factors and one of these could be the lack of a single or integrated procurement system that is currently being used by a government department (National Treasury, 2015:59). This fragmentation of systems with no discernible relationships needs to be addressed to ensure an efficient e-PP

system. The researcher argues that the implementation of an efficient e-PP system largely depends on the adequacy of readiness factors in order to facilitate proper planning and minimise system implementation challenges.

4.3.2.5 Technological environment

The technology environment is concerned with the government’s allocation of the required infrastructure at all levels to disseminate the e-PP service effectively and efficiently.

4.3.2.5.1 Challenges of preparedness

Figure 4.28 provides the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating that there are challenges regarding preparedness when migrating from paper-based to e-PP.

FIGURE 4.28: Challenges of preparedness

Figure 4.28 shows that 28.32% (n=32) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that there are challenges regarding preparedness when migrating from paper-based to e-PP: 51.33% (n=58) agreed; 8.85% (n=10) of public procurement officials disagreed with the above concern, and 2.65% (n=3) strongly disagreed. **Figure 4.28** also shows that 8.85% (n=10) of public procurement officials were neutral (neither agreed nor disagreed) on whether there are challenges of preparedness when transitioning from paper-based to e-PP. This means that over seven tenths (79.65%, n=90) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed with the statement, against 11.5% (n=13) of public procurement officials who disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement. This means that government departments should create a roadmap or plan outlining the specific steps that must be taken to completely transition from a paper-based procurement system to an e-PP system. This seems to be supported by the findings of Kalakota and Robinson (2001:272) and Patel, Kumar and Khajuria (2016:265).

4.3.2.5.2 System incompatibility

Figure 4.29 provides the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating that there are system incompatibilities when implementing the new IT system in government departments.

FIGURE 4.29: System incompatibility

Figure 4.29 shows that 28.32% (n=32) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that there are system incompatibilities in the implementation of the new IT system in government departments and 43.36% (n=49) agreed with the statement. A total of 16.81% (n=19) of public procurement officials did not express their opinion (neither agreed nor disagreed) about whether system incompatibilities exist when implementing the new IT system in the department, compared to 9.73% (n=11) who disagreed and 1.77% (n=2) who strongly disagreed. This means that the majority (71.68%, n=81) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed with the statement, whilst just 11.5% (n=14) disagreed and strongly disagreed. Incompatibilities in the IT system (both hardware and software) are a barrier to the success of e-PP. Therefore, government procuring entities should use compatible IT systems to ensure successful e-PP implementation.

4.3.2.5.3 Software infrastructure

Figure 4.30 presents the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating that government departments are not well equipped in terms of systems software infrastructure.

FIGURE 4.30: Software infrastructure

Figure 4.30 indicates that 23.01% (n=26) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that government departments are not well equipped in terms of systems software infrastructure, and 37.17% (n=42) agreed with the statement; 16.81% (n=19) of public procurement officials remained undecided (neither agreed nor disagreed) on the statement. The results also show that 19.47% (n=22) of public procurement officials disagreed that government departments are not well equipped in terms of systems software infrastructure, and 3.54% (n=4) strongly disagreed; 60.18% (n=68) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed with the statement, while 23.01%

(n=26) disagreed and strongly disagreed with it. When adopting the e-PP system, procuring entities should equip their government departments with the adequate software infrastructure to drive efficient e-PP. If government departments are unable to invest in system software infrastructure, they can look to the private sector and foreign aid for assistance (De la Harpe, 2015:1572).

4.3.2.5.4 Network system

Figure 4.31 presents the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating that government departments’ network system is inadequate for e-PP operations.

FIGURE 4.31: Network system

Figure 4.31 shows that 21.24% (n=24) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that the network system of government departments is inadequate for e-PP operations,

30.97% (n=35) strongly agreed, and 22.12% (n=25) were neutral on the statement; 19.47% (n=22) of public procurement officials disagreed that the network system of government departments is inadequate for e-PP operations and 6.19% (n=7) strongly disagreed. This means that 25.66% (n=29) of public procurement officials disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement, while 52.21% (n=59) agreed and strongly agreed. This finding suggests that an e-PP system is reliant on a faster and more dependable network system than the system that is currently operated by government departments. Slow download speeds and limited access to broadband outside of major economic centres (rural/poorer areas) can impede efforts to prepare government departments for e-PP adoption.

4.3.2.5.5 Staff preparedness

Figure 4.32 provides the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating that the staff is inadequately prepared to work with the new IT system and the Internet.

FIGURE 4.32: Staff preparedness

The results exhibited in **Figure 4.32** show that 16.81% (n=19) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that the staff is inadequately prepared to work with the new IT system and the Internet and 31.86% (n=36) agreed. **Figure 4.32** shows that 19.47% (n=22) of public procurement officials hold a neutral opinion (neither agreed or disagreed) that the staff is inadequately prepared to work with the new IT system and the Internet, with 24.78% (n=28) who disagreed and 7.08% (n=8) who strongly disagreed. Therefore, 31.86% (n=36) of public procurement officials disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement, while 48.67% (n=55) agreed and strongly agreed. This means that a majority of public procurement officials perceived that they are not adequately prepared to work with modern IT technology and the internet, owing to a lack of positive professional development. However, the trend towards automation of procurement processes may result in the retrenchment of unprepared public procurement officials.

4.3.2.5.6 Staff skills in ICT

Figure 4.33 provides the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with regard to the statement indicating that the staff is inadequately skilled in ICT to deal with e-PP system.

FIGURE 4.33: Staff skills in ICT

Figure 4.33 indicates that 15.04% (n=17) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that the staff is inadequately skilled in ICT to deal with e-PP system and 36.28% (n=41) of public procurement officials agreed. Another 19.47% (n=22) of public procurement officials responded that they neither agreed nor disagreed with the statement. **Figure 4.33** also shows that 23.89% (n=27) of public procurement officials disagreed that the staff is inadequately skilled in ICT to deal with e-PP system and 5.31% (n=6) of public procurement officials strongly disagreed with the statement. This means that 29.2% (n=33) of public procurement officials disagreed and strongly disagreed that the staff is

inadequately skilled in ICT to deal with e-PP system, compared to 51.32% (n=58) who agreed and strongly agreed. This finding suggests that some public procurement officials lack the necessary ICT skills to work with the e-PP system. This finding seems to be consistent with the finding of Kusi *et al.* (2016:649) who indicated that a lack of ICT skills might lead to anxiety, a negative attitude and a lack of willingness to use e-PP system. To reap the full range of potential benefits from the e-PP system, it is critical to make financial commitments towards the training of public procurement officials on e-PP use as well as IT skills to be able to effectively transact over the Internet.

4.3.2.5.7 Integration of IT systems

Figure 4.34 presents the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials regarding the statement indicating that the department integrates its IT system with other directorates within the department.

FIGURE 4.34: Integration of IT systems

Figure 4.34 shows that 8.85% (n=10) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that their department integrates its IT system with other directorates within the department and 43.36% (n=49) agreed. Another 25.66% (n=29) of public procurement officials were unsure (neither agreed or disagreed) about this assertion. The figure also shows that 16.81% (n=19) of public procurement officials disagreed that their department integrates its IT system with other directorates within the department and 5.31% (n=6) strongly disagreed with the statement. This means 52.21% (n=59) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed that their department integrates its IT system with other directorates within the department, while 22.12% (n=25) disagreed and strongly disagreed. This finding seems contradictory to that of **Figure 4.27**, suggesting that system implementation was a problem for government departments due to possibly lack of a single or integrated procurement system. These contradictory findings from this study call for other studies on the topic in government departments with a bigger sample size to shed more light on the situation and provide a clear stance in confirmation or disconfirmation of findings from **Figure 4.27** or **Figure 4.32**.

4.3.2.5.8 Technical challenges

Figure 4.35 provides the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with regard to the statement indicating that there are technical challenges in the e-PP system that prevent its adoption.

FIGURE 4.35: Technical challenges

Figure 4.35 show that 12.39% (n=14) of public procurement officials strongly agreed and 35.4% (n=40) agreed that the e-PP system has technical challenges that prevent it from being adopted; 30.97% (n=35) of public procurement officials neither agreed nor disagreed with the statement. **Figure 4.35** also shows that 19.47% (n=22) of public procurement officials disagreed that there are technical challenges in the e-PP system that prevent its adoption and 1.77% (n=2) of public procurement officials strongly disagreed. Based on the results of the figure, it is observed that 47.69% (n=54) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed with the statement, while 21.24% (n=24) disagreed and strongly disagreed. These technical challenges could be attributed to partial (CSD and eTender) e-PP features introduced by the South African government. Therefore, there is a need for a full e-PP overhaul in order to reform public procurement in light of the capability of emerging technology and improve the efficiency of public procurement processes.

4.3.3 E-PP readiness challenges

There are various readiness challenges associated with e-PP adoption. These include resistance to change, staff skills, staff transparency, staff enthusiasm, competition, corruption, e-PP system acquisition cost, e-PP system running cost, operating systems, procurement policies, procurement legislation, and confidential information. The frequency distributions of e-PP readiness challenges are provided in **Figures 4.36, 4.37, 4.38, 4.39, 4.40, 4.41, 4.42, 4.43, 4.44, 4.45, 4.46 and 4.47**. The results from the frequency distributions are presented, interpreted and discussed in the sub-sections that follow.

4.3.3.1 Resistance to change

Figure 4.36 provides the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating resistance to change as a readiness challenge to e-PP adoption.

FIGURE 4.36: Resistance to change

Figure 4.36 shows that 22.12% (n=25) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that resistance to change is a challenge associated with government departments' readiness to e-PP adoption, while 39.83% (n=45) agreed; 14.16% (n=16) of public procurement officials neither agreed nor disagreed whether resistance to change is a readiness challenge associated with government departments' readiness to e-PP adoption. **Figure 4.36** also shows that 22.12% (n=25) of public procurement officials disagreed and 1.77% (n=2) strongly disagreed with the statement. This suggests that 61.94% (n=70) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed that resistance to change is a readiness challenge to e-PP adoption, compared to 23.89% (n=27) who disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement. This implies that there is resistance to change in many government departments and public procurement officials are satisfied with the current procurement system. The negative attitude of public procurement officials towards the adoption of an e-PP system, as shown in **Figure 4.23**, may be one of the

main drivers of resistance to change. This has been listed among e-PP adoption challenges within government departments by Orina (2013:34) and United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, (2018:3). Such attitude towards e-PP adoption hinders government departments from enhancing procurement process efficiency (Kabanda, Pitso & Kapepo, 2019:242).

4.3.3.2 Staff skills

Figure 4.37 presents the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating poor staff skills as a readiness challenge to e-PP adoption.

FIGURE 4.37: Staff skills

Figure 4.37 indicates that 15.93% (n=18) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that poor staff skills are a challenge associated with government departments' readiness to adopt the e-PP system; 34.51% (n=39) agreed and 16.81% (n=19) did not articulate their stance on this statement (neither agreed nor disagreed). **Figure 4.37** also shows that 29.2% (n=33) of public procurement officials disagreed that poor staff skills are a challenge associated with government departments' readiness to the adoption of the e-PP system, while only 3.54% (n=4) strongly disagreed. It is observed that over half (50.44%, n=57) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed that poor staff skills are a challenge associated with government departments' readiness to adopt e-PP, compared to 32.74% (n=37) who disagreed and strongly disagreed with this statement. This finding is consistent with the findings of the Department of Telecommunications and Postal Services' (DTPS) (2017:39) report on South Africa's e-Government strategy and roadmap, which mentions a shortage of ICT local skills to implement and use e-Government services. Therefore, in order for the e-PP system to be successfully adopted in the public sector, a skills gap must be bridged, either by officially recognising SCM as a profession or by organising e-PP-related courses for public procurement officials. This would assist in upskilling through training public procurement officials who did not have a SCM or procurement qualification but who were working in the public procurement space.

4.3.3.3 Staff transparency

Figure 4.38 presents the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with regard to the statement indicating staff transparency as a readiness challenge to e-PP adoption.

FIGURE 4.38: Staff transparency

Figure 4.38 reveals that 12.39% (n=14) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that transparency of staff in the execution of their duties is a challenge associated with the readiness of government departments to adopt the e-PP system and 37.17% (n=42) agreed. Another 19.47% (n=22) of public procurement officials were unsure (neither agreed or disagreed) on whether staff transparency is a challenge associated with the readiness of government departments to adopt the e-PP system. **Figure 4.38** also reveals that 26.55% (n=30) of public procurement officials disagreed with the statement, while

4.42% (n=5) strongly disagreed. A total of 49.56% (n=56) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed that staff transparency is a challenge associated with the readiness of government departments to adopt the e-PP system, although 30.97% (n=35) disagreed and strongly disagreed. This may be due to the vulnerability of public procurement to corruption, maladministration and mismanagement. According to Transparency International's (2020:2) report, South Africa rated 44 out of 100, ranking 69 and being one of the two-thirds of countries with serious levels of corruption. The transparency that comes with the adoption of e-PP has ignited opposition from public procurement officials, hampering e-PP readiness (Purchasing & Procurement Center 2017; Mpehle & Mudogwa, 2020:3).

4.3.3.4 Staff enthusiasm

Figure 4.39 provides the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials regarding the statement indicating lack of staff enthusiasm as a readiness challenge to e-PP adoption.

FIGURE 4.39: Staff enthusiasm

Figure 4.39 demonstrates that 15.04% (n=17) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that lack of staff enthusiasm is a readiness challenge associated with e-PP adoption and 34.51% (n=39) agreed. A total of 20.35% (n=23) of public procurement officials neither agreed nor disagreed with the statement. The results also show that 26.55% (n=30) of public procurement officials disagreed and 3.54% (n=4) strongly disagreed that lack of staff enthusiasm is a readiness challenge associated with e-PP adoption. This means that nearly half (49.55%, n=56) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed with the assertion, while 30.09% (n=34) disagreed and strongly disagreed. Therefore, the majority of public procurement officials are not enthusiastic (hence their negative attitude - **FIGURE 4.23**) about adopting an e-PP system in their departments, revealing an e-PP readiness challenge. Such an attitude displays a barrier to e-PP adoption, and government departments should therefore

educate and train public procurement officials on the roles, benefits and capacities of an e-PP system (Orina, 2013:38; Sithole, 2017:167; Rukuni, Maziriri & Mulaudzi, 2020:18).

4.3.3.5 Competition

Figure 4.40 provides the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with regard to the statement indicating competition from other departments as a readiness challenge to e-PP adoption. Competition occurs when a government department has competitors (rivals) to benchmark performance.

FIGURE 4.40: Competition

The results, as displayed in **Figure 4.40**, show that 9.73% (n=11) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that competition from other departments is a challenge to e-PP readiness, and 12.29% (n=14) agreed; 35.4% (n=40) of public procurement officials were

neutral about the statement. **Figure 4.40** also shows that 35.4% (n=40) of public procurement officials disagreed that competition from other departments is a challenge associated with readiness of government departments to adopt an e-PP system, while 7.08% (n=8) strongly disagreed. As a result, 22.12% (n=25) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed with this statement, compared to 42.48% (n=48) who disagreed and strongly disagreed. Since government departments do not compete, it may be concluded that competition between departments does not pose a readiness challenge for them to adopt e-PP. As a result, public entities lack competitors against whom they may compare their performance (Orina, 2013:26).

4.3.3.6 Corruption

Figure 4.41 presents the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating corruption in the procurement process as a readiness challenge to e-PP adoption.

FIGURE 4.41: Corruption

Figure 4.41 shows that only 21.24% (n=24) of public procurement officials strongly disagreed that corruption in the procurement process is a challenge associated with government departments readiness to e-PP adoption, 24.78% (n=28) agreed, and 27.43% (n=31) neither agreed nor disagreed with the statement. **Figure 4.41** also shows that 22.12% (n=25) of public procurement officials disagreed that corruption in the procurement process is a challenge associated with government departments' readiness for e-PP adoption and 4.42% (n=5) strongly disagreed. This suggests that 46.02% (n=52) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed with the statement, compared to 26.54% (n=30) who disagreed and strongly disagreed with it. This result confirms the National Treasury report (National Treasury, 2016:7) that indicates that corruption is a common problem in South African government departments, with the current paper-based procurement system being the single largest source. To address corruption, it is believed that the full use of e-PP could play a vital role in reducing the scourge of

corruption since the public procurement system will be traceable and auditable (Bello & Iyagba, 2013; Mundree, 2018:22).

4.3.3.7 E-PP system acquisition cost

Figure 4.42 provides the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with regard to the statement indicating high cost of acquiring the e-PP system as a readiness challenge to e-PP adoption.

FIGURE 4.42: E-PP system acquisition cost

Figure 4.42 shows that 19.47% (n=22) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that the high cost of acquiring the e-PP system is related to the readiness challenges of adopting e-PP and 44.25% (n=50) agreed; 12.39% (n=14) of public procurement officials disagreed that the high cost of acquiring the e-PP system is related to the readiness

challenges of adopting the e-PP and 2.65% (n=3) of the public procurement officials strongly disagreed with the statement. **Figure 4.42** also shows that 21.24% (n=24) of the public procurement officials neither agreed nor disagreed that the high cost of acquiring the e-PP system is related to the readiness challenges of adopting the e-PP; 63.72% (n=72) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed with the statement, while 15.04% (n=17) disagreed and strongly disagreed with it. This finding concurs with those of Kramer (2016:24) who states that a certified ready-to-use e-PP system would necessitate a significant financial commitment, since high costs involved can be financially debilitating for governments. However, the cost savings may be major benefits of adopting an e-PP system, among other aspects.

4.3.3.8 E-PP system running cost

Figure 4.43 provides the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating perceived high cost of running the e-PP system as a challenge to e-PP adoption readiness.

FIGURE 4.43: E-PP system running cost

Figure 4.43 illustrates that 15.04% (n=17) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that the perceived high cost of operating the e-PP system is a challenge to e-PP adoption readiness, 53.1% (n=60) agreed and 17.7% (n=20) were neutral about the statement. **Figure 4.43** also displays that 11.5% (n=13) of public procurement officials disagreed and 2.65% (n=3) strongly disagreed that the perceived high cost of operating the e-PP system is a challenge to e-PP adoption readiness. It is therefore observed that more than six tenths (68.14%, n=77) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed with the statement, compared to 14.15% (n=16) who disagreed and strongly disagreed. This means that the cost factors (including hidden costs) incurred prior to and after e-PP adoption must be measured and quantified in order to comprehend the likely outcomes of e-PP adoption.

4.3.3.9 Fragmented operating systems

Figure 4.44 presents the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with regard to the statement indicating fragmentation of operating systems within government departments as a challenge to e-PP adoption readiness.

FIGURE 4.44: Fragmented operating systems

The results of **Figure 4.44** show that 16.81% (n=19) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that fragmentation (disintegration) of operating systems (i.e., Logis, Intenda, SAP, etc.) within government departments is a readiness challenge in adopting an e-PP system, while 49.56% (n=56) agreed; 25.66% (n=29) of public procurement officials neither agreed or disagreed that fragmentation of operating systems within government departments is a readiness challenge in adopting an e-PP system. **Figure 4.44** also indicates that 6.29% (n=7) of public procurement officials disagreed with the

statement and 1.77% (n=2) strongly disagreed. This means that almost three-fifths (66.37%, n=75) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed that the fragmentation of operating systems within government departments poses a readiness challenge to the adoption of the e-PP system, whilst the smallest proportion (7.96%, n=9) disagreed and strongly disagreed with the assertion. This finding is consistent with the National Treasury report (2015:59) that acknowledges that South Africa's public procurement is currently supported by a variety of systems that are fragmented, underutilised, and vary in functionality, scale and performance.

4.3.3.10 Procurement policies

Figure 4.45 presents the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating the influence of procurement policies as a challenge to e-PP adoption readiness.

FIGURE 4.45: Procurement policies

Figure 4.45 displays that 13.27% of public procurement officials strongly agreed that influence of procurement policies is a challenge to e-PP system readiness and (n=15) 48.67% (n=55) agreed with the statement; 23.89% (n=27) of public procurement officials neither agreed nor disagreed with the statement. **Figure 4.45** also shows that 12.39% (n=14) of public procurement officials disagreed that influence of procurement policies is a challenge to e-PP system readiness and 1.77% strongly disagreed with this claim. It emerged from the observation of the figures that the majority (61.94%, n=70) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed with the statement, whereas 14.16% (n=16) disagreed and strongly disagreed. However, the influence of procurement policies on e-PP adoption readiness needs to be investigated further by means of inferential statistics.

4.3.3.11 Procurement legislation

Figure 4.46 provides the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating proper procurement legislation as a challenge to e-PP readiness.

FIGURE 4.46: Procurement legislation

Figure 4.46 shows that 12.39% (n=14) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that proper procurement legislation is a challenge associated with readiness of government departments to adopt e-PP system, 47.79% (n=54) of public procurement officials agreed and 23.89% (n=27) were neutral regarding this statement. Results from **Figure 4.46** also show that 12.39% (n=14) of public procurement officials disagreed with the statement, while 3.54% (n=4) strongly disagreed. This means that 60.18% (n=68) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed that proper procurement legislation is a challenge associated with the readiness of government departments to adopt an e-PP system, compared to 15.93% (n=18) who disagreed and strongly disagreed. Therefore, this finding suggests that the current procurement legislation deters e-PP adoption and thereby displays the unreadiness of government departments to tap into the full benefits of e-PP adoption. There are currently too many pieces of legislation (local, provincial, and national) governing public procurement, and having consolidated

public sector procurement legislation, free of loopholes and inconsistencies, would be ideal in South Africa (Manyathi, 2019:208). This finding confirms our literature review (Chapter 2) findings, particularly Kramer (2016:36), highlighting that e-PP requires a comprehensive and supportive legislative and regulatory framework.

4.3.3.12 Confidential information

Figure 4.47 provides the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with regard to the statement suggesting perception of loss of confidential information as a challenge to e-PP readiness.

FIGURE 4.47: Confidential information

Figure 4.47 reveals that 18.58% (n=21) of public procurement officials strongly agreed that perception of loss of confidential information is one of the readiness challenges of

government departments in e-PP adoption and 32.74% (n=37) of public procurement officials agreed with the statement. **Figure 4.47** also indicates that 21.24% (n=24) of public procurement officials disagreed that perception of loss of confidential information is a challenge that needs to be considered in order to ensure the successful adoption of the e-PP and 4.42% (n=5) strongly disagreed; 23.01% (n=26) of public procurement officials neither agreed nor disagreed with the statement. This means that 51.32% (n=58) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed with the statement against 25.66% (n=29) who disagreed and strongly disagreed. This finding indicates the necessity that adequate precaution be taken when adopting and implementing the e-PP system to maintain a high degree of confidentiality in order to guard against vulnerabilities of the information systems of government departments and risks associated with the adoption and implementation of e-PP systems. Consistent with this view, Narang and Narang (2017:8) argue that for an organisation to contain the security risks and protect information systems, as well as to safeguard data confidentiality, availability and the integrity of public procurement processes, a security control should be considered.

4.3.3.13 Shift from the current paper-based procurement system to e-PP

Figure 4.48 presents the frequency distribution results of the level of agreement of public procurement officials with respect to the statement indicating whether public procurement officials would recommend a shift from the current paper-based procurement system to an e-PP system.

FIGURE 4.48: Shift from the current paper-based procurement system to e-PP

Figure 4.48 shows that 80.53% (n=91) of public procurement officials affirmed that they would recommend a shift from the current paper-based procurement system to e-PP. The figure also shows that 10.62% (n=12) of public procurement officials indicate that they would not recommend a shift from the current paper-based procurement system to e-PP and 8.85% (n=10) did not express an opinion about the statement. This suggests that about seven-tenths (80.53%, n=91) of public procurement officials agreed with the assertion, while 10.62% (n=12) disagreed. Based on this result, it can be observed that public procurement officials recognise that the time is ripe for the South African government to transition from a traditional paper-based public procurement system to an e-PP system. As a result, the researcher states that an e-PP system can be a tool to reform the South African public procurement system if supporting structures (i.e., readiness aspects) are in place.

It should be noted that comments from public procurement officials, as asked on V48 of the questionnaire, are summarised in **Table 4.20** and discussed in Appendix A. The following section presents factor analysis and reliability

4.4 FACTOR ANALYSIS AND RELIABILITY

4.4.1 Factorial structure of the questionnaire

A factor analysis with principal component was used to assess the factorial structure of the questionnaire. First, data were tested for factor analysis adequacy using the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sample adequacy and Bartlett's test of sphericity. The results of the KMO and Bartlett's test are presented in Section 4.4.1.1. Based on the results of these tests, the researcher proceeded to perform the principal component factor analysis using the Varimax rotation of the 27 Likert scale questions from the questionnaire. Factor retention was informed by the Kaiser criterion, where only factors with Eigenvalues greater than 1 were retained (Kaiser, 1960). The results of the factor analysis are presented in Section 4.4.1.2.

4.4.1.1 KMO and Bartlett's test

As depicted in **Table 4.1** below, the KMO measure of the sample adequacy was 0.820. This figure meets the requirements (0.60 or higher) for proceeding with factor analysis, as recommended by Kaiser (1970), Field (2018:1005), and Tabachnick and Fidell

(2019:483). The results for Bartlett's test of sphericity used for assessing the correlation matrix adequacy showed an appropriately observed chi-squared value of 1245.755 with 351 degrees of freedom and the level of significance (p-value) of 0.000. This means both the observed chi-squared value and degree of freedom are very large and the p-value is smaller than 0.05. Furthermore, these estimated values indicate a fair justification and appropriateness for performing factor analysis to identify major predictors of e-PP readiness.

TABLE 4.1: Results of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sample adequacy and Bartlett's test of sphericity

KMO and Bartlett's test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		0.820
	Chi-square	1245.755
	Degrees of freedom	351
Bartlett test of sphericity	p-value	0.000

4.4.1.2 Factor analysis results

The factor analysis results performed on the sampled population (n=113), as depicted in **Table 4.2**, show that only eight items had Eigenvalues greater than 1. **Table 4.2** also presents the proportion of variance accounted for by each of the items and the total variation accounted for by the eight factors. The eight retained factors accounted for about 67% of the total variation for the questionnaire.

TABLE 4.2: Eigenvalues, Proportion of variance and Cumulative variance explained by each item

Factor	Eigenvalue	Difference	Proportion	Cumulative
Factor 1	8.066	5.906	0.299	0.299
Factor 2	2.160	0.585	0.080	0.379
Factor 3	1.574	0.116	0.058	0.437
Factor 4	1.458	0.037	0.054	0.491
Factor 5	1.421	0.070	0.053	0.544
Factor 6	1.351	0.220	0.050	0.594
Factor 7	1.130	0.114	0.042	0.636
Factor 8	1.016	0.123	0.038	0.673
Factor 9	0.893	0.112	0.033	0.706
Factor 10	0.780	0.035	0.029	0.735
Factor 11	0.745	0.047	0.028	0.763
Factor 12	0.698	0.044	0.026	0.789
Factor 13	0.654	0.068	0.024	0.813
Factor 14	0.586	0.013	0.022	0.835
Factor 15	0.573	0.085	0.021	0.856
Factor 16	0.488	0.030	0.018	0.874
Factor 17	0.457	0.028	0.017	0.891
Factor 18	0.430	0.059	0.016	0.907
Factor 19	0.371	0.016	0.014	0.920
Factor 20	0.355	0.019	0.013	0.934
Factor 21	0.336	0.020	0.012	0.946
Factor 22	0.316	0.016	0.012	0.958
Factor 23	0.300	0.035	0.011	0.969
Factor 24	0.265	0.021	0.010	0.979
Factor 25	0.244	0.058	0.009	0.988
Factor 26	0.186	0.035	0.007	0.994

Factor 27	0.151	0.000	0.006	1.000
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LR test: independent vs. saturated: $\chi^2(351) = 1257.95$ Prob > $\chi^2 = 0.0000$

Table 4.3 provides the variance of the eight factors that were retained based on factor analysis results. According to **Table 4.3**, factor 1 (technological environment) explained the total variance of 13.7%, factor 2 (legal environment) accounted for 9.7% and factor 3 (economic environment) accounted for 8.8%. Factor 4, 5 and 6 (operating environment, organisational environment, and procurement policy and structure) explained the total variance of 8.2%, 7.3% and 6.9%, respectively. The variance for factor 7 (IT system integration) is 6.5% and 6.3% is the variance for factor 8 (procurement structure).

TABLE 4.3: Total variance explained by the extraction of 8 factors

Factor	Variance	Difference	Proportion	Cumulative
Factor 1	3.699	1.078	0.137	0.137
Factor 2	2.621	0.246	0.097	0.234
Factor 3	2.375	0.155	0.088	0.322
Factor 4	2.220	0.263	0.082	0.404
Factor 5	1.956	0.107	0.073	0.477
Factor 6	1.850	0.099	0.069	0.545
Factor 7	1.751	0.046	0.065	0.610
Factor 8	1.705	0.000	0.063	0.673

LR test: independent vs. saturated: $\chi^2(351) = 1257.95$ Prob > $\chi^2 = 0.0000$

Table 4.4 provides the orthogonal rotation of the solution for the eight retained factors where loadings smaller than 0.40 were omitted, as recommended by both Pituch and

Stevens (2016:354) and Field (2018:1023). This is because a lower loading item indicates that it might not be an effective measure of its factor, and should therefore be removed from the factor (Fabrigar & Wegener, 2012:26; Field, 2018:1023). The factor loadings analysis for each of the variables was performed to establish a relationship between an item and its corresponding factor.

The principal component factor analysis using the Varimax rotation of the 27 Likert scale questions (from V9 to V35) was carried out on the Part B of the questionnaire. The results in **Table 4.4** reveal that only one item loads high on factor 8 (V10), while factor 7 only has two items loading high on it (V34 and V35).

TABLE 4.4: Eight rotated factor (fac) loadings (pattern matrix) and unique variance

Variable	Fac1	Fac2	Fac3	Fac4	Fac5	Fac6	Fac7	Fac8	Uniqueness
Part B: Q1.1						0.477		0.436	0.251
Part B: Q1.2								0.834	0.232
Part B: Q1.3					0.736				0.244
Part B: Q1.4					0.741				0.330
Part B: Q2.1		0.724							0.349
Part B: Q2.2		0.437		0.478					0.439
Part B: Q2.3		0.831							0.218
Part B: Q2.4		0.587							0.444
Part B: Q2.5		0.549	0.403						0.430
Part B: Q3.1									0.440
Part B: Q3.2			0.513						0.492
Part B: Q3.3			0.610				0.427		0.403
Part B: Q3.4			0.832						0.270
Part B: Q4.1				0.846					0.237

Part B: Q4.2	0.528			0.318
Part B: Q4.3		0.555	0.405	0.296
Part B: Q4.4			0.756	0.253
Part B: Q4.5	0.415			0.462
Part B: Q4.6		0.474	0.576	0.323
Part B: Q5.1	0.509			0.337
Part B: Q5.2	0.608			0.373
Part B: Q5.3	0.739			0.269
Part B: Q5.4	0.814			0.275
Part B: Q5.5	0.713			0.305
Part B: Q5.6	0.639		0.463	0.216
Part B: Q5.7			0.774	0.249
Part B: Q5.8			0.433 0.434	0.371

(Blanks represent abs (loading)<.4)

Because of the results in **Table 4.4**, the factor analysis was revised, restricting the number of factors to six. **Table 4.5** shows that when six factors are retained, they account for 59% of the total variation for the questionnaire.

The rotated factor analysis solution, as seen in **Table 4.5**, indicates that seven (7) items (V26, V28, V29, V30, V31, V32 & V33) loaded high on factor 1, all of which relate to technology. Therefore, the name of the factor was retained as it is. Factor 2 held and loaded high on all of its five items (V13, V14, V15, V16 & V17), suggesting that these items fell under one (1) theme, the legal framework. Therefore, the name of the factor was also retained. The table also indicates that three items (V19, V20 & V21) loaded high on factor 3. All these three items come under one theme and all contribute to finance. Five items (V11, V12, V18, V27 & V35) loaded high into factor 4 and were grouped into a procurement structure theme. Factor 5 loaded up to 4 items (V22, V23, V24, V25 &

V26) and all relate to leadership as they measured the same theme and its name was retained. The remaining 2 items (V9 & V10) loaded high into factor 6. Both items paired together to form a subtheme that can be named procurement policy, which emanated from the operating environment (factor 5).

TABLE 4.5: Six rotated factor loadings (pattern matrix) and unique variances

Variable	Technol ogy	Legal	Finance	Procure structure	Leaders hip	Procure policy	Unique ness
Part B: Q1.1						0.711	0.349
Part B: Q1.2				0.406		0.529	0.405
Part B: Q1.3				0.717			0.248
Part B: Q1.4				0.589			0.539
Part B: Q2.1		0.747					0.365
Part B: Q2.2		0.494			0.449		0.465
Part B: Q2.3		0.781					0.275
Part B: Q2.4		0.616					0.497
Part B: Q2.5		0.509	0.494				0.443
Part B: Q3.1				0.434			0.501
Part B: Q3.2			0.568				0.497
Part B: Q3.3			0.703				0.454
Part B: Q3.4			0.739				0.394
Part B: Q4.1					0.800		0.289
Part B: Q4.2					0.455		0.530
Part B: Q4.3					0.615		0.326
Part B: Q4.4					0.468	-0.470	0.335
Part B: Q4.5	0.440						0.475
Part B: Q4.6				0.684			0.336
Part B: Q5.1	0.581		0.438				0.390
Part B: Q5.2	0.638						0.426
Part B: Q5.3	0.708						0.406

Part B: Q5.4	0.808		0.298
Part B: Q5.5	0.742		0.341
Part B: Q5.6	0.679		0.380
Part B: Q5.7			0.526
Part B: Q5.8	0.428	0.457	0.483

(Blanks represent abs (loading)<.4)

The principal component factor analysis using the Varimax rotation of the 12 Likert scale questions (from V36 to V47) was carried out on the Part C of the questionnaire. The results of this analysis, as depicted in **Table 4.6**, show that only three factors were retained (V36, V37 & V38) as their Eigenvalues are above 1, and the dropped items due to lower loadings were attached to variable V39 to V47. The retained three factors accounted for about 64% of the total variation for the questionnaire.

TABLE 4.6: Factor analysis with Varimax rotation

Factor	Eigenvalue	Difference	Proportion	Cumulative
Factor 1	4.960	3.504	0.413	0.413
Factor 2	1.456	0.162	0.121	0.535
Factor 3	1.294	0.466	0.108	0.643
Factor 4	0.828	0.184	0.069	0.712
Factor 5	0.644	0.028	0.054	0.765
Factor 6	0.617	0.056	0.051	0.817
Factor 7	0.560	0.120	0.047	0.863
Factor 8	0.441	0.066	0.037	0.900
Factor 9	0.375	0.059	0.031	0.931
Factor 10	0.316	0.012	0.026	0.958
Factor 11	0.305	0.101	0.025	0.983
Factor 12	0.204	0.000	0.017	1.000

LR test: independent vs. saturated: $\chi^2(66) = 561.03$ Prob > $\chi^2 = 0.0000$

Table 4.7 presents the total variance explained by the extraction of three factors. The total variance of 21.7% was explained by factor 1, while 21.4% and 21.2% were accounted for factor 2 and factor 3, respectively.

TABLE 4.7: Total variance explained by the extraction of 3 factors

Factor	Variance	Difference	Proportion	Cumulative
Factor 1	2.599	0.031	0.217	0.217
Factor 2	2.569	0.026	0.214	0.431
Factor 3	2.543	0.000	0.212	0.643

LR test: independent vs. saturated: $\chi^2(66) = 561.03$ Prob > $\chi^2 = 0.0000$

Table 4.8 shows the pattern matrix of twelve rotated loadings. The results of the orthogonal rotation solution on e-PP readiness challenges in South Africa, as seen in **Table 4.8**, show that four items (V37, V38, V39 & V41) loaded high on Factor 1, all of which relate to the staff enthusiasm theme. The table also shows that four items (V40, V42, V43 & V44) loaded high into Factor 2, forming the high cost of e-PP system theme. The remaining four items (V36, V45, V46 & V47) loaded high into Factor 3 and were assigned to the theme of proper procurement legislation.

TABLE 4.8: Twelve rotated factor loadings (pattern matrix) and unique variances

Variable	Lack of staff enthusiasm	High cost of e-PP system	Lack of proper procurement legislation	Uniqueness
Part C: Q1.1	0.502		0.525	0.465
Part C: Q1.2	0.696		0.452	0.303
Part C: Q1.3	0.797			0.293
Part C: Q1.4	0.810			0.280
Part C: Q1.5		0.643		0.491
Part C: Q1.6	0.493	0.476		0.527
Part C: Q1.7		0.839		0.267
Part C: Q1.8		0.725		0.279
Part C: Q1.9		0.653	0.422	0.376
Part C: Q1.10			0.749	0.326
Part C: Q1.11			0.805	0.305
Part C: Q1.12			0.722	0.377

(Blanks represent loading less than .40)

4.4.1.3 Discussions of factor analysis results

The principal component factor analysis using the Varimax rotation was carried out on the Part B and Part C of the questionnaire. The rotated factor analysis results on Part B of the questionnaire in **Table 4.5** show six factors that influenced e-PP readiness in South African government departments. These were technology, legal framework, organisation's finance, procurement structure, organisation's leadership and procurement policy.

Factor 1: Technology

The technology of government departments is the most critical factor affecting e-PP readiness, with incompatibilities in the IT system (both hardware and software) acting as a barrier to e-PP success. To ensure successful e-PP adoption, government departments in South Africa need to use compatible IT systems and have the necessary supporting software infrastructure to enable government departments to streamline their procurement processes. Such an e-PP readiness effort would allow for reliable and accessible network connectivity for both urban and remote developed areas of South Africa. This is consistent with Mpehle and Mudogwa (2020:3) who state that user e-PP experience heavily depends on the availability, nature and capacity of the existing network infrastructure (e.g., broad-band coverage). In addition, successful e-PP adoption requires ICT skills training programmes for government procurement officials to be adequately equipped to deal with current IT technology. Consistent with this view, Kusi *et al.* (2016:649) warn that staff who lack ICT skills might display anxiety, a negative attitude and resistance against the use of e-PP system.

Factor 2: Legal framework

Legal framework is another important factor that influences e-PP readiness in South African government departments. The framework is not yet capacitated to allow for full use of e-PP as South Africa's public procurement legislation does not specifically include e-PP (Mpehle & Mudogwa, 2020:5). In addition, circulars and instruction notes serve as legal basis for a dual public procurement system (paper-based with some electronic features). It is therefore vital that a specific legislation governing e-PP in South Africa be

developed to ensure legal certainty and to provide a consolidated piece of law that addresses the unique demands of an end-to-end e-PP system. This view is consistent with Orina (2013:37) who found that the Kenyan public sector needed a proper legal and regulatory framework to support an end-to-end e-PP system. Furthermore, recent developments in South Africa's public procurement system stress that the entire regulatory framework of public procurement be redrafted by means of a new Public Procurement Bill, with the goal of simplifying the confusing and fragmented regulations that currently govern public procurement processes. Such an undertaking is a crucial step towards successful e-PP readiness in South Africa.

Factor 3: Organisation's finance

Investment costs of e-PP system is an important factor for e-PP readiness. Given that South Africa presently uses partial e-PP, establishing an end-to-end e-PP system will need a substantial financial investment (Kramer, 2016:24). As a result, the South African government should commit considerable financial resources for the effective implementation of the e-PP system. Proper planning for capacity development of staff to operate the e-PP system and train suppliers plays a crucial role in ensuring a positive e-PP experience. The implementation of such an undertaking would incur short-term or long-term hidden costs such as maintenance and support costs, modernisation and upgrade costs, which may be higher if they are not managed effectively (Huai, 2012:1161). Therefore, government departments need to put in place a mechanism that monitors and minimises short-term and long-term hidden costs relative to e-PP implementation.

Factor 4: Procurement structure

The procurement structure was identified as another critical factor that affects e-PP readiness. In South Africa, there is currently a lack of a single or integrated procurement system used by government departments. National Treasury (2015:3) attributes this issue to challenges in the legal environment and legacy systems challenges. To establish an efficient e-PP system, the fragmentation of the public procurement system should be addressed. This means that there is a need for a full e-PP overhaul in order to reform public procurement in the light of developing technological potential and to increase the efficiency of public procurement processes. This initiative would allow the government to get value for money, streamline procurement processes and deliver better services to the citizens of the country.

Factor 5: Leadership

Adequate leadership support is needed in order to be ready for successful e-PP adoption. Several findings have all suggested that government departments that lack leadership to steer them toward e-PP readiness are likely to affect the entire public sector and cripple e-PP readiness efforts (Koech, Ayoyi & Mugambi, 2016:22; Anthony, 2018:43). To avoid such danger, leadership in government departments needs to motivate and stimulate public procurement officials to develop a positive attitude towards the adoption of e-PP systems. This would minimise staff resistance and sabotage of the implementation of the e-PP system in government departments.

Factor 6: Procurement policy

An organisation's procurement policy on e-PP is another critical factor for successful e-PP readiness. In various countries, a lack of public policy on e-PP was highlighted as a barrier to e-PP readiness (Australian Government Information Office, 2005; Doherty, McConnell & Ellis-Chadwick, 2013). E-PP is not one of the competing priorities of a government department. This is why e-PP has been successful in governments where it had been prioritised, as well as where policy reforms had been clearly outlined and implemented. The public procurement system in South Africa is highly decentralised and fragmented, and does not specifically include e-PP. To overcome these issues, the legal framework needs to be amended to allow for centralisation of procurement processes in the public sector and to increase public procurement systems efficiency.

The rotated factor analysis results on Part C of the questionnaire in **Table 4.8** show three factors that influenced e-PP readiness challenges. This included lack of staff enthusiasm, high cost of a e-PP system and lack of proper procurement legislation.

Factor 1: Lack of staff enthusiasm

Staff enthusiasm plays a critical role in e-PP readiness as enthusiasm can make staff willing to adopt e-PP system. However, the lack of staff enthusiasm makes e-PP adoption a difficult task. This study found that the majority of public procurement officials were not enthusiastic about e-PP adoption (see **Figure 4.39**). This finding is confirmed by Orina's (2013) study in Kenyan government departments. To overcome this barrier to e-PP adoption, government departments need to educate and train public procurement officials

on the roles, benefits and capacities of the e-PP system (Orina, 2013:38; Sithole, 2017:167; Rukuni, Maziriri & Mulaudzi, 2020:18). They also need to find ways and strategies that motivate and stimulate public procurement officials to embrace the implementation of new procurement systems. Some of the ways may include rewarding training participation and awarding of training certificates.

Factor 2: High cost of e-PP system

This study finding shows that the majority respondents strongly agreed and agreed that the high cost of acquiring and of running e-PP system was another challenge in e-PP adoption (see **Figure 4.42** and **Figure 4.43**). Consistent with this finding, Kramer (2016:24) points out that the use of a certified e-PP system requires significant financial investment and involves high costs related to its usage. In support of this view, Huai (2012:1161) explains that short-term or long-term hidden costs (e.g., maintenance and support, modernisation and upgrade) are important elements of cost structure related to the use of an e-PP system. These costs may be higher when it is not managed properly. Therefore, government departments need to assess the cost factors relative to e-PP adoption and find cost reduction strategies to adopt in the implementation phase of the e-PP system.

Factor 3: Lack of proper procurement legislation

Procurement legislation is an important tool that guides procurement practices in organisations. This study found that the majority of public procurement officials opine that the current procurement legislation is another challenge to e-PP adoption in South Africa

(see **Figure 4.46**), which means that there is lack of proper procurement legislation. This implies that South Africa's government departments are unready to tap into the full benefits of e-PP adoption. The finding is consistent with several findings (National Treasury, 2015; Manyathi, 2019:208) that indicate multiple, inconsistent and cumbersome pieces of public procurement legislation. To overcome this challenge, there is a need for comprehensive and consolidated legislation for public procurement. Such a tool would streamline procurement practices in the public sector and aid to deliver better services to citizens.

4.4.2 Reliability analysis

The purpose of assessing the measurement model is to determine the validity and reliability of the manifest variables. Internal consistency assessments are carried out by way of individual manifest evaluations to set up the reliability tests. The Cronbach alpha test for internal consistency was performed to test the suitability of questionnaire items.

4.4.2.1 Internal consistency: Part B of questionnaire

The results of the internal consistency of Part B: Q4.5; Q5.1 - Q5.6 are shown in **Table 4.9**. **Table 4.9** shows an adequate Cronbach alpha for the items of Part B of the questionnaire for Q4.5 and Q5.1 to Q5.6, as individual items resulted in an acceptable overall reliability of 0.856, which is above the recommended 0.70 cut-off point.

TABLE 4.9: Internal consistency of Part B: Q4.5; Q5.1 - Q5.6

Item	Observed	Sign	Item-test correlation	Item-rest correlation	average interitem covariance	Cronbach's alpha
Part B: Q4.5	113	+	0.663	0.540	0.821	0.847
Part B: Q5.1	113	+	0.742	0.622	0.751	0.836
Part B: Q5.2	113	+	0.747	0.635	0.757	0.833
Part B: Q5.3	113	+	0.689	0.564	0.797	0.844
Part B: Q5.4	113	+	0.800	0.709	0.733	0.823
Part B: Q5.5	113	+	0.767	0.667	0.753	0.829
Part B: Q5.6	113	+	0.715	0.602	0.788	0.838
Test scale					0.771	0.856

Table 4.10 reveals that the Cronbach alpha for items of Part B of the questionnaire from Q2.1 to Q2.5 is 0.759. This Cronbach alpha value is above the cut-off point and the internal reliability of these items was therefore acceptable.

TABLE 4.10: Internal consistency of Part B: Q2.1 - Q2.5

Item	Observed	Sign	Item-test correlation	Item-rest correlation	average interitem covariance	Cronbach's alpha
Part B: Q2.1	113	+	0.766	0.583	0.541	0.694
Part B: Q2.2	113	+	0.663	0.450	0.649	0.743
Part B: Q2.3	113	+	0.761	0.599	0.563	0.690
Part B: Q2.4	113	+	0.694	0.522	0.637	0.718
Part B: Q2.5	113	+	0.687	0.487	0.628	0.730
Test scale					0.603	0.759

The results of internal consistency test in **Table 4.11** show that the Cronbach alpha for Part B of the questionnaire for Q3.2 to Q3.4 is 0.653, suggesting a weak correlation as

the Cronbach alpha value is below the 0.7 cut-off mark. This weak correlation may be attributed to the small number of items on these questions.

TABLE 4.21: Internal consistency of Part B: Q3.2 - Q3.4

Item	Observed	Sign	Item-test correlation	Item-rest correlation	average interitem covariance	Cronbach's alpha
Part B: Q3.2	113	+	0.765	0.423	0.542	0.617
Part B: Q3.3	113	+	0.778	0.500	0.465	0.508
Part B: Q3.4	113	+	0.765	0.471	0.505	0.546
Test scale					0.504	0.653

The results of the internal consistency test, as seen in **Table 4.12**, show Cronbach's alpha of 0.725 for the items of Part B of the questionnaire for Q1.3, Q1.4, Q3.1, Q4.6 and Q5.8.

The internal reliability of these items was acceptable.

TABLE 4.32: Internal consistency of Part B: Q1.3 - Q1.4; Q3.1; Q4.6; Q5.8

Item	Observed	Sign	Item-test correlation	Item-rest correlation	Average interitem covariance	Cronbach's alpha
Part B: Q1.3	113	+	0.725	0.515	0.518	0.666
Part B: Q1.4	113	+	0.694	0.481	0.552	0.679
Part B: Q3.1	113	+	0.683	0.477	0.565	0.681
Part B: Q4.6	113	+	0.721	0.524	0.527	0.662
Part B: Q5.8	113	+	0.624	0.425	0.628	0.700
Test scale					0.558	0.725

Table 4.13 shows that the Cronbach alpha for Part B items of the questionnaire for Q4.1 to Q4.4 is 0.707. This Cronbach alpha value points out that there was an acceptable internal consistency between the items.

TABLE 4.43: Internal consistency of Part B: Q4.1 - Q4.4

Item	Observed	Sign	Item-test correlation	Item-rest correlation	Average interitem covariance	Cronbach's alpha
Part B: Q4.1	113	+	0.696	0.445	0.586	0.673
Part B: Q4.2	113	+	0.700	0.432	0.580	0.683
Part B: Q4.3	113	+	0.815	0.633	0.421	0.555
Part B: Q4.4	113	+	0.710	0.473	0.567	0.656
Test scale					0.538	0.707

4.4.2.2 Internal consistency: Part C of questionnaire

Table 4.14 indicates that the Cronbach alpha for Part C items of the questionnaire for Q1.2 to Q1.4 and Q1.6 is 0.769. The internal reliability of these items was acceptable.

TABLE 4.54: Internal consistency of Part C: Q1.2 - Q4.4; Q1.6

Item	Observed	Sign	Item-test correlation	Item-rest correlation	Average interitem covariance	Cronbach's alpha
Part C: Q1.2	113	+	0.742	0.528	0.687	0.736
Part C: Q1.3	113	+	0.836	0.680	0.550	0.653
Part C: Q1.4	113	+	0.827	0.667	0.564	0.661
Part C: Q1.6	113	+	0.671	0.420	0.791	0.790
Test scale					0.648	0.769

The results of internal consistency test, as seen in **Table 4.15**, display a Cronbach alpha of 0.792 for Part C items of the questionnaire for Q1.5 and Q1.7 to Q1.9. This means that the internal reliability of these items was adequate.

TABLE 4.65: Internal consistency of Part C: Q1.5; Q1.7 – Q1.9

Item	Observed	Sign	Item-test correlation	Item-rest correlation	Average interitem covariance	Cronbach's alpha
Part C: Q1.5	113	+	0.685	0.489	0.889	0.792
Part C: Q1.7	113	+	0.841	0.683	0.615	0.698
Part C: Q1.8	113	+	0.856	0.714	0.598	0.681
Part C: Q1.9	113	+	0.750	0.536	0.765	0.775
Test scale					0.717	0.792

Table 4.16 shows that the Cronbach alpha for Part C items of the questionnaire for Q1.1 and Q1.10 to Q1.12. These items resulted in an acceptable overall reliability of 0.784.

TABLE 4.76: Internal consistency of Part C: Q1.1; Q1.11 – Q1.12

Item	Observed	Sign	Item-test correlation	Item-rest correlation	average interitem covariance	Cronbach's alpha
Part C: Q1.1	113	+	0.716	0.490	0.817	0.782
Part C: Q1.10	113	+	0.817	0.660	0.668	0.697
Part C: Q1.11	113	+	0.795	0.614	0.693	0.719
Part C: Q1.12	113	+	0.790	0.605	0.700	0.724
Test scale					0.720	0.784

4.5 INFERENCEAL STATISTICS

This section presents and discusses the results of inferential statistics. A Chi-square test was used to assess the relationship between readiness challenges and e-PP adoption, and a Kruskal-Wallis test was also used to determine the relationship between years of service in the public sector procurement/SCM and readiness challenges to e-PP adoption.

4.5.1 Chi-square test

An independent Chi-square test was carried out to test the relationship between the perception of e-PP adoption challenges and its adoption. The Chi-square test of independence determines whether two variables are likely to be related and whether a significant proportion of a population prefers one response over another (Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2018:789; Bairagi & Munot, 2019:175). Section 4.5.1.1 presents the results of the Chi-square test.

4.5.1.1 Relationships between readiness challenges and e-PP adoption

Table 4.17 presents the results of the Chi-square test on the relationships between readiness challenges and e-PP adoption. These results include the relationships between:

- Resistance to change and e-PP adoption;

- Poor staff skills and e-PP adoption;
- Lack of transparency and e-PP adoption;
- Lack of staff enthusiasm and e-PP adoption;
- Competition from other departments and e-PP adoption;
- Corruption in the procurement process and e-PP adoption;
- High cost of acquiring the e-PP system and e-PP adoption;
- Perceived high cost of running the e-PP system and e-PP adoption;
- Fragmentation of operating systems and e-PP adoption;
- Influence of procurement policies and e-PP adoption;
- Proper procurement legislation and e-PP adoption;
- Perception on loss of confidential information and e-PP adoption.

The results of the Chi-square test, as seen in **Table 4.17** below, indicate that resistance to change has a meaningful effect on the adoption of e-PP ($p < 0.05$). It is also shown that 82.86% of respondents who agreed that reluctance to change is a readiness challenge to e-PP adoption, suggested that they would recommend the shifting from the current paper-based procurement system to e-PP compared to 92.59% of those who disagreed and 50.00% of those who were neutral. The results show that employees who considered resistance to change as a challenge to e-PP adoption were less likely to recommend its adoption compared to those who did not regard it as a challenge and those who were neutral. The findings concur with those of Sithole (2017:218) that indicate resistance to change as one of the barriers to e-procurement adoption in South African small and medium construction firms. In the South African public sector, Nokele and Mukonza

(2021:113) investigated the adoption of e-Government in the Department of Home Affairs and found that resistance to technology was a barrier to e-Government adoption. They recommended that the Department launch an internal awareness campaign about the e-government paradigm (online applications and communications) in the Department. Employee resistance to technology was identified as a barrier to realising the full potential of e-PP in the Lesotho public sector by Kabanda, Pitso, and Kapepo (2019:242) while researching the role of institutional forces in the adoption of e-PP.

A significant relationship was found between the high cost of acquiring the e-PP system and e-PP adoption ($p < 0.05$), as exhibited in **Table 4.17**. The table also shows that 87.50% of respondents who agreed that the high cost of acquiring the e-PP system is a challenge to the adoption of the e-PP system, suggested that they would recommend the adoption of the e-PP system compared to 76.47% of those who disagreed and 62.50% of those were neutral. This also suggests that public procurement officials who perceived high cost of acquiring the e-PP system as a challenge to e-PP readiness and adoption and those who were neutral were less likely to recommend its adoption than those who did not see it as a challenge. These findings are consistent with the findings of Davids (2019:67), who examined the role of electronic healthcare systems (e-Government system) in the Western Cape and found that the cost of acquiring new technology such as the Open Medical Record System (OpenMRS) in the healthcare sector is high.

Several studies suggested various avenues to addressing high acquisition cost for an e-PP system. For instance, Malemela (2018:36) examined perceptions of City of Tshwane

residents on the electronic petition system. The study found that Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) provide a feasible model for financing e-Government through building channel infrastructure and national network connectivity. Rukuni *et al.* (2020:18) assessed e-PP at a South African state-owned enterprise (SOE) and discovered that SOEs may seek low-cost suppliers to acquire e-PP software at a lower cost. The Department of Telecommunication and Postal Services (DTPS, 2017:35) suggested a scale and scope of interventions to be performed for South Africa to fulfil its e-Government objectives in the national e-Government strategy and roadmap. According to the e-Government strategy, the introduction of PPP would be a way for financing e-Government activities.

Table 4.17 shows that the perceived high cost of running the e-PP system has a significant relationship with e-PP adoption ($p=0.001$). The table also shows that 88.31% of respondents who agreed that the perceived high cost of running the e-PP system is a challenge to e-PP adoption suggested that they would recommend the shifting from the current paper-based procurement system to e-PP, compared to 81.25% of those who disagreed and 50.00% of those who were unsure (neutral). The findings suggest that public procurement officials who perceived the high cost of running the e-PP system as a challenge to its adoption and those who were neutral were less likely to recommend it than those who did not perceive it as a challenge. This finding is supported by Lobong and Keji's (2020:85) study on factors influencing e-PP implementation in South Sudan, which revealed that government departments should be aware of the high potential hidden costs (such as system integration, supplier enablement, and procurement process

reengineering) associated with the implementation of e-PP systems. This means that in order to understand the likely consequences of e-PP adoption, the cost elements (including hidden costs) incurred before, during and after e-PP adoption must be assessed and documented.

According to **Table 4.17**, a significant relationship was found between fragmentation of operating systems and e-PP adoption ($p=0.001$). Similarly, 90.67% of respondents agreed that fragmentation of operating systems within government departments is a readiness challenge in e-PP system adoption, compared to 77.78% of those who disagreed and 55.17% of those who decided not to indicate their position on the matter. These findings altogether are consistent with those of **Figure 4.44** that show almost three-fifths (66.37%, $n=75$) of public procurement officials agreed and strongly agreed that the fragmentation of operating systems within government departments poses a readiness challenge to the adoption of the e-PP system, compared to 7.96% ($n=9$) of the respondents who disagreed and strongly disagreed with the assertion. The findings of Rukuni *et al.*'s (2020:19) study, when examining e-PP at a South African state-owned enterprise, revealed similar results, showing incompatibility of e-PP software with current procurement processes as one of the barriers to e-PP adoption. Sithole's (2017:169) research on e-PP implementation in the Gauteng Department of Infrastructure Development revealed that there is no integrated e-PP system in the department and that the systems in use are fragmented (with no relationship to each other).

Table 4.17 further shows that there was no significant relationship between poor staff skills and e-PP adoption ($p=0.175$). The proportion of public procurement officials who would recommend e-PP, even though they regarded poor staff skills as a readiness challenge to e-PP adoption, does not differ significantly from that of those who would recommend it even though they do not regard poor staff skills as readiness challenge to e-PP adoption, as well as those who were neutral. As there is no relationship between poor staff skills and e-PP adoption, this finding is consistent with that of Ibem and Laryea (2015:378), who discovered that poor skills are attributable to a lack of adequate training and competence on e-procurement systems and applications. Furthermore, they found that the present level of expertise on e-procurement in South Africa is a major impediment to the adoption of e-procurement in the construction sector.

In his study on the use of an electronic system (e-Government) for agency nurse staffing in public hospitals in the Western Cape, Van As (2018:176) discovered that nurses have basic computer literacy knowledge and skills, which are primarily self-taught, and that in order to have a successful adoption of an electronic information management system, he advised professional nurses to receive training on the use of the e-Government system. This would help in ensuring the competency of the system and professional nurses. Makau (2018:50) studied factors influencing the adoption of e-procurement in the hotel sector and also recommended that further training programmes be presented to ensure that all procurement officials have the requisite knowledge and abilities to adopt e-PP.

Lack of transparency and e-PP adoption were not significantly associated ($p=0.079$), as shown in **Table 4.17**. This finding seems to contract that of Svidronova and Mikus (2015:320) that suggests that e-procurement may be a feasible solution to the lack of transparency and related issues in public sector. This is consistent with the results of Habiburrochman and Fatimah (2020:1003), who investigated the effects of asymmetric information on e-procurement adoption at public universities and found that transparency has a positive and significant effect on the intention to adopt e-procurement. Kusi (2014:59) examined the current literature on existing models and frameworks for the adoption of an e-PP system in Ghana's healthcare sector and advised public hospitals to adopt e-PP since manual procurement is unsustainable due to a lack of transparency.

Table 4.17 shows that lack of enthusiasm and e-PP adoption were not significantly related ($p=0.341$). This finding is inconsistent with several studies. For instance, Transparency International (2021:2) links a lack of enthusiasm and e-PP adoption to South Africa's high level of corruption. A study by Altayyar (2017:211) on e-procurement barriers in Saudi Arabian SMEs found that enthusiasm to embrace technology leads to a positive attitude and perspective on the impact of e-procurement on the future performance of a company. Mohungoo, Brown, and Kabanda (2020:46) conducted a comprehensive analysis of e-PP implementation challenges and their findings suggest that Sub-Saharan African nations with low corruption perception index scores have showed enthusiasm and interest in adopting e-PP.

According to **Table 4.17**, there is no statistically significant association between competition from other departments and e-PP adoption ($p=0.255$). This indicates that public procurement officials' perceptions of competition from other departments have no influence on e-PP adoption. This is supported by the respondents (85%; $n=40$) who disagreed or strongly disagreed in Orina's (2013:26) investigation of e-PP readiness aspects in Kenya's public sector that competition from competitors is a challenge to e-PP readiness.

Table 4.17 shows that corruption in the procurement process and e-PP adoption were not significantly related ($p=0.762$). This finding is disputed by the finding of a similar study by Mpehle and Mudogwa (2020:8) that examined the use of CSD in Limpopo provincial departments and demonstrated that the adoption of CSD constituted a substantial step toward decreasing procurement waste and corruption. Consistent with this view, Duma (2018:28) stresses the need for tightening the procurement system as a result of the losses generated by corruption in all sectors of government, and states that e-PP adoption will enhance procurement uniformity, reducing corruption in government procurement processes.

The influence of procurement policies and e-PP adoption were found not to be significantly associated ($p=0.085$). However, Chen, Bretschneider, Stritch, Darnall, and Hsueh (2021:15) documented the relationship between the influence of procurement policies and e-PP adoption, indicating that government departments are more likely to use an e-PP system to navigate complex procurement policies. Because ICTs increase

the government's ability for information seeking and processing, the findings suggest that ICTs may be a viable alternative for resolving the conflict between competing procurement policies (Chen *et al.*, 2021:2). In order to improve compliance with procurement processes, Zitha *et al.* (2016:72) proposed developing procurement policies by including all authorities who would be essential in e-PP adoption.

The results of **Table 4.17** exhibits that proper procurement legislation had no a significant relationship with e-PP adoption ($p=0.165$). This finding contradicts the national e-Government strategy and roadmap that indicated a lack of legislation to facilitate digitisation of e-Government services (DTPS, 2017:22). The delay in adopting comprehensive e-PP legislation might be attributed to the fact that there are now a number of role players in the South African government who have a legal mandate to manage, enable, create or execute e-Government. Existing procurement laws and regulations must be examined to see if they can handle the challenges that have arisen as a result of the new ICT period (Oyediran & Atintola, 2011:573; Manyathi, 2019:208). According to the national e-Government strategy and roadmap, the procurement policy environment and legislative framework should be harmonised to allow digital transformation (DTPS, 2017:22).

Perception on loss of confidential information and e-PP adoption were found not to be associated, as exhibited in **Table 4.17** ($p=0.344$). In their study on cloud computing (e-Government) for large enterprises in South Africa, Bakasa and Pekane (2021:259) discovered that security is one of the main factors considered when selecting a service

provider. Iben and Laryea (2015:378) urge that e-procurement system adopters be aware of current security applications and techniques that seek to protect the safety, security and integrity of e-procurement transactions. Their findings further indicated that the majority of the security problems identified were linked to the confidentiality of data during transmission (Iben & Laryea, 2015:376). Based on the above, the researcher advocates for awareness campaigns and training to enhance understanding of e-PP for stakeholders (government departments and suppliers) to be e-PP ready.

TABLE 4.87: Relationships between readiness challenges and e-PP adoption

Item Variables		Yes		No		Do not know		Chi ²	Pr
		Freq	Perc	Freq	Perc	Freq	Perc		
Resistance to change	Agree	58	82.86	6	8.57	6	8.57	12.878	0.012*
	Disagree	8	92.59	1	3.70	1	3.70		
	Neutral	8	50.00	5	31.25	3	18.75		
Poor staff skills	Agree	47	82.46	4	7.02	6	10.53	6.341	0.175
	Disagree	32	86.49	4	10.41	1	2.70		
	Neutral	12	63.16	4	21.05	3	15.79		
Lack of transparency	Agree	49	87.50	4	7.14	3	5.36	8.370	0.079
	Disagree	29	82.86	3	8.57	3	8.57		
	Neutral	13	59.09	5	22.73	4	18.18		
Lack of staff enthusiasm	Agree	47	83.93	5	8.93	4	7.14	4.511	0.341
	Disagree	29	85.29	3	8.82	2	5.88		
	Neutral	15	65.22	4	17.39	4	17.39		
Competition from other departments	Agree	19	76.00	2	8.00	4	16.00	5.332	0.255
	Disagree	42	87.50	5	10.42	1	2.08		
	Neutral	30	75.00	5	12.50	5	12.50		
Corruption in the procurement process	Agree	44	84.62	4	7.69	4	7.69	1.859	0.762
	Disagree	24	80.00	4	13.33	2	6.67		
	Neutral	23	74.19	4	12.90	4	12.90		

High cost of acquiring the e-PP system	Agree	63	87.50	4	5.56	5	6.94	12.365	0.015*
	Disagree	13	76.47	4	23.53	0	0.00		
	Neutral	15	62.50	4	16.67	5	20.83		
Perceived high cost of running the e-PP system	Agree	68	88.31	4	5.19	5	6.49	17.713	0.001***
	Disagree	13	81.25	3	18.75	0	0.00		
	Neutral	10	50.00	5	25.00	5	25.00		
Fragmentation of operating systems	Agree	68	90.67	4	5.33	3	4.00	19.614	0.001***
	Disagree	7	77.78	2	22.22	0	0.00		
	Neutral	16	55.17	6	20.69	7	24.14		
Influence of procurement policies	Agree	60	85.71	7	10.00	3	4.29	8.190	0.085
	Disagree	13	81.25	2	12.50	1	6.25		
	Neutral	18	66.67	3	11.11	6	22.22		
Proper procurement legislation	Agree	59	86.76	5	7.35	4	5.88	6.490	0.165
	Disagree	14	77.78	3	16.67	1	5.56		
	Neutral	18	66.67	4	14.81	5	18.52		
Perception on loss of confidential information	Agree	49	84.48	4	6.90	5	8.62	4.487	0.344
	Disagree	23	79.31	5	17.24	1	3.45		
	Neutral	19	73.08	3	11.54	4	15.38		

*-p<0.05, **-p<0.01, ***-p<0.001

4.5.2 Kruskal-Wallis Test

A one-way ANOVA by rank test was used to assess the relationships between years of service in the public sector procurement/SCM role and perceptions of e-PP readiness challenges. The results of the Kruskal-Wallis test in **Table 4.18** reveal that the number of years working in the public sector procurement/SCM environment has no significant impact on resistance to change as a readiness challenge to the adoption of the e-PP system (p=0.247). This means that public procurement officials' perception of resistance to change as a readiness challenge to e-PP adoption did not differ on the basis of the

number of years in the public sector procurement/SCM environment. This finding is disputed by Van Dyk and Van Bell's (2019:6) study on influencing digital transformation adoption in South Africa, which found that most workers who had been with an organisation for a long time were accustomed to doing things in a specific way. This suggests that most public procurement officials with many years of working experience in the public sector are resistant to change. The findings of South Africa's national e-Government strategy and roadmap report point to ways to reduce the risk of change resistance by raising awareness among stakeholders, increasing accountability, and improving change management (DTPS, 2017:40). Resistance to change when adopting new systems is natural and affects all transformation initiatives (Sithole, 2017:148).

Table 4.18 shows that no significant relationship was found between the number of years working in the public sector procurement/SCM environment and poor staff skills as a readiness challenge to e-PP adoption ($p=0.271$). This demonstrates that public procurement officials' perceptions of poor staff skills as a readiness challenge to e-PP adoption did not change due to the number of years spent in the public sector procurement/SCM environment. This finding contradicts previous studies: Rowland and Adefuye's (2021:12) assessment on factors impacting human error and safety of patients in the pre-hospital emergency care setting found that a lack of skills and experience can contribute to errors during pre-hospital treatment. A skills gap in relation to e-PP readiness can occasionally come from a lack of experience, as suggested by the conclusions of the Public Service Sector Education and Training Authority (PSETA, 2017:18).

According to **Table 4.18** there was no significant association between transparency of staff as a readiness challenge to e-PP adoption and years of experience in the public sector procurement/SCM environment ($p=0.796$). This finding indicates that public procurement officials' perceptions of staff transparency as a barrier to e-PP adoption did not change based on the number of years spent in the public sector procurement/SCM environment. However, staff transparency is highlighted (in Section 4.3.3.3) as a readiness challenge to e-PP adoption, and this appears to be confirmed by Christopher's (2015:957) and Sibanda, Zindi, and Maramura's (2020:9) findings, which state that a lack of transparency measures increases the likelihood of public procurement officials to engage in acts of corruption. The transparency that comes with e-PP adoption has sparked opposition from public procurement officials, slowing e-PP readiness (Purchasing & Procurement Center 2017; Mpehle & Mudogwa, 2020:3).

As shown in **Table 4.18**, lack of staff enthusiasm was not significantly associated with the number of years working in the public sector procurement/SCM environment ($p=0.722$). This means that the perceptions of public procurement officials of lack of enthusiasm as a readiness challenge to adopt e-PP did not change based on the number of years spent in the public sector procurement/SCM environment. Mathole's (2017:139) findings in her study on the adoption of cellular telephones by youth in the City of Tshwane complement this finding by indicating that the young are enthusiastic about innovations and are also adaptable to changing technologies. The demographic profile of public procurement officials in this study (section 4.3.1) shows fewer youths than older people working in

public procurement, which may be one of the drivers for lack of enthusiasm. When comparing older and more experienced employees to younger and less experienced employees in the Western Cape healthcare system, Davids (2019:114) discovered that older and more experienced staff exhibited less enthusiasm for the adoption of a new technology and were less inclined to utilise it. This might be because younger workers are more at ease with technology than older workers.

Table 4.18 shows that competition from other departments was not significantly associated with the number of years working in the public sector procurement/SCM environment ($p=0.637$). This suggests that public procurement officials' views of competition from other departments as a readiness challenge to e-PP adoption were unaffected by the number of years spent in the public sector procurement/SCM environment. This result is consistent with and supported by Orina's (2013:26) findings, which found no connection between the two (competition and years in public sector). Her findings also revealed that government departments do not compete, leading her to conclude that competition among departments does not pose a readiness challenge for them to adopt e-PP.

Corruption in the procurement process and the number of years working in the public sector procurement/SCM environment were not significantly associated, as exhibited in **Table 4.18** ($p=0.330$). This implies that public procurement officials' perceptions of corruption in the procurement process as a readiness challenge to e-PP adoption did not change based on years of experience in the public sector procurement/SCM environment.

This study's finding backs the findings of a Corruption Watch's (2020:6) survey on young people's perceptions about corruption in South Africa, which revealed that 49% of respondents did not consider the act of offering a monetary reward in return for a tender to constitute corruption. This demonstrates that young people have a high level of knowledge and awareness of corruption.

Table 4.18 shows that the perceived high cost of running an e-PP system and the perceived high cost of acquiring an e-PP system were not significantly related to the number of years working in public sector procurement ($p=0.484$ and $p=0.702$, respectively). According to the findings, public procurement officials' perceptions of high acquisition and running costs as readiness challenges to e-PP adoption did not change based on the number of years in the public sector procurement/SCM environment. This result of the study confirms previous findings of Bwalya's (2018:181) study on e-Government contextual difficulties in Africa, indicating high cost of technology acquisition as one of the issues influencing e-Government adoption. Conversely, Khubone, Tlou, and Mashamba-Thompson (2020:5) discovered no significant relationship between perceived high costs of running an e-PP system and number of years working in public sector procurement. Their findings indicate that maintaining the health information system requires paying high running costs. This finding is therefore consistent with this study's finding.

Table 4.18 shows that the remaining four readiness challenges to e-PP adoption (fragmentation of operating systems within government departments, influence of

procurement policies, proper procurement legislation, and perception on loss of confidential information) also had no significant relationship with the number of years working in the public sector procurement/SCM environment ($p=0.260$, $p=0.637$, $p=0.694$, and $p=0.753$, respectively). This means that the views of public procurement officials on the four identified readiness challenges to e-PP adoption did not change based on the number of years in the public sector procurement/SCM environment. The study on public health system challenges in the Free State, South Africa by Malakoane, Heunis, Chikobvu, Kigozi, and Kruger (2020:12) found no link between fragmentation of operating systems within government departments and number of years working, but they did identify a lack of integration of services as a cause of poor health system performance due to fragmentation. This finding is consistent with the finding of this study, as indicated above. This finding also supports National Treasury's (2015:12) statement indicating that "system fragmentation makes SCM compliance difficult".

This study's finding on the relationship between procurement policy influence and procurement working experience, as above shown, contradict Fadina and Barjolle's (2018:10) study on farmers' adaptation strategies, which revealed a correlation between the most experienced farmers and their potential to change strategies. This suggests that public procurement officials with extensive experience in the procurement/SCM environment are more likely to influence procurement policies. This calls for a need to tighten the procurement system (Duma, 2018:28).

On the association between proper procurement legislation and experience, Brunette and Klaaren's (2020:10) findings contradict the findings of this study. They discovered in their paper on reforming South Africa's public procurement system that even experienced and skilled public procurement officials had difficulty determining which laws apply to which planned procurements. This compels public procurement officials to piece together procurement laws and regulations. As a result, there is a need for a new statutory instrument to govern public procurement in South Africa, because there are numerous drivers of public procurement law reform, as established by Quinot's (2020:3) study when examining South African procurement law.

The findings of Ibem and Laryea (2015:376) confirm this study's finding on the relationship between loss of confidential information and number of years in public sector procurement, as almost all surveyed respondents (including those with less and more experience) recognised security problems pertaining to confidentiality. According to South Africa's e-Government strategy and roadmap, all government departments should be aware of legislative obligations to ensure suitable measures for the protection of confidential information are in place (DTPS, 2017:15).

TABLE 4.98: Relationships between years of service and readiness challenges of e-PP adoption

Variables	Item	Obs	Rank Sum	Rank Mean
Resistance to change	Agree	70	4163.5	59.48
	Disagree	27	1555	57.59
	Neutral	16	722.5	45.16

Chi-squared (corrected for ties) =		2.793	with	2 d.f.	(p = 0.247)	
Poor staff skills	Agree	57			3486.5	61.17
	Disagree	37			2032	54.92
	Neutral	19			922.5	48.55
Chi-squared (corrected for ties) =		2.608	with	2 d.f.	(p = 0.271)	
Transparency of staff	Agree	56			3202	57.18
	Disagree	35			2065.5	59.01
	Neutral	22			1173.5	53.34
Chi-squared (corrected for ties) =		0.456	with	2 d.f.	(p = 0.796)	
Lack of staff enthusiasm	Agree	56			3242.5	57.90
	Disagree	34			1993.5	58.63
	Neutral	23			1205	52.39
Chi-squared (corrected for ties) =		0.650	with	2 d.f.	(p = 0.722)	
Competition from other departments	Agree	25			1407	56.28
	Disagree	48			2882	60.04
	Neutral	40			2152	53.80
Chi-squared (corrected for ties) =		0.902	with	2 d.f.	(p = 0.637)	
Corruption in the procurement process	Agree	52			3089	59.40
	Disagree	30			1803.5	60.12
	Neutral	31			1548.5	49.95
Chi-squared (corrected for ties) =		2.219	with	2 d.f.	(p = 0.330)	
High cost of acquiring the e-PP system	Agree	72			4078	56.64
	Disagree	17			863	50.76
	Neutral	24			1500	62.50
Chi-squared (corrected for ties) =		1.453	with	2 d.f.	(p = 0.484)	
Perceived high cost of running the e-PP system	Agree	77			4389.5	57.01
	Disagree	16			834	52.13
	Neutral	20			1217.5	60.88
Chi-squared (corrected for ties) =		0.708	with	2 d.f.	(p = 0.702)	
Fragmentation of operating systems within government departments	Agree	75			4245.5	56.61
	Disagree	9			387.5	43.06
	Neutral	29			1808	62.34
Chi-squared (corrected for ties) =		2.696	with	2 d.f.	(p = 0.260)	

Influence of procurement policies	Agree	70	4003.5	57.19
	Disagree	16	814	50.88
	Neutral	27	1623.5	60.13
Chi-squared (corrected for ties) =		0.903 with	2 d.f. (p = 0.637)	
Proper procurement legislation	Agree	68	3968.5	58.36
	Disagree	18	924.5	51.36
	Neutral	27	1548	57.33
Chi-squared (corrected for ties) =		0.730 with	2 d.f. (p = 0.694)	
Perception on loss of confidential information	Agree	58	3200	55.17
	Disagree	29	1664	57.38
	Neutral	26	1577	60.65
Chi-squared (corrected for ties) =		0.567 with	2 d.f. (p = 0.753)	

4.6 SUMMARY

Chapter 4 provided a detailed analysis of the data and findings from the various statistical analyses of the primary data collected in order to assess South African government departments' readiness to adopt e-PP. E-PP readiness adoption was assessed on the factors that affect e-PP readiness and the main e-PP readiness challenges. Descriptive analysis using figures and tables helped explain the characteristics of the sample. The factorial structure of the questionnaire was assessed and checked for adequacy (reliability), and inferential statistics were performed.

The dependent variable was e-PP adoption challenges, and the set of independent variables (e-PP readiness factors) included the operating environment, legal environment, economic environment, organisational environment and technical environment. To reduce the number of independent variables, principal component

analysis was performed on the 27 Likert scale questions of Part B of the questionnaire and on 12 Likert scale questions of Part C of the questionnaire using principal component extraction and Varimax rotation to determine the factorial structure of the items. In Part B of the questionnaire, eight factors were retained and accounted for about 67% of total variation of the questionnaire. These factors were later reduced to six through the rotated factor loading analysis. They all affected e-PP adoption and included technology, legal framework, organisation's finance, procurement structure, organisation's leadership, and procurement policy. In Part C of the questionnaire, three factors were retained and accounted for about 64% of the total variation for the questionnaire. These factors affected e-PP adoption challenges and included lack of staff enthusiasm, high cost of e-PP system and lack of proper procurement legislation.

A Chi-square test was used to assess the relationship between the perception of e-PP adoption challenges and its adoption. The results of the Chi-square test showed that that resistance to change; high cost of acquiring the e-PP system; perceived high cost of running the e-PP system; and fragmentation of operating systems have a significant relationship with e-PP adoption. The results also showed that poor staff skills; lack of transparency; lack of enthusiasm; competition from other departments; corruption in the procurement process; influence of procurement policies; proper procurement legislation; and perception on loss of confidential information have no relationship with e-PP adoption.

A Kruskal-Wallis test was also used to determine the relationship between years of service in the public sector procurement/SCM and perceptions of e-PP adoption challenges. The results of the Kruskal-Wallis test indicated that the number of years working in the public sector procurement/SCM environment has no significant relationship with resistance to change; poor staff skills; transparency of staff; lack of staff enthusiasm; competition from other departments; corruption in the procurement process; perceived high cost of running an e-PP system; fragmentation of operating systems within government departments; influence of procurement policies; proper procurement legislation; and perception on loss of confidential information as a readiness challenge to the adoption of the e-PP system.

Both the literature findings in Chapter 2 and the results of empirical findings presented and discussed in Chapter 4 allow for conclusions and recommendations to be made in Chapter 5. Chapter 5 provides the conclusions and recommendations for the study.

CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 INTRODUCTION

Chapter 4 presented and discussed the findings of data analysis. This final chapter aims to draw conclusions on the readiness of government departments to adopt e-PP in South Africa and to propose recommendations. These conclusions and recommendations are guided by the literature review chapter (Chapter 2) and the empirical findings (Chapter 4). This chapter structure starts with the conclusions and recommendations related to each secondary objective, followed by the linking of secondary objectives to questions in the questionnaire, empirical findings, conclusions and recommendations. The chapter then provides the study's limitations, suggests future research and provides a final word.

5.2 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS RELATIVE TO EACH SECONDARY OBJECTIVE

The literature review and empirical findings provide the basis for drawing conclusions and making recommendations in this section, as indicated above. The main objective of the study was to assess the readiness factors of e-PP that affect the adoption challenges in the government departments of South Africa. Two secondary objectives were formulated from the main objective. The answers to each secondary objective are provided, followed by recommendations.

5.2.1 Secondary research objective 1

SRO1: To determine readiness factors that affect the e-PP adoption in South African government departments
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The literature analysis revealed several readiness factors affecting e-PP adoption in organisations. These readiness factors are related to operating, legal, economic and technical environments. In South Africa, a dual procurement system, comprising a paper-based and electronic component, is in operation and circulars and instruction notes serve as legal framework for e-PP adoption. This means that the legal framework is not yet adequately capable of allowing the full use of e-PP because South African legislation governing public procurement does not specifically include e-PP. On the other hand, an e-PP initiative requires a large financial commitment and to maximise investments in e-PP, organisations, irrespective of their organisational size, need to find ways to make their employees accept e-PP. This is because the successful technical implementation of e-PP plays an enabling role in transforming organisational structures and in streamlining public procurement practices.

Conclusion 1: Based on empirical findings, a set of readiness factors that affected the e-PP adoption in South African government departments was created through factor analysis. These readiness factors were technology, legal framework, organisation's finance, procurement structure, leadership, and procurement policy. The factors were extracted based on how they relate to one another; government departments and other

organisations can therefore consider these factors in their e-PP readiness decision making.

Based on the above conclusion, the following recommendations for South African government departments are made:

1. Government departments should determine what ICT infrastructure is required (and where it is insufficient) to support an end-to-end e-PP system;
2. The legal framework governing public procurement should be reformed to provide a consolidated piece of legislation;
3. Government departments should devote significant financial resources to ensuring the successful implementation of the e-PP system, as well as training procurement staff and suppliers;
4. Instead of simply adding e-PP technology to the current procurement system, it should be completely restructured and reformed to become an end-to-end e-PP system;
5. Appropriate leadership support is required to adopt e-PP, as well as to urge and stimulate public procurement officials to develop a positive attitude toward the system's adoption; and
6. Government departments should prioritise public procurement reform and clearly articulate policy reforms in their competing priorities.

5.2.2 Secondary Research objective 2

SRO 2: To determine the readiness challenges of e-PP adoption in South Africa's government departments and how these challenges can be addressed or dealt with

The literature analysis revealed several readiness challenges of e-PP adoption in organisations. These include IT and Internet transaction skills; resistance to change; lack of enthusiasm among staff; mindset change of procurement officials to accept new procurement approaches and practices; establishment of an appropriate and context tailored strategy; and fragmentation of procurement systems. The varying readiness challenges together make e-PP adoption difficult and ineffective.

Conclusion 2: Based on empirical findings, three readiness challenges of e-PP adoption were found in South African government departments. These were created through factor analysis and include lack of staff enthusiasm, high cost of acquiring and running an e-PP system and lack of proper procurement legislation. Government departments need to take the necessary steps to ensure that these readiness challenges are addressed and streamline procurement processes in South Africa's public sector.

Based on the above conclusion, the following recommendations for South African government departments are made:

1. Government departments should make financial commitments to train and develop public procurement officials in e-PP use and IT skills so that they can effectively

transact over the Internet and foster a positive attitude toward e-PP system adoption;

2. The cost elements (including hidden costs) incurred prior to and after e-PP adoption should be known (through e-PP adoption cost analysis) and contained by government departments; and
3. Government departments should create a comprehensive legislative and regulatory framework that supports e-PP. The newly redrafted Public Procurement Bill should incorporate a technology-based approach to procurement processes while also taking all stakeholders' technology needs into account. It is critical to streamline and consolidate public procurement legislation so that there are no loopholes.

5.3 LINKING SECONDARY OBJECTIVES TO QUESTIONS IN THE QUESTIONNAIRE, EMPIRICAL FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Figure 5.1 illustrates the links between the two secondary research objectives and questions pertaining to e-PP readiness in the questionnaire, the empirical findings, as well as the conclusions and recommendations provided in this chapter.

Figure 5.1: Linking secondary objectives to questions in the questionnaire, empirical findings, conclusions and recommendations

5.4 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The following limitations were observed during this study. Firstly, the suspension of all non-COVID-19 research due to the COVID-19 outbreak in South Africa hampered the distribution of questionnaires to public procurement officials. Secondly, the study solely represents the perspectives of public procurement officials employed in the public sector. Thirdly, the literature on scholarly e-PP initiatives is quite limited, implying that e-PP adoption and implementation initiatives in the South African public sector are still in their early phases. The majority of studies have been undertaken in other countries, and this analysis relied on the literature from those studies. Finally, this study was limited to five (5) identified national government departments in South Africa's ministerial clusters. The limitations of this study could open up pathways for many future research studies on defining key characteristics of e-PP that would be appropriate and as well point to some of the developments to be avoided, because adopting e-PP is far more than just a technological challenge. Some suggestions for further research are proposed in the next section.

5.5 SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

This study assessed the readiness factors of e-PP that affect the adoption challenges in South African government departments. Further research is required to build on the existing findings, address gaps in the body of knowledge, and confirm or refute the current

findings (due to the limitations outlined in section 5.5). The following key areas are suggested for further studies:

- to determine the readiness and willingness of suppliers and/or service providers to use e-PP;
- to apply additional research methodology and techniques, such as qualitative approaches and structural equation modelling to obtain rich data and create in-depth analysis and insights from a new viewpoint;
- to compare the private sector's e-PP readiness levels, factors and challenges to those of the public sector;
- to assess the e-PP readiness of all spheres of government (i.e., provincial and municipal levels of government) to discover whether there are substantial e-PP readiness differences;
- to explore the impact of e-PP on society, governments and the business environment; and
- to examine the benefits and shortcomings of e-PP in a digital society.

5.6 A FINAL WORD

The primary research objective of this study was:

To assess the readiness factors of e-PP that affect the adoption challenges in South African government departments

The e-PP readiness factors affecting the adoption challenges in South African government departments were assessed through literature analysis and statistical analysis. It was established empirically that a set of readiness factors affect e-PP adoption in South Africa's government departments. These factors were technology, legal framework, organisation's finance, procurement structure, leadership, and procurement policy. It was also established that government departments face three readiness challenges of e-PP adoption, namely lack of staff enthusiasm, high cost acquiring and running of e-PP system and lack of proper procurement legislation. Therefore, government departments need to prepare in terms of legal framework, finances, staff enthusiasm and training and cost-reduction strategies to fully benefit from e-PP adoption and experience improved efficiency. This can only be possible through the transitioning from paper-based procurement system to a fully implemented e-PP system.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A: Comment box

4.3.4 Comments from public procurement officials

A comment box was included in the questionnaire (V48) for public procurement officials to write down any concerns or opinions on e-PP aspects that were not covered by the questionnaire. As seen in **Table 4.20** below that provides a breakdown of the groupings and percentages of responses, a total of 51 public procurement officials expressed their concerns or opinions about e-PP in the comment box, and other public procurement officials decided not to write their comments because these were optional.

TABLE 4.1019: Breakdown Comments from public procurement officials

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Resistance to change and non-uniformity	5	10%
Lack of skills	6	12%
IT infrastructure	9	18%
IT system integration	3	6%
SCM policies	6	12%
Benefits associated with e-PP adoption	17	33%
Political leadership support	5	10%
Total	51	100%

From the analysis of 51 comments of public procurement officials, the following concerns or opinions were identified and grouped together: (i) resistance to change and non-uniformity, (ii) lack of skills, (iii) IT infrastructure, (iv) IT system integration, (v) SCM policies, (vi) benefits associated with e-PP adoption, and (vii) political leadership support. These concerns or opinions are presented and discussed below to provide a holistic picture of e-PP readiness in government departments.

4.3.4.1 Resistance to change and non-uniformity

Of the 51 public procurement officials who wrote about their concerns or opinions on e-PP, 10% (n=5) showed that there is a reluctance and high level of non-uniformity with regard to the adoption of new information systems. This may be due to fear for safety of information systems and lack of staff preparedness to adopt e-PP. The following concerns or opinions on resistance to change are illustrated in the following excerpts from the public procurement officials:

“Staff are reluctant to try new systems”.

“My main concern is that in my department people are resistant to change and lack of proper planning can affect the change to paperless system on time”.

“My concern is about resistance to change by officials and the safety of the e-PP system in relation to hacking by external people”.

"The problem with government is that there is high non-uniformity"

"Most seniors are not educated or [are] not ready to change, [and] poor ethics [leading to] poor performance...."

The concerns of public procurement officials seem to relate to a lack of education, unreadiness to adopt e-PP, as well as poor ethics and poor performance of public procurement officials. These concerns of public procurement officials corroborate the study's finding in Section 4.3.3.1, which suggests that there is reluctance to change in many government departments and public procurement officers are pleased with the present procurement system. Thus, according to the literature review findings (Section 2.3.3.4), resistance to change is largely motivated by the fear of transitioning to a new system. To address this fear, Toroitich, Mburugu, and Waweru (2017:247) state that government departments must understand why public procurement officials oppose change and find potential solutions. Bausa, Kourtidis, Liljemo, Loozen, Rodrigues and Snaprud (2013:22) and Mundree (2018:24) argue that public procurement officials must be educated about the e-PP system before they can engage in this procurement reform. The researcher agrees with the above suggestion and stresses the need for public procurement officials to be informed about the benefits of e-PP in order for them to embrace the e-PP without any fear or resistance.

According to 41.59% (n=47) of public procurement officials in this study (Section 4.3.2.4.1), ethical challenges in government departments prevent the adoption of e-PP, and government law establishing an e-PP policy should be a tool to combat the stigma of resistance to change and non-uniformity (Sithole, 2017:218). This is why Koech *et al.* (2016:22) advocate for a culture transformation before adopting e-PP.

4.3.4.2 Lack of skills

Table 4.20 shows that 12% (n=6) of public procurement officials indicated that SCM inefficiencies are the product of incompetent public procurement officials who lack expertise and skills. This delays effective e-PP adoption and therefore public procurement officials need to be trained in e-PP. These concerns are highlighted in the following excerpts:

“The competencies and skills of procurement practitioners are not taken into account when any system is being looked into for implementation. Most practitioners have not studied SCM but were dumped in the area from somewhere and they have to learn SCM and therefore changing that mindset and attitude will be a huge challenge”.

“Managers who are heading SCM are not people who are qualified in the field, it’s people from other functions, hence the delay in the adoption of e-PP”.

“inefficiencies in government”

“The issue of training on e-PP is required for staff to be able to operate effectively”.

“Training to [sic] IT and SCM officials is needed because the system is costly and there must allocation budget [sic] to run with the software and equipment”.

“... In general, poor level of skill. Many government employees can't use Excel, and poor policies. If possible, check the IFMS (Integrated Financial Management System) from the National Treasury, it came as the better alternative but never passed the test or implementation because of interference. The current transversal system, BAS, LOGIS, and PERSAL, does not respond to current conditions and is not effective nor efficient”.

The concerns of public procurement officials point to the need for training and continuing support to public procurement officials but, most significantly, for SCM professionalisation. Collaboration between academics, industry associations, the public sector and the private sector, according to Boateng (2017:10), is critical for effective SCM professionalisation in South Africa. This effort will enable the SCM profession to be licensed for competency and conduct by moving SCM staff from practitioners to professionals, because there can be no progress without standards. This effort also calls for a cost-efficiency model in terms of human resources expenditure, provided that, as

the e-PP system is adopted, procurement processes will be streamlined (automated) and less staff will be required. In Section 4.3.3.2, 50.44% (n=57) of public procurement officials acknowledged a skills gap that must be overcome, indicating the need for financial commitments to public procurement official training. This would help to upskill public procurement officials who do not have SCM qualifications but are operating in the SCM sector, and as such diminish procurement capacity and competence (Fourie & Malan, 2020:13).

4.3.4.3 IT infrastructure

Table 4.20 shows that 18% (n=9) of public procurement officials presented the IT infrastructure required for the efficient adoption and functioning of the e-PP system as the greatest challenge to a successful e-PP reform and sustainable development of SMMEs in both cities and rural areas.

“System restrict [sic] users without the proper ICT structure, especially in districts and rural areas”.

“The vast rural nature of most of our country and connectivity poses a real obstacle to implementing electronic systems in government in general. Government is also currently reliant on old legacy systems [sic] that are an obstacle to systems integration. There needs to be an overall modernisation of government’s operating systems to ensure effective implementation of e-PP”.

“The IT infrastructure of the Department is very poor”.

“My concern is, what will happen in rural areas where there will be no network coverage for days? How will officials operate and how will local business benefit? It looks as if businesses from cities will continue dominance over rural businesses”.

“Connectivity challenges in rural areas as well as technological challenges experienced by SMMEs”.

“I think the department must fix the IT infrastructure system of the department, then we will talk about EPP. With the current status it is unfortunate”.

“As much as the Government is on [sic] process of fully introducing the e-PP model, the challenge will be the Suppliers that the Government is trying to empower. Our country is behind when coming to advanced technology. It will be fruitless when Suppliers failed to respond on e-PP. Another challenge will be the overloading of the system, as result it may crush, which may delay the service delivery. The society at large, must be also be educated, and be able to buy in the whole process of e-PP”.

“Technological considerations including supplier capacity and capability constraints affecting fairness, equity, transparency, competitiveness and cost-

effectiveness, particularly with respect to SMMEs; security, privacy and confidentiality requirements; minimum configuration requirements; accessibility and connectivity issues particularly in rural areas; data pricing; intermittent interruptions in connectivity”.

“E-PP adoption not the same in all provinces. All provinces to at least be getting a basic network and IT desktops and laptops to start working on”.

IT infrastructural challenges, as excerpted above named by public procurement officials, would have an effect on the ability of suppliers to engage in e-PP due to lack of Internet connectivity in and around the underdeveloped (poor) regions of South Africa. This view is consistent with and confirmed by Mose, Njihia and Peterson’s (2013:593) findings that indicate that a lack of Internet connectivity between businesses and consumers would result in non-participation in procurement processes. The obsolete state of government IT infrastructure would also influence government departments’ participation in e-PP, thereby affecting service delivery and posing a barrier to system integration (Kramer, 2016:18; Duma, 2018:60). According to Sithole (2017:57), the use of e-PP is largely reliant on the availability, nature, and capacity of current infrastructure. This requires the development of an e-PP system with adequate and appropriate IT infrastructure to service both the buyer (governmental departments) and the seller (suppliers) (De la Harpe, 2015:1588).

The findings in Section 4.3.2.5.8 attributed the technical challenges to the current procurement system (dual - paper-based and electronic-based features) and revealed the need for a full e-PP overhaul in order to reform public procurement in light of emerging technological capability and improve the efficiency of public procurement processes. The technological environment is concerned with the government putting in place the necessary infrastructure at all levels (rural and urban) in order to efficiently disseminate the e-PP service.

4.3.4.4 IT system integration

A lack of IT system compatibility in procurement management, as expressed by 6% (n=3) of public procurement officials in **Table 4.20**, creates a challenge in combining the existing procurement process with the desired e-PP systems. The following problems linked to IT system integration were indicated:

“I think provincial and national departments should only use 1 system. Maybe payment of 30 days to suppliers will improve and other integration of payment system”.

“This will also help in improving government integrated systems, thereby improve service delivery. Moreover, makes it simple for departments to do business among each other”.

“Central Supplier Database is a joke at the moment, no checking of companies or individuals that register. One person registers for 20 commodities, not possible. This makes our work so much harder with procurement and open to fraud. The system should clean this system up first”.

The above comments of public procurement officials just stressed what was found in Section 4.3.3.9 suggesting that the disintegration of IT systems is a readiness challenge in the adoption of e-PP. This finding is supported by the National Treasury report (2015:59), as already indicated in the section above. It can therefore be noted that end-to-end e-PP adoption is a potential approach for promoting more integrated and open processes (Siita, 2014:11; Opong, 2020:27).

In their study that investigates the utilisation of the CSD, Mpehle and Mudogwa’s (2020:8) findings also confirmed the above comments on technological barriers of the CSD stating that the CSD should place a limit on the number of commodities that each supplier may register in order to allow emerging SMEs to focus on their main business activities. The findings of Zitha, Sebola, and Mamabolo (2016:67) suggest that CSD will go a long way toward resolving inconsistencies such as the rotation method in selecting suppliers, the limit on the number of commodities and industry classifications.

4.3.4.5 SCM policies

The results of **Table 4.20** show that 12% (n=6) of public procurement officials stressed that the effective and efficient adoption of e-PP depends on the adequacy of the relevant regulations to permit and regulate e-PP. As South Africa has a minimum standard of provision in the legislative and regulatory framework that does not support e-PP adoption, changes to the legal environment are likely to contribute to the introduction of the Public Procurement Bill.

“The main issue on e-Procurement is the legislation that still requires that we all evaluate in the same environment and that tender documents are opened by the SCM unit in front of the evaluators”.

“New legislation like Public Procurement Bill must enable technological approach in the implementation of procurement processes”.

“Government policies are restricting and does not allow exploring or challenging other avenues. Or allow youngsters or youth to come up with new innovative procedures”.

“Contradictory regulations and legislation. Departments may be ready to move, however the Supplier's readiness to accept new methods poses risk of change. Auditors' (internal and external) methodologies do not allow for the move from paper base to electronic. Any Procurement system customised to the needs of government has been proven to be extremely

expensive (SAP, Walker, Oracle - New IFMS base). SITA legislation does not enhance future - but cheaper enhancements in IT infrastructure. This adds to the cost of running systems in Government”.

“Will the Auditor General be accepting e-PP paper trail for audit purposes without decrying limitation of scope”.

“Our regulations are not supporting e-PP”.

Concerns or opinions of public procurement officials suggest the SCM policies are to be amended and enforced to improve procurement process efficiency. The legal framework, as confirmed by the results in Section 4.3.2.2, is not properly capable of enabling the full use of e-PP since the public sector lacks e-PP enforcing policies and legislation, leaving the desire to embrace e-PP dependent on government departments (Sithole, 2017:52). The newly redrafted Public Procurement Bill, which was recently issued for public comments, should allow for a technology-based approach to procurement process implementation. This is based on the findings of Kramer (2016:30) and Anthony (2018:47) suggesting that in order for e-PP to deliver the intended benefits, a thorough and supporting legal and regulatory structure is required. To get support for automating (e-PP) procurement processes, the redrafted legislative framework must take into account all stakeholders (including auditors and suppliers).

Another source of concern affecting the efficiency of public procurement processes negatively is the current operating systems (LOGIS, Intenda, Procure to Pay, Hardcat, ISP, and SAP, among others) used by South African government departments, which are underutilised and vary in functionality and performance. The legislation of the State Information Technology Agency (SITA) must be in step with the National Treasury's developments in order to replace these old enterprise resource type systems. This would aid government to reduce operating cost and effort duplication, as well as uncertainty and challenges in procurement decision-making (Dza, Fisher & Gapp, 2013:51).

4.3.4.6 Benefits associated with e-PP adoption

The majority (33%, n=17) of public procurement officials recognised the benefits associated with e-PP adoption in government departments, claiming that the introduction of e-PP would reduce the administrative burden on both government and suppliers, retain the integrity of SCM and reduce costs and corruption. It will also ensure transparency in procurement processes in the public sector. The following are the benefits associated with e-PP adoption, as indicated by public procurement officials:

“E-PP will help in eliminating corruption in the public sector procurement”.

“E-PP is the way to go in order to save costs and mostly time”.

“E-PP will make life easier since there will be no paper work, but it will be a challenge to clients since some are not well skilled when it comes to the computer”.

“Using of e-PP will reduce environmental problems like pollution and storage costs since less papers will be printed and procurement procedures will be digitalised”.

“E-PP will be good for transformation of procurement in government departments”.

“I think the concept is great. It could assist with transparency and eliminating paper-based activities. The only down fall [sic] for me would be accessibility of the system by suppliers, especially those from poor backgrounds. If the government had invested in infrastructure for an ordinary citizen, this would be a great concept but as we stand should the government go for the e-PP route, many ordinary citizens would fall within the cracks”.

“The e-PP is reliable in the sense that it is able to keep evidence of all the necessary supporting /information documents that one may need especially during audit periods. Government officials will be forced to expedite their processes since the system is able to indicate where and who caused the delay. The e-PP is more useful in terms of contract management, i.e., it is

able to link a purchase order number to the set budget of a particular procurement item which prevents overpaying”.

“If properly implemented, e-PP will assist government departments in ensuring transparency and shorten turnaround times for the procurement process. In addition, e-PP will assist with reporting, dashboards at a press of a button”.

“The e-PP saves times and it is efficient. You can also work from home and has audit trail”.

“I recommend a shift from the current paper-based procurement system to e-PP. It may lead to cost reduction, improved transparency, and accountability, among others, hence I fully agree that it is needed. For example, In Kenya, they have adopted e-Procurement but there are several functions they still perform manually such as tender process and auction that take place in Asset section. Many procuring entities have failed to embrace the culture of e-procurement, while some organisations are likely to overstate the extent to which they deploy the use of e-procurement. Hence, there is need for an enhanced, automated and interlinked procurement system that will lead to improved competitiveness and will be cost effective to the parties concerned. Davis, Bagozzi and Warshaw (1989) found in a study that more than 50% of procurement activities in

procuring firms are conducted manually. Akinyi (2010) reiterated that the manual process of carrying out procurement functions is most times expensive, slow, inefficient, while data storage and retrieval has not been encouraging. According to the Epiq Technologies (2010) report, adoption of e-procurement technology in an organisation enables a firm to organise its interactions with its most crucial suppliers, monitoring tools to help control costs, and keeping an open line of communication with potential suppliers during a business process. Government needs to have a budget for upgrading procurement systems. The following needs to be attended: Availability of ICT equipment Training Ensure Authenticity Collaboration between suppliers and Government Procurement Risks performance.”[sic]

“The introduction of e-PP will be very much welcomed by departments as it will give control and access of information to individual departments as compared to paper-based procurement. This will also ensure that there are no lost pape work and everything will be transparent which will in turn reduce incidents of corruption”.

“No more supplier relationship. Rotation of suppliers encourage. Paperless solution will result in more productivity and cost savings”.

“This should be the direction to fully implement the principles of section 217 of the constitution and will allow continuous and proper reporting to measure are [sic] effective the South African procurement is”.

“It will make the working life of supply chain officials easy because one could work from any place and it will speed up service delivery”.

“Due to current circumstances or condition e-PP will resolve all problems which we are encountering and people will be able to perform their function effectively and efficiency whenever they are and the system should have proper audit tray. I strongly support immigration from paper based procurement to e-PP.” [sic]

“I think considering the challenges of COVID 19 it is a way to go”.

“Technology helps to keep every information and makes things easy”.

Benefits can only be realised if the challenges associated with the adoption of e-PP are handled correctly. This means that, among other things, the necessary laws, regulations, and policies must be developed and thoroughly executed. According to National Treasury’s Director-General Lungisa Fuzile (2015:1) in his preface to the 2015 Public Sector SCM review, the benefits of procurement reform (including e-PP adoption) will be significant if it is in compliance with Section 217 of the Constitution. Ambe (2016:277)

asserts that for the South African government to reap the full benefits of reformed procurement processes, a common vision among key players, ethical leadership and the creation of sophisticated curriculum are required.

Adoption of e-PP provides a number of benefits for both suppliers and the government (Kramer, 2016:7; Koech *et al.*, 2016:21). It is therefore important for this study to assess the readiness of South African government departments to adopt e-PP (by identifying factors that affect e-PP readiness, levels of e-PP readiness and challenges of e-PP readiness) in order to realise these benefits.

4.3.4.7 Political leadership support

Table 4.20 shows that 10% (n=5) of public procurement officials indicated a need for adequate political leadership support to change the legal and regulatory framework that would allow e-PP to be adopted. Some public procurement officials suggest that leadership in the public sector should reposition SCM from being a supportive or enabling function to be a strategic function. This is because if SCM is not well handled, the strategic direction of the organisation would be compromised. This is supported by the following the quotes extracted from public procurement officials' comments:

“E-PP is doable provided there is an enthusiasm and political will from the highest appointed executive. The fragmented implementation of partial e-PP evidenced in government departments [and other public] entities short

charges the potential benefits that could be received from full implementation of the e-PP”.

“At this point the issues are not so much people driven but leadership and understanding of e-procurement. The paper-based [procurement system] itself is not even streamlined nor clear in policy implementation. If we go online, it will simply be garbage in garbage out. This is not about the system we choose it is about the process flow of procurement and the value chain of procurement being aligned to legislation in all of government. That is where we must begin. Then buying a system will be a possibility”.

“The attitude of procurement not being considered as a strategic tool or mechanism to enhance efficiency and effectiveness, results in procurement being manipulated and also buy-in from senior management and policy makers”.

“IFMS/NT (Integrated Financial Management System / National Treasury) prevents departments from procuring and implementing e-PP systems”.

“There is a serious lack of political will to make the public procurement system fair, open, transparent and equitable and competitive”.

It emerges that adequate political leadership support is needed in the revision of the legal and regulatory framework that would allow for e-PP adoption. The Asian Development Bank (2013:65) conducted an e-PP handbook study and found that political leadership and sponsorship are essential components in developing and sustaining e-PP in the public sector. In a case study on pioneering e-PP in Rwanda, The World Bank (2018:5) found that political will promotes ICT-based development. The study highlights that Rwanda's procurement reform began with the adoption of new procurement legislation followed by the recruitment of knowledgeable leaders from one of the world's most sophisticated e-PP systems (Republic of Korea). Manyathi (2019:72) examined procurement practices in South Africa and revealed that 89% of those surveyed confirmed that there is political pressure in SCM, which in most cases leads to non-compliance with public procurement prescripts.

One of the numerous challenges to the successful adoption and implementation of e-PP systems in Africa is a lack of political will to fully commit to procurement reforms (Dza *et al.*, 2013:54). Based on these findings, it is clear that having political leadership support to develop and implement the required legislative and regulatory framework to enable an e-PP system is critical to its success. South Africa needs to go through political transformation in order to gain support from the highest political levels for successful e-PP readiness.

Based on the above discussion, it became clear that public procurement officials in government departments are unprepared and unwilling to adopt e-PP due to a lack of

education, poor ethics and poor performance. With training and ongoing support for public procurement officials, as well as professionalisation of SCM, the SCM profession will be able to be certified for competency and conduct. It also emerged from the comments that IT infrastructure challenges would have an effect on suppliers' capacity to engage in e-PP due to a lack of Internet connection in and around South Africa's underdeveloped (poor) regions. According to the comments or opinions, the adoption of the e-PP should streamline the procurement process as well as thoroughly establish and enforce SCM policies in order to achieve procurement efficiency. The findings also suggest that e-PP adoption benefits may be realised only if the challenges associated with e-PP adoption are managed appropriately and consistently. Public procurement officials believe that adequate political leadership support is required for the revision of the legislative and regulatory framework that would allow for the adoption of e-PP.

Appendix B: Ethical Clearance

Tshwane University
of Technology

Faculty of Management Sciences Research Ethics Committee [FCRE-ECO]

The TUT Research Ethics Committee is a registered Institutional Review Board (IRB 00005968) with the US Office for Human Research Protections (IORG# 0004997) (Expires 30 Jan 2020). Also, it has Federal Wide Assurance for the Protection of Human Subjects for International Institutions (FWA 00011501) (Expires 22 Jan 2019). In South Africa It is registered with the National Health Research Ethics Council (REC-160509-21). The FCRE-ECO is a subcommittee of the TUT Research Ethics Committee

Date: 11 June 2020

Ref #: FCRE2020/FR/04/003-MS
Name: Maepa DN
Student #: 214185679

Mr DN Maepa
C/o Dr MF Mpanya (D Tech)
Marketing, Supply Chain and Sport Management
Faculty of Management Sciences

Dear Ms Maepa

Title: Assessment of electronic public procurement readiness in government departments

Investigator: DN Maepa

Programme: M Tech: Logistics

Supervisor: Dr MF Mpanya (D Tech)

Co-supervisor: Dr TB Phume (D Tech)

Thank you for submitting your application for ethics clearance.

In reviewing your application for ethics approval, all relevant documents and corrections are duly noted

The proposed research project may now continue with the proviso that:

- 1) The researcher will conduct the study according to the procedures and methods indicated in the approved proposal, particularly in terms of any undertakings and/or assurances made regarding the confidentiality of the collected data.
- 2) The researcher will act within the parameters of any applicable national legislation, professional codes of conduct, institutional guidelines and scientific standards relevant to the specific field of study.
- 3) Kindly note that the mentioned documents will be sent to the TUT-REC for ratification

Type of Decision:

The Faculty of Management Sciences Research Ethics Committee reviewed the documents at its meeting on **03 June 2020**. The study is **Approved**.

Note:

The reference number [top right corner of this communiqué] should be clearly indicated on all forms of communication [e.g. Webmail, E-mail messages, letters] with the intended research participants.

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The Committee wishes you well with your research endeavours.

AT Roux (Prof)
Chairperson
Faculty Committee Research Ethics
Email: RouxAT@tut.ac.za
Tel: 012 382 4750/5824
[Ref#: FCRE2020/FR/04/003-MS]

cc Supervisor/HoD/etc.

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Appendix C: Information letter

**Tshwane University
of Technology**

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FACULTY OF MANAGEMENT SCIENCES

DEPARTMENT OF MARKETING, SUPPLY CHAIN
& SPORT MANAGEMENT

PROJECT TITLE: ASSESSMENT OF ELECTRONIC PUBLIC PROCUREMENT READINESS IN GOVERNMENT DEPARTMENTS

M-Tech Logistics candidate: Mr. DN Maepa

Student #: 214185679

Study leader: Dr. M.F. Mpwanya, D-Tech Logistics, Department of M.S.S, Tshwane University of Technology, Pretoria.

Dear Potential research participant,

You are invited to participate in the research study that forms part of my formal MTech studies at the Tshwane University of Technology. The title of my study is: *Assessment of electronic public procurement readiness in government departments*. The information below will help you to understand the purpose of this study and will allow you to decide whether you would like to participate or not.

The main objective of this study is to assess electronic public procurement (e-PP) readiness in South African government departments to transition from paper based, manual methods, transaction processing and communication to e-PP. From the main objective, the following are the secondary objectives:

- To determine factors that affect the e-PP readiness in South African government departments.
- To determine e-PP readiness challenges in South African government departments and identify ways to address them.

Please take note of the following:

- **Participation:** Participation is voluntary, and you have the right to withdraw your participation in the research at any point and there is no need to explain why.
- **Time:** Completing the questionnaire will take approximately 15 minutes -or less – of your time.
- **Confidentiality:** All information obtained will be treated strictly confidentially, stored for 5 years at the Tshwane University of Technology, used for the purposes of this study only; and **no** personal details (such as address, contact number etc.) will be required. Once information is obtained, the study account of the project will be closed to allow information to be removed from the survey monkey database.
- **Ethical clearance:** The Faculty Committee for Postgraduate Studies and the Research Ethics Committee of the Tshwane University of Technology have approved this formal study proposal. The ethics clearance number can be made available should you have any questions, or need additional information regarding this research, please do not hesitate to contact the chair of the TUT Research Ethics Committee. Prof WA Hoffmann, Chair: TUT Research Ethics Committee
Tel: 012 3826246 or me. Master Student DN Maepa Email: 214185679@tut4life.ac.za Cell: 079 271 6198.

The Tshwane University of Technology stipulates that any person willing to participate and be surveyed by a staff member or by a registered student, should give his or her consent and, by participating in this survey, you are automatically giving your consent to participate in this research study.

Thank you for your willingness to participate.

Appendix D: Survey questionnaire

GENERAL INSTRUCTIONS

You are kindly requested to answer **all** questions and complete **all** sections of the questionnaire by placing an (X) to the number that represents your answer(s).

Example of how to complete this questionnaire:

Gender

If you are female:

Female	X
Male	

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Part A: Respondent demographic profile information:

In this section, we kindly request your personal information. Kindly tick the appropriate box for your response.

1. What is your age group?

[V1]

18 – 25 Years	
26 – 35 Years	
36 – 45 Years	
46 – 60 Years	
61 and above	

2. What is your gender?

[V2]

Male	
Female	
Other	

3. What is your highest level of education you have completed?

[V3]

Grade 12/Matric	NQF 4	
N6 Certificate	NQF 5	
National Diploma/Diploma	NQF 6	
Bachelor's degree/Advanced Diploma/B Tech	NQF 7	
Honours Degree/Post Graduate Diploma	NQF 8	
Master's Degree	NQF 9	
Doctoral Degree	NQF 10	

4. What is the name of the government department you work for? Please write it in full? [V4]

5. What is your designation within your department? One option only.

[V5]

Administration clerk	
Administration officer	
Assistant director	
Deputy director	

Director	
Chief director	
Chief financial officer	
Other (please specify)	

6. Which supply chain management unit/division do you work in? [V6]

Demand management	
Acquisition management	
Logistics management	
Disposal management	
Risk management	
Other (please specify)	

7. How long have you been working in public-sector procurement/supply chain management? [V7]

Less than 1 Year	
1 – 4 Years	
5 – 7 Years	
8 – 10 Years	
More than 11 Years	

8. How would you rate your knowledge of the Internet? [V8]

Very poor	
Reasonably poor	
Average	
Reasonably good	
Very good	

Part B: Factors that affect the e-PP readiness in South African government departments

This section assesses factors that affect the e-PP readiness in South African government departments. You are asked to indicate to what extent you agree or disagree with the statements below by ticking an (X) on an option, using the five-point Likert scale where 5 represents “strongly agree”, and 1 represents “strongly disagree”

1. Operating environment

The procurement environment sees elements of e-PP support levels, drivers of e-PP adoption and procurement structures that currently operate with dual paradigm, partially paper-based, and some

electronic features. With the five-point Likert scale where 5 represents “strongly agree”, and 1 represents “strongly disagree”, indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements.

		5	4	3	2	1	
1.1	The government’s procurement policy hinders implementation of e-PP system.						V9
1.2	The government’s procurement structural system is favorable to the adoption of e-PP.						V10
1.3	The use of partial electronic features (i.e. Central Supplier Database and eTender publication portal) inhibits the adoption of full e-PP system.						V11
1.4	The overall level of e-PP adoption in the public sector affects your decision to implement the system in your government department.						V12

2. Legal environment

Legal environment considers the national and international jurisdiction in terms of readiness and recognition of regulations and policies to align e-PP with manual procurement and comply with a fair, transparent, competitive and cost-effective e-PP system. With the five-point Likert scale where 5 represents “strongly agree”, and 1 represents “strongly disagree”, indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements.

		5	4	3	2	1	
2.1	National legislations inhibit the adoption of e-PP in your department.						V13
2.2	International laws hinder the adoption of e-PP in your department.						V14
2.3	The current South African legal framework is favorable to the adoption of e-PP.						V15
2.4	The anticipated changes to the South African legal framework affect the adoption of e-PP.						V16
2.5	The South African government provides a favorable legal framework in order to adopt e-PP.						V17

3. Economic environment

The economic environment concerns both the buyer and the supplier, who should be able to meet the costs of implementing and running the e-PP system, and the financial commitment with e-PP adoption benefits from the financial investment. With the five-point Likert scale where 5 represents “strongly agree”, and 1 represents “strongly disagree”, indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements.

		5	4	3	2	1	
3.1	The operating costs of your department have decreased since the inception of partial electronic features (i.e. Central Supplier Database and eTender publishing portal).						V18
3.2	Financial challenges have hindered adoption and speed of implementing e-PP system.						V19
3.3	There are perceived hidden costs (short term or long term) that hinder the adoption of e-PP.						V20
3.4	There are economic challenges sourcing for clients to use the e-PP system.						V21

4. Organisational environment

Organisational environment focuses on the planned level of adoption, the essentiality of awareness for e-PP potential impact on organisational performance and the need to understand the antecedents of employees' acceptance. With the five-point Likert scale where 5 represents "strongly agree", and 1 represents "strongly disagree", indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements.

		5	4	3	2	1	
4.1	There are ethical challenges in the department that hinders adoption of e-PP.						V22
4.2	The negative attitude of employees towards adoption of e-PP system is a hindrance to implementation in the department.						V23
4.3	There are transparency challenges in the department about adoption of e-PP.						V24
4.4	There are accountability issues in the adoption of e-PP in the department.						V25
4.5	A leadership gap in the department hinders e-PP adoption.						V26
4.6	System implementation is a problem in the department.						V27

5. Technological environment

The technology environment is concerned with the government setting up the required infrastructure at all levels to effectively and efficiently disseminate the e-PP service. With the five-point Likert scale where 5 represents "strongly agree", and 1 represents "strongly disagree", indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements.

		5	4	3	2	1	
5.1	There are challenges regarding preparedness when migrating from paper-based to e-PP.						V28
5.2	There are system incompatibilities when implementing the new IT system in your department.						V29
5.3	The department is not well equipped in terms of systems software infrastructure.						V30
5.4	The department's network system is inadequate for e-PP operations.						V31
5.5	The staff is inadequately prepared to work with the new IT system and the Internet.						V32
5.6	The staff is inadequately skilled in ICT to deal with e-PP system.						V33
5.7	The department integrates its IT system with other directorates within the department.						V34
5.8	There are technical challenges in the e-PP system that hinder its adoption.						V35

Part C: Readiness challenges to e-PP adoption in South Africa's government departments

The readiness challenges associated with the adoption of an e-PP system will shed light on the critics that need to be looked into to ensure successful e-PP adoption. With the five-point Likert scale where 5 represents "strongly agree", and 1 represents "strongly disagree", indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements.

		5	4	3	2	1	
1.1	Resistance to change.						V36
1.2	Poor staff skills.						V37
1.3	Transparency of staff.						V38
1.4	Lack of staff enthusiasm.						V39
1.5	Competition from other departments.						V40
1.6	Corruption in the procurement process.						V41
1.7	High cost of acquiring the e-PP system.						V42
1.8	Perceived high cost of running the e-PP system.						V43
1.9	Fragmentation of operating systems within government departments (Oracle, SAP, ATC, etc.)						V44
1.10	Influence of procurement policies.						V45
1.11	Proper procurement legislation.						V46
1.12	Perception on loss of confidential information.						V47

1.13 Given the above-mentioned readiness challenges to e-PP adoption, would you recommend a shift from the current paper-based procurement system to e-PP? [V48]

Yes	
No	
Do not know	

1.14 If you have any concern or opinion about e-PP other than what has been stated, please write down here: [V49]

.....
.....
.....
.....

Thank you for completing the questionnaire.